

CORK BIRD REPORT

2019–23

Cork Bird Report Editorial Team

Cork Bird Report 2019–23

Edited by Cork Bird Report Editorial Team:
Mark Shorten, Paul Moore, Tom Gittings, Jim Wilson, and Harry Hussey

Front cover: Collared Pratincole. *Glareola pratincola*, the Gearagh, March 2020, R.T. Mills
Frontispiece: Redwing *Turdus iliacus*, Dursey Island, April 2025, M. Shorten

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Common Buzzard *Buteo buteo*
Harper's Island; Mark Shorten

The Cork Bird Report was the first annual county bird report published in Ireland. Though not published annually, reports covered all the years from 1963 through to 2006, apart from 1972–75. The most recent issues, 1996–2004 (368 pages) and 2005–6 (181 pages), were by far the largest and most comprehensive reports. Previous Cork Bird Reports are available at <https://birdwatchcork.com/publications/>

In previous reports, observations were requested from observers (or extracted from them) and supplied in written format or spreadsheet. Apart from records published in the Irish Rare Bird Report, most records here have been downloaded from Irishbirding.com, eBird, BirdTrack, and i-WeBS. There has been a rapid increase in eBird and BirdTrack records, and this has allowed for the first time to create species mapping in the county with some confidence (Tom Gittings). These are

Fig 1. Number of Cork records for BirdTrack and eBird 2019–25

	BirdTrack	eBird
2019	8466	17389
2020	11545	13144
2021	9804	14384
2022	9068	20674
2023	12074	43841
2024	11540	44708
2025	10401	40785

eBird - 2km squares with records

not atlas maps but give a view on the distribution of species between Atlas projects. Not all species are covered in this report, but the majority are.

i-WeBS data was collated by Tom Gittings. For trends on these species, check <https://www.npws.ie/sites/default/files/publications/pdf/irish-wildlife-manual-162.pdf>.

The main sources for this report are (with acknowledgments): the Irish Rare Bird Report, irishbirding.com (Joe Doolan), Birdguides (Josh Jones), BirdTrack (Scott Mayson), eBird, Cape Clear Bird Observatory, annual logs (the late Steve Wing and Brian Caffery), Birds of Dursey (the late Derek Scott), Birds of West Beara (Kieran Grace), Alan McCarthy, Allan Mee, and Claire Heardman.

New species added to County Cork bird list – five-year periods – 1959–2023

This report should be read in conjunction with The Birds of County Cork (Smiddy P., Shorten M and Heselden R. 2022. CUP)

Twelve new species and one subspecies were added to the county list. New additions to the county list keep on coming but at a lower rate than in previous periods.

2019

Two-barred Warbler, Dursey Island, 1st Irish

Short-billed Dowitcher, Clonakilty
Semipalmated Plover, Lissagriffin
Horned Lark, Dursey Island

2020

Brown Shrike, Rathduff
Collared Pratincole, the Gearagh
Northern Harrier, Barry's Head
Belted Kingfisher, Dunboy

2022

Scopoli's Shearwater, off Baltimore 1st Irish

2021

Greater Sand Plover, Rossbrin Cove

2023

Penduline Tit, the Geragh, first Irish record
American Cliff Swallow, Garnish Point
Iberian Chiffchaff, Caher East, Mizen Head

Some lows and highs of 2019–23

No Twite recorded in 2019–23.	Great Spotted Woodpecker breeding again.
Last pair of Curlew in NW of the county.	Breeding seabirds generally increasing.
No Lapwing breeding.	Two Snowy Owls, first since 1827.
Hen Harrier continues to decline as breeding species.	Influx of shearwaters, climate related.
Some wader and wildfowl species continue to decline.	Influx of herons and Glossy Ibis, climate related.
A single unobserved Bewick's Swan (satellite tracked).	Publication of Birds of County Cork.
Continued decline of Turtle Dove as a migrant.	Increase in range of Reed Warbler and possibly Cetti's Warbler.
Some friends lost including Steve Wing and Julian Wyllie.	Success of Harper's Island Nature Reserve.
Continued decline in arable land and the sound of rock breakers in west Cork taking rough ground for dairy farming.	Continued increase of Osprey records. Clogheen and White's Marsh to be managed for wildlife.
A single Corncrake.	Chough population stable.
	Substantial increase in records received.
	Return of breeding White-tailed Eagle.

Brent Goose light-bellied *Branta b. hrota*

Brent Goose light-bellied - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24-1

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	165	98	272	105	136	185	135
Ballymacoda	112	54	150	58		132	
Cork Harbour	69	16	152	4	62	34	83
Ballycotton Shanagarry	67	71	45	89	106	75	40
Courtmacsherry, Broadstrand & Dunworley	33	29	45	45	30	28	
Clonakilty Bay	20	9	27	16	26	28	11

Brent Goose Dark-bellied *Branta b. bernicla*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
39	0	7	32

With seven previous records for Dark-bellied Brent, thirty-two is a considerable increase, probably reflecting an increase in Pale-bellied Brent *Branta b. hrota*. Ballingalanna on 3 February 2019; Ballycotton on 14 March 2020; Ballycotton on 6 February 2022; Ballycotton from 14–18 October 2023; Ballymacoda on 6 February 2022; Broadstrand on 2 February 2022; Cape Clear on 4 November 2019; ten birds at Clonakilty from 10 January to 5 February 2023; one at Clonakilty on 8 December 2023; two at Dunwhorley on 9 February 2019; two at Knockadoon on 14 January 2020; one at Rosscarbery on 23–30 December 2021.

Canada Goose *Branta canadensis*

Small numbers of feral birds, with a maximum of up to six birds at Rostellan from 29 October 2019 to 12 January 2020. One to two birds also recorded at Kilcolman, Garinish Point, The Lough, Ballycotton, Cuskinny and Pilmore. No evidence of breeding.

Barnacle Goose *Branta leucopsis*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
270	-	238	32

A typical spread of migrant records - thirty-two birds in total, peaking in late September and October, with a maximum of seven at the Old Head of Kinsale on 29 September 2021. A bird was present at Toons Bridge in the winters of 2020/21 and 2023/24 with three at the Sulane Delta from 4 November 2021 to 19 February 2022.

Greylag Goose *Anser anser*

Almost all records are from the naturalised populations, which appear to be doing well. There were at least fifteen counts of 100 birds or more from Kilcolman (max 150) and presumably the same population at Churchtown; the Gearagh (250 birds on 4 September 2020, not i-WeBS count) and Toons Valley.

A flock of seven birds on 28 October 2019 at Ballybranigan is one of the few records that may be of wild Icelandic race birds.

Peak annual counts of feral Greylag Goose flocks during the period

2016/17 to 2019/20, compared to peak counts during the 2007/08 survey by Boland & Crowe (2008). From Burke (2022 and 2025)

Flock	16/17	17/18	18/19	19/20	20/21	21/22	22/23	peak	07/08
Cork City		28	20	1				28	83
Inishcarra Reservoirs	135	120	168	163	180	250	174	168	42
North Cork		100	150	100				150	111

Pink-footed Goose *Anser brachyrhynchus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
230	0	107	133

A total of 133 birds surpasses the total of birds from the first record in 1974 to 2018. The majority of birds occur in October on the coast as passage migrants. There were flocks of fifteen at Toormore and twelve at Mizen Head on 14 and 15 October 2023 respectively, with forty-two in that month.

Pink-footed Goose *Anser brachyrhynchus* Cape Clear, October 2022, J.Lynch

Birds were also recorded at Lissagriffin, the Gearagh, Sands Cove, Ballycotton, and Galley Head. A flock of about ten birds was recorded at two sites in Cork City with passive acoustic recording on 23 September 2023 - recording here - <https://xeno-canto.org/590451>.

One or two birds have wintered at Toons Bridge since 2020/21. Five birds remained at Aghamilla, near Clonakilty, from 2 November 2021 until 19 February 2022. One wintered near Bantry from January to April 2022.

Pink-footed Goose – 2019–23

Greater White-fronted Goose *Anser albifrons* | (subspecies: *flavirostris*; *albifrons*)

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
-	-	-	11

Formerly a regular winter flock at Kilcolman, now a scarce migrant and winter visitor. Eleven birds were recorded in 2019–23.

Two at Cahermore on 27 February 2020; one at Churchtown on 2 January 2022; Kilcolman from 20 January to 18 April 2021; five at Turk Head on 6 April 2020; one at Lough Cluhir from 18 January to 28 February 2020.

One bird of the European/Russian race *Anser a. albifrons* - at Toons Bridge from 18 October 2020 remained until 14 March 2021, presumed same 17 November 2021 to 13 February 2022. A bird at the Gearagh from 13–22 November 2020, is presumed to be the Toons Bridge bird.

Mute Swan *Cygnus olor*

Mute Swan - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24-1

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total	292	276	234	235	262	328	359
mean_peak							
Inishcarra Reservoirs	75	46	42	84	127	73	87
Cork Harbour	57	44	47	40	64	66	63
Ballyhonock Lough	44	26	64	28		41	45
Ballybutler Lake	42	61	9	2		56	41
Clonakilty Bay	37	37	32	18	49	30	36
Bantry Bay	28	23	31	0	22	21	44

Rosscarbery	26	38	24	16	30	20	16
Lough Aderry	23	48	25	4		9	9
Lough Cluhir	21	13	23	6	17	25	25
Bandon River	16	4			4	28	27

Bewick's Swan *Cygnus columbianus* (subspecies: bewickii; columbianus)

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
-	-	-	1

On 30 November 2023, a single satellite-tracked Bewick's Swan (Peter) arrived from England and flew as far west as Whitegate, stopping for 20 minutes at Ballymacoda and moving to east to Wexford. The bird remained in Wexford until 2 December before returning to winter in the Fens, East Anglia, in England. <https://zwerorschwan.de/en/bewicks-swans-on-the-move-the-map>

This bird, unobserved by birders, was the first Cork record since a flock of up to seven birds was at Ballymacoda from 9 December 2010 until 11 January 2011. Formerly a regular winter visitor, with regular flocks of a hundred or more birds up to the early 1990s.

Whooper Swan *Cygnus cygnus*

The 2020 International Swan Survey (Burke *et al.* 2021) found 488 birds in Cork, 12% of which were juveniles. This represented a 100% increase on the 2015 survey, while there was a 26.5% increase in the Irish population. The main site was the Blackwater Callows (in Cork and Waterford), with 218 birds (not included in i-WeBS counts below). This was the only nationally important site. Elsewhere and not in the survey, there were counts of fifty to 100 birds at Ballinacarriga, Bandon Valley, the Gearagh, Churchtown (110 maximum on 3 January 2022), Kilcolman and Toons Bridge (137 maximum on 10 March 2021).

Whooper Swan - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	195	184	65	110	198	393	135
Ballyhea Gravel Pit	177					177	
Bandon River	112	122			80	115	129
Inishcarra Reservoirs	73	64	62	110	120	103	15
Kilcolman Marsh	14	14					

Common Shelduck *Tadorna tadorna*

No breeding records were received.

Common Shelduck - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	987	1138	999	817	1134	1013	653
Cork Harbour	743	924	694	631	913	689	493
Clonakilty Bay	103	74	124	107	105	143	68

Courtmacsherry, Broadstrand & Dunworley	93	131	80	58	82	78	
Ballymacoda	47	8	52	5		82	
Glandore Harbour/ Union Hall	33		13	25	38	53	27
Bandon Estuary	31	30	35			50	10
Ballycotton Shanagarry	28	38	40	21	21	23	20
Stick Estuary	15	0	38		2	10	27
Ilen Estuary	12	15	4	0	22	20	0

Mandarin Duck *Aix galericulata*

Scarce introduced species, no evidence of breeding in the county.

Eight birds recorded in 2019–23, though the same bird was probably seen more than once at The Geragh.

The Geragh 2–14 February 2020, four birds; singles at the Gearagh on 4 October 2021 and 17 August 2022; Lough Beg on 24 September 2021 and Saleen on 23 September 2023.

Garganey *Spatula querquedula*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
174	7	129	36

Thirty-six birds in the period 2019–23 were the highest in the series since 1959. Clonakilty and the Geragh accounted for most birds with ten each. Notably, four birds occurred three times at Clonakilty on 21 March 2022, from 5–26 May 2023, and at Mizen Head on 21 April 2022. Fourteen of the aged birds were male. Almost all remained for a day or two, with one at the Gearagh remaining from 6 September to 1 October 2021.

Garganey – five-year periods – 1959–2023

Garganey – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Clonakilty			2	4	4	10
The Gearagh	3		3	3	1	10
Mizen Head				4		4
Harper's Island					2	2
Kilcolman Fen					2	2
Lough Aderra		1			1	2
Ballycotton				1		1
Bantry				1		1
Castlemartyr				1		1
Midleton			1			1
Owenahincha		1				1
Youghal		1				1
Total	3	3	6	14	10	36

Garganey *Spatula querquedula* and Glossy Ibis *Plegadis falcinellus*, Castlemartyr, April 2022, S. Cronin

Blue-winged Teal *Spatula discors*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
20	3	15	2

Male and female at Garretstown, 27 April 2022.

Shoveler *Spatula clypeata*

One at Kilcolman on 5 May 2022, was the only breeding season record.

Shoveler - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	80	89	38	13	76	121	78
Kilcolman Marsh	51	51					
Clonakilty Bay	32	4	3	4	27	63	64
Charleville Lagoons	30	22				38	
Cork Harbour	27	20	12	4	43	27	35
Blarney Fen - Clogheenmilcon	20						20

Gadwall *Mareca strepera*

A pair at Doneraile on 27 June 2023 was the only possible breeding record. Birds are regular from late August to mid-April.

Gadwall - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	83	70	130	38	14	85	115
Lough Aderry	56	54	30	21		55	87
Ballynacarriga Lake	41	0	82				
Ballyhonock Lough	13	18	17	6		7	11
Ballybutler Lake	10	2	0	2		18	19
Cork Harbour	10	12	9	5	6	10	14

Common Wigeon *Mareca penelope*

Wigeon - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24-

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	3492	4588	3261	2880	3508	4105	1996
Cork Harbour	1127	1242	1141	1115	1162	1171	919

Courtmacsherry , Broadstrand & Dunworley	801	1053	1204	654	580	367	
Clonakilty Bay	629	930	559	647	596	637	423
Ballymacoda	506	586	384	174		548	
Lissagriffin Lake	264	237	239	176	319	301	225
Ballycotton Shanagarry	176	281	123	136	190	200	85
Rosscarbery	171	125	7	0	200	268	257
Charleville Lagoons	170	1				339	
Inishcarra Reservoirs	145	201	154	175	170	99	103
Bantry Bay	130	120	140	0	105	164	120

Mallard *Anas platyrhynchos*

Mallard - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	1152	1352	969	952	1206	1171	1060
Cork Harbour	397	405	444	253	302	406	427
Inishcarra Reservoirs	237	410	23	164	350	137	265
Clonakilty Bay	199	272	121	162	257	169	175
Charleville Lagoons	84	100				69	
Castlemartyr Lake	82	126	64	90		69	69
Bandon Estuary	81	88	106			85	44
Ballymacoda	76	23	122	135		82	
Courtmacsherry , Broadstrand & Dunworley	71	37	74	86	121	52	
Bantry Bay	67	48	61	0	56	89	79
Rosscarbery	62	65	50	15	65	29	99

Pintail *Anas acuta*

Pintail - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	32	51	21	26	27	44	18
Cork Harbour	27	51	20	26	25	20	18
Ballymacoda	12	0	0	0		35	

Common Teal *Anas crecca*

No breeding records were received.

Common Teal - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	3159	3831	3189	2794	3241	3130	2403
Cork Harbour	1402	1791	1433	1411	1234	1318	1232
Inishcarra Reservoirs	654	620	390	840	1400	560	298
Ballymacoda	488	439	590	257		435	
Ballycotton Shanagarry	408	826	489	247	198	476	50
Courtmacsherry Broadstrand & Dunworley	332	474	314	334	357	182	
Clonakilty Bay	290	295	303	138	286	282	282
Ringabella Creek	175	122	161		198	199	196
Charleville Lagoons	165	230				100	
Stick Estuary (Oysterhaven)	155	44	312		81	95	243
Lissagriffin Lake	102	78	61	93	113	148	111

Green-winged Teal *Anas carolinensis*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
-	0	83 (87 in BOC)	9

Nine birds recorded in 2019–23, in a typical spread of sites. A seemingly returning bird present at Courtmacsherry, having been seen first in January 2017, was recorded in winters 2019/20, 2020/21, 2021/22, and 2022/23. Likewise, a bird at the Gearagh was presumed to have been first seen in 2018. All records were between 1 November and 5 April, apart from an unseasonal bird on 6 June 2021 at Kinsale Marsh.

Single birds reported from the following: Ballintubbrid on 29–30 December 2022; Ballycotton on 4–5 April 2023; Kilcolman 22–23 March 2019; Kilmaloda 10–11 January 2023; Kinsale Marsh on 26 June 2021 and 1 November 2021 to 19 February 2022; Leap on 1–7 February 2023; Lissagriffin on 28 March 2019; The Gearagh 9 January 2023

Common Pochard *Aythya ferina*

The species is still an uncommon winter species, with maximum counts of eleven at Ballinacaggiga in 2019/20, ten at Garryhesta (now inaccessible) on 16 January 2022, and nine at Lough Aderry on 28 January 2022. A total of fifty-five birds recorded. A bird at Kilcolman on 2 May 2021 raises the possibility of breeding. The earliest autumn record was 24 October. Only one bird was recorded in 2023.

Pochard - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
Ballynacarriga Lake	8	5	11				
Castlemartyr Lake	0	0	1	0		0	0
Classis Lake West	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Cork Harbour	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Kilcolman Marsh	1	1					
Lough Aderry	0	1	0	0		0	0
Bateman's Lough	1	0	0	0	3	0	

Ring-necked Duck *Aythya collaris*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
90	0	72 (77 in BOC)	18

Eighteen new birds were recorded in 2019–23. There was a large influx in December 2018 with a peak of nine birds at Garranes Lake remaining from 4 December to 24 March 2019. Giving an exact number of the birds is difficult, and returning birds are excluded where possible. Birds were

Ring-necked Duck – 1959–2023 – five-year periods

recorded between 8 October and 1 May. Seven of the birds were adult males. The species has been increasing since the first record in 1974.

Ring-necked Duck - site totals 2019–23

Garranes Lake	9	Ballylickey	1
Lough Atarriff	3	Ballynacarriga Lough	1
Blarney	2	Carrigillihy	1
Dunmanway	2	Cork City	1
Lough Allua	2	Ballinascarty	0
The Gearagh	2	Lough Clubir	0

Tufted Duck *Aythya fuligula*

Breeding was confirmed at Cork City in 2021 and at The Gearagh in 2022.

Tufted Duck - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	68	90	111	98	68	44	28
Ballynacarriga Lake	26	12	39				
Cork Harbour	25	43	36	16	18	15	12
Classis Lake West	17	27	40	24	14	5	0
Lough Cluahir	15	16	13	21	20	13	12
Castlenalact Lake	14		26	22	17	0	14
Bateman's Lough	12	13	10	2	11	15	
Blarney Lake	12						12
Clogheenmilcon	10						10

Tufted Duck *Aythya fuligula*, Cork City, June 2021, M.Shorten

Greater Scaup *Aythya marila*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
-	-	-	7

Formerly more common, with up to 90 birds in the 1970s, seven birds in 2019–23, is about average. The Lough on 3 November 2019; Whitegate on 9–18 November 2021; two birds at Whites’s Marsh on 28 November 2021; Cuskinny Marsh on 8–14 May 2023; 15 November 2023 and Lough Cluahir on 11–28 December.

Lesser Scaup *Aythya affinis*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
0	0	2	7

Four records, a first winter male at Bateman's Lake from 12 December 2021 to 8 January 2022; first winter male at Garryhesta, 16 January 2022, (present from 26 December 2021); female at Ballinacarriga Lake on 30 January 2022 and a second calendar-year at Lough Cluhir on 30 March to 7 April.

Common Eider *Somateria mollissima*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
At least 153	3	138 at least	12

Twelve birds in 2019–23 is about average, with birds in a typical spread of sites. Three at Ballycotton on 4 December 2019 was the peak. Birds were recorded between 2 December and 28 May. Apart from the Broad Strand and Cuskinny birds, all were seen on single days. One Broad Strand, 2 January to 2 March 2019; three Ballycotton, 4 December 2019; one Belvelly, 6 December 2019; two Youghal, 26 February 2020; one Baltimore, 28 May 2020; one Old Head of Kinsale, 5 November 2022; one off Cuskinny, 18 November 2022 to 7 January 2023; one off Cuskinny, 11 March 2023, and one Dunmanus Bay, 11 December 2023.

Surf Scoter *Melanitta perspicillata*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
35	1	28	6

Four birds in 2019–23 is a bit above average, all in typical coastal locations - first-winter female at Garretstown, 6 December 2020; one at Crookhaven on 8 December 2021; adult male at Aghada from 19 November 2022 to 17 April 2023; female type at Ahenesk from 5 November 2023 to 2 December 2023.

Velvet Scoter *Melanitta fusca*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
75	5	63	11

Eleven birds in 2019–23 was about average, with a peak of five at Bantry Bay between January and March 2020.

One at Aghada from 1 December 2019 to 4 January 2020; Pilmore on 1 January 2020; One at Owenahincha from 17 January to 6 March, with two additional birds from 20 January to 19 February 2022, Cape Clear on 9 April 2023. Five in January and two in March 2020 in Bantry Bay (i-WeBS).

Common Scoter *Melanitta nigra*

In winter, small numbers recorded in Cork Harbour and Ballycotton - less than five usually. The most regular winter location, Owenahincha/Cloghna Head, usually holds about twenty to thirty birds, with a maximum of ninety-three on 10 November 2019.

Long-tailed Duck *Clangula hyemalis*

A typical scattering of records, forty-seven birds, all coastal. Four near Skibbereen on the Ilen on 23 November 2019 was the peak count.
 An exceptional early record of a bird at Dursey Island on 5 August. The remaining records were between 15 October and 9 May.

Long-tailed Duck – 2019–23 – total site counts

Aghada	9	Lough Beg	2	Cunnamore	1
Clonakilty	4	Whitegate	2	East Ferry	1
Ballydehob	4	Ballycotton	1	Inchydoney Bay	1
Skibbereen	4	Crookhaven	1	Ringaskiddy	1
Garretstown	3	Dursey Island	1	Rossleague	1
Sherkin	2	Owenahincha	1	Shanvallybeg, Bantry	1
Courtmacsher	2	Timoleague	1	White's Marsh	1
Rosscarbery	2	Belvelly	1		

Bufflehead *Bucephala albeola*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
3	0	2	1

A first-winter female seen flying by Aghada Pier on 20th December 2021 was relocated at Oysterhaven on 2 and 3 January 2022 and then at the pond at Barry’s Head from 23 January to 18 April. The third county record.

Common Goldeneye *Bucephala clangula*

Maximum count was of five birds at Carrigrennan, Little Island, Cork Harbour on 30 November 2019. One or two birds were regular at the Gearagh, with a peak of four on 7 February 2021. One to three birds were seen at Bateman’s Lake, Castle Lake (Carrigtowhill), Clonakilty, Courtmacsherry, Douglas Estuary, Lough Atarriff, Lough Clubhir and Youghal.

Goldeneye – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Ballinascorthy			1			1
Carrigrennan	5	1	1			7
Castle Lake, Carrigtowhill		1				1
Clonakilty					1	1

Courtmacsherry				2		2
Douglas Estuary			4			4
Dunkettle		1				1
The Gearagh	4	2	2	3	1	12
Glounthaune Estuary			1			1
Lough Atarriff	1					1
Lough Clubir				2	4	6
Youghal			1			1
Total	10	5	10	7	6	38

Earliest and latest dates were 28 October and 2 April.

Goosander *Mergus merganser*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
-	-	109	30

Thirty birds were recorded in 2019–23, though this probably includes returning birds. Twelve were recorded at the Gearagh with a peak of four on 7 March 2020. One or two birds occurred at Ballyhonock and Castlemartyr, with singles at Ballincollig, Rock Island (Crookhaven) and Timoleague. From January 2023, up to three birds were regular at Harty’s Quay in the Douglas Estuary.

A pair were seen displaying in the upper Lee valley on 10 March 2019.

The earliest arrival date is 11 November, and 4 April is the latest date.

Red-breasted Merganser *Mergus serrator*

No breeding reports were received.

Red-breasted Merganser - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	93	93	129	79	70	97	75
Cork Harbour	46	62	62	30	33	41	30
Ballydehob Estuary	19	13	21	19	14	21	26
Roaringwater Bay	14	14	12	11	20	11	13
Crookhaven	14	8	8	2	11	17	24
Croagh Bay	13	8	14	13	16	18	10
Courtmacsherry, Broadstrand & Dunworley	12	8	24	7	7	11	

Red Grouse *Lagopus lagopus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
-	-	-	9

The species is very much under-recorded but also rare. Most sightings are from wind farm surveys. Gun clubs have released birds in the Nagles Mountains and perhaps elsewhere (B.O'Mahoney pers comms.). One Caherdowney, Millstreet, 21 October 2019; two Caherdowney, Millstreet, 2 December 2019; one Boggeragh Mountains, 11 May 2020; one Boggeragh Mountains, 22 January 2021; two Boggeragh Mountains, 26 April 2021; one Derrynasaggart Mountains, 31 July 2022; two Gougane Barra 24 April 2021.

Quail *Coturnix coturnix*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
-	-	60	4

Four records are about average for the species.

Cape Clear on 14 October 2022; Mizen Head on 2 May 2021; Rossmore, near Clonakilty on 5 June 2023 and Ballymaloe from 21–27 July 2023. The Rossmore and Ballymaloe birds were singing.

Nightjar *Caprimulgus europaeus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
-	-	60	5 or 6 birds

Three migrants, all in May and June 2019 - Dursey Island on 1 June; Turk Head on 4–5 June, singing; Cape Clear on 12 May. Two or three birds were singing in the Ballyhouras (Cork side) in July 2019, there was no proof of breeding.

Alpine Swift *Tachymarptis melba*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
37	2	20	15

One record in 2022 and a major influx across the south and east of Ireland in March 2023. The first bird was found at Carrigaline on 15 March, two on the following day, three on 17 March and four on 18 March, with one on 19 March. Birds were seen roosting on the Church of Our Lady and St John. Three were present in Cork City from 20–25 March, usually feeding along the Lee Fields and suspected roosting around Shandon. The final bird was at Lough Aderra on 2 April.

At least four, Carrigaline, 15th to 21st March; One, Bandon, 16th March; Two, Middleton, 17th March; One, Clonakilty, 17th March; One, Rosscarbery, 20th and 21st March; At least three, Cork City, 20th to 25th March; Two, Lough Aderra, 2nd April.

Common Swift *Apus apus*

	Earliest date	Latest date
2019	1 May	28 September
2020	13 April	22 August
2021	26 April	21 August
2022	29 April	22 October
2023	20 April	10 August

Maximum counts were of twenty to thirty birds from Bandon, Skibbereen, Carrigaline, Dunmanway, and Lough Beg.

Alpine Swift *Tachymartus melba* Carrigaline, March 2023, S. Cronin

Common Cuckoo *Cuculus canorus*

	Earliest date	Latest date
2019	25 March	31 July
2020	14 April	20 June
2021	9 April	9 June
2022	26 March	18 August
2023	18 April	29 July

Maximum counts of four at Coomhola on 17 May 2019 and Ballyhouras on 14 May 2020.

Stock Dove *Columba oenas*

Most records were on one to five birds, with up to thirty-four at Trabolgan in January 2021 and forty-seven at Crosshaven on 2 May 2021.

Woodpigeon *Columba palumbus* (subspecies: *palumbus*)

Just four counts of 100 birds or more - Aghada, 15 January 2019 (120); Lough Beg, 5 December 2020; Dunmanway, on 23 April 2022; Ringaskiddy on 1 November 2023. Passage numbers are low at Cape Clear, with an October maximum of nineteen birds.

Turtle Dove *Streptopelia turtur*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
-	-	-	42

Forty-two birds recorded 2019–23, which probably indicates continued decline in the species. It should be noted that CCBO was not operational in several years, and numbers may reflect this. The maximum count was of four birds at Cape Clear on 19 May 2019. The earliest was on 15 April, and 24 November was the latest. One was present at Ardfield on 29–31 January 2023.

Turtle Dove – 2019–23

Cape Clear	12	Allihies	1	Power head	1
Mizen Head	6	Ardfield	1	Rocky Bay	1
Garinish	3	Barleycove	1	Skibbereen	1
Union Hall	3	Douglas	1	Timoleague	1
Pilmore	2	Knockadoon Head	1	Tragumna	1
Sherkin Island	2	Old Head of Kinsale	1	Clonakilty	1
Toe Head	2				

Turtle Dove – 2004–2023

Collared Dove *Streptopelia decaocto*

Only a handful of counts of more than ten birds, with maximum counts of fifteen at Ringabella on 20 November 2021 and sixteen at Pilmore on 31 December 2021.

Corncrake *Crex crex*

Two records - at Goleen on 13 August 2019 and Barry’s Head on 1 October 2023. Disappointing given the marginal increase in the Irish population.

Common Coot *Fulica atra*

Regularly forty to fifty birds at The Lough. Elsewhere, numbers were quite low, with maximum counts at Blarney Lake, twelve on 11 July 2019, and thirty at Garryhesta on 29 November 2020.

Common Coot- i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24-1-1

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	81	90	215	17	13	41	44
Ballynacarriga Lake	102	3	200				
Lough Aderry	39	67	19	13		31	38

Little Grebe *Tachybaptus ruficollis*

Little Grebe - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	182	186	224	61	139	168	192
Cork Harbour	105	84	134	6	86	109	111
Kilkeran Lake	36	38	44	13	26		35
Lough Aderry	18	17	17	12		17	19
Ballynacarriga Lake	15	0	30				
Farranamanagh Lough	11	4	16				14
Charleville Lagoons	10	20				0	
Clonakilty Bay	10	6	9	6	18	3	12

Red-necked Grebe *Podiceps grisegena*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
27	4	21	2

Two records - Ballylickey on 1 December 2019 and Cloghna Head (near Ownahincha) on 26 January 2020.

Slavonian Grebe *Podiceps auritus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
213	3	199	11

Ten birds recorded, with a typical spread of records. Almost all single-day birds, apart from a bird at Aghada from 5 January to 12 March. Apart from an exceptionally early bird at Courtmacsherry on 30 August 2020, the remaining records were between 10 December and 12 March. All were single birds.

Kinsale, 19 December 2019; Rosbrin, 20 December 2019 to 2 March 2020; Aghada, 4 December 2019 to 4 January 2020; Toormore, 9 January 2020; Whitegate, 9 February 2020; Ballydehob, 2–3 March 2020; Courtmacsherry 30 August 2020; Rosscarbery, 10 December 2020; Aghada, 5 January 12 March 2022; Ballydehob, 3 March 2020.

Great Crested Grebe *Podiceps cristatus*

Breeding occurred at the Gearagh, Lough Aderra, and Blarney Lake.

Great Crested Grebe - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24-1-1

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	147	65	251	13	144	126	151
Cork Harbour	142	62	249	0	133	118	150
Inishcarra Reservoirs	13	9	5	12	34	4	12

Black-necked Grebe *Podiceps nigricollis*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
86	4	78	7

Seven birds were recorded in 2023–19, a fairly typical spread of records. The bird at Courtmacsherry was the only one to remain— probably the same bird from 2 January to 26 March and 30 October to 4 November. One Cape Clear, 4–20 December 2019; two Ballydehob, 19 January 2020; one Bantry, 1–2 January 2023; one Aghada, 13 January 2023; one Courtmacsherry, 2 January to 26 March 2023 and one Courtmacsherry, 30 October to 4 November 2023.

Oystercatcher *Haematopus ostralegus*

Breeding in very small numbers along the coast, but no details received.

Great crested Grebe - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	2245	2553	2279	1759	2180	2654	1557
Cork Harbour	1307	1333	997	1025	1438	1560	1207
Courtmacsherry, Broadstrand & Dunworley	408	318	412	333	525	376	
Ballymacoda	363	309	453	263		327	
Clonakilty Bay	252	305	190	136	231	321	211
Ballycotton Shanagarry	135	249	170	35	115	64	79
Bantry Bay	54	59	65	8	28	65	51
Rosscarbery	54	68	45	60	35	65	57
Glandore Harbour/Union Hall	47		35	49	74	45	34
Crookhaven	45	51	51	41	44	33	48

Black-winged Stilt *Himantopus himantopus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
36	4	22	10

Ten birds in 2023 is the most recorded since an influx in March and April 1990, when there were at least eleven individuals.

Male, White's Marsh, 21–25 April 2021; Female, Clogheen Marsh, 27 April 2021.

Five, Lough Erril, Cape Clear Island, 4–22 April 2023, with two remaining to 30 April; One, White’s Marsh, 4–24 April 2023; One, Ringarogy Island, Roaringwater Bay, 11 April 2023; One, Lough Cluhir, 27 April 2023, and presumed same, Squince Lagoon, 27–30 April.

Avocet *Recurvirostra avosetta*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
52	23	26	3

One at Kinsale Marsh from 9–21 November 2021 and from 4 December until 3 April 2022, and presumed same at Lough Beg on 25 November. Two at Kinsale Marsh on 6 December 2022 and presumed same on Arigideen Estuary from 26 December into 9 January 2023, one remaining until 12 January.

Grey Plover *Pluvialis squatarola*

Grey Plover - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	175	140	236	84	34	324	143
Ballymacoda	210	114	226	84		290	
Ballycotton Shanagarry	53	29	26	25	21	51	140
Clonakilty Bay	28	55	25	2	30	29	3
Cork Harbour	16	22	10	9	18	10	22

European Golden Plover *Pluvialis apricaria*

European Golden Plover- i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	5667	10930	8436	600	3167	4559	1241
Ballymacoda	5533	7650	5200	74		3750	
Cork Harbour	1598	2650	2000	36	2500	110	730
Inishcarra Reservoirs	1080	2000	1000	600	600	600	1200
Clonakilty Bay	840	700	1	0	1000	2500	0
Ballycotton Shanagarry	521	615	210	0	1500	250	30
Rosscarbery	433	63	0	0	1000	750	350
Ilen Estuary	79	0	270	0	14	110	0
Lissagriffin Lake	44	47	91	0	53	13	16
Bandon Estuary	40	0	0			160	0
Courtmacsherry, Broadstrand & Dunworley	11	0	0	0	0	45	

Pacific Golden Plover *Pluvialis fulva*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
4	0	3	1

An adult female at Ballycotton 15–19 July 2023, the fourth county record.

Pacific Golden Plover *Pluvialis fulva*, Ballycotton, July 2023, S.Cronin

American Golden Plover *Pluvialis dominica*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
94	0	74	20

Twenty birds were recorded in 2019–23, the second highest five-year period, since 1959. There were three in 2019, two in 2020, and seven in 2021 and eight in 2023. Five were adults; the remainder were juveniles. Apart from one at Ballycotton on 13 April 2020, all were between 29 August and 14 November, one remaining until 12 December.

American Golden Plover

Black-winged Stilt *Himantopus himantopus*, Whites Marsh, April 2023, S.Cronin

Avocet *Recurvirostra avosetta*, Kinsale Marsh, March 2022, M. Shorten

Juvenile, Muckcross Estuary, 22–28 October 2019; Juvenile, Harper’s Island, 24–26 October 2019; Juvenile, Ballycotton, 26 October 2019. Adult summer, Garryvoe, 13 April 2020; Adult, Mizen Head, 29 August 2020.

Juvenile Lissagriffin, 6 October 2021; one at Old Head of Kinsale, 9 October 2021; Juvenile 10–15 October 2021; one at Ballycotton, 6–16 October 2021; Juvenile at Rosscarbery, 23 October 2021; one at the Geragh; 14 November 2021; Juvenile at Ballycotton, 30 October to 15 December 2021. Adult, Ballycotton, 21–2 September 2023; Juvenile, Lissagriffin, 9 October 2023; Juvenile, Muckross, Clonakilty, 19–29 October 2023 joined by an adult, 27–29 October; Adult, Rosscarbery, 26 September to 7 October 2023, and, presumed same, 7 November; Juvenile, Rosscarbery, 26 October 2023; Juvenile, Rosscarbery, 9–12 November 2023; Juvenile, Bullen’s Bay, Old Head of Kinsale, 10 November 2023.

Dotterel *Charadrius morinellus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
40	1	33	6

Six birds were recorded, one at Galley Head on 12 April 2022, was just the fourth spring record. The bird at Blackrock was heard calling in flight.

Blackrock, 31 August 2021; juvenile Cape Clear on 19 September 2020; Cape Clear on 6 October 2022; Galley Head on 2 September 2021; Galley Head on 12 April 2022 and a juvenile at Hungry Hill on 4 September 2022.

Common Ringed Plover *Charadrius hiaticula*

Breeding reported from Little Island, Ballycotton, Allihies, Ardgroom and Eyries.

Common Ringed Plover - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	350	388	460	253	221	347	335
Ballymacoda	121	96	141	166		126	
Ballycotton Shanagarry	90	104	152	49	50	48	95
Clonakilty Bay	67	94	89	93	14	83	55
Courtmacsherry, Broadstrand & Dunworley	47	48	52	85	61	28	
Cork Harbour	44	27	30	62	40	28	95
Rosscarbery	35	2	0	0	50	51	72
Bear Haven	30	38	20	40	31	59	0
Ilen Estuary	29	100	26	2	20	0	0
Toormore Bay	26	22	25	24	31	20	32
Bantry Bay	23	47	30	10	18	7	14

Semipalmated Plover *Charadrius semipalmatus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
1	0	0	1

Second calendar-year, Galley Cove, 1st October 2021 to 3 April 2022. This is presumed to be the same bird that was sound recorded during passive nocturnal recording at Lissagriffin on 1st and 31st July and on 1st August (S.Ronayne). The first county record.

Semipalmated Plover *Charadrius semipalmatus* and Common Ringed Plover, Galley Cove, November 2021, R.T. Mills; February 2022 J.Lynch

Little Ringed Plover *Charadrius dubius*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
78	0	57	21

Twenty-one birds were recorded in 2019–23, the highest in five-year periods since 1959. Birds occurred between 27 March and 23 August. Proof of breeding remains elusive - despite searches in Cork Harbour and the regular appearance of birds at Harpers Island, no breeding evidence has been found. Thirteen of seventeen aged birds were adults.

Little Ring Plover – five-year periods – 1959–2023

Little Ringed Plover – 2019–23 – site totals

Ballycotton	6	Kilcolman	2	Owenahincha	1
Harpers Island	6	Clonakilty	1	Rosscarbery	1
The Gearagh	4				

Kentish Plover *Charadrius alexandrinus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
4	0	3	1

One female at Ballycotton on 19 April 2021, the fourth county record - all previous records are from Ballycotton.

Greater Sand Plover *Anarhynchus leschenaultii*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
1	0	0	1

The first county record was of an adult at Rossbrin Cove, near Schull on 21 April 2021.

Northern Lapwing *Vanellus vanellus*

No breeding records were received.

Northern Lapwing - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	3579	5217	3033	2068	2674	4620	2351
Ballymacoda	679	839	587	127		612	
Clonakilty Bay	659	407	480	546	577	1418	413
Inishcarra Reservoirs	643	1110	580	368	175	130	1222
Courtmacsherry, Broadstrand & Dunworley	507	807	437	313	494	291	
Ballycotton Shanagarry	412	625	374	443	619	301	140
Bandon Estuary	284	545	255			321	14
Rosscarbery	132	210	13	0	130	233	75
Stick Estuary (Oysterhaven)	131	175	127		119	140	96
Ringabella Creek	125	127	44		0	278	174

Upland Sandpiper *Bartramia longicauda*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
3	1	1	1

A juvenile on the Bill of Clear, Cape Clear from 9–13 October 2023, was the third county record.

Eurasian Whimbrel *Numenius phaeopus*

Peak spring counts: Harper’s Island, 356 on 8 May 2021; Toormore, 200 on 19 and 26 April 2020; Pilmore, 150 on 28 April 2019 and Toormore, 100 on 24 April 2019.
No autumn count exceeded ten birds.

Peak winter counts were: Corkbeg Bay (Whitegate), five on 28 November 2019; Roche’s Point, three on the following dates - 10 January 2019, 24 December 2021 and 1 January 2021. Elsewhere regular in Cork Harbour - Great Island (a few locations), Aghada, Belvelly, Harper’s Island, Lough Beg, Luc Strand, Carrigreanan and Saleen.
Nocturnal passive recording at Sundays Well, reflects the main spring passage in April in the county.

Whimbrel - nocturnal passive recording - 2020–23 – Sundays Well – Trektellan

Common Curlew *Numenius arquata*

A pair in north-west Cork in 2019 - possibly the known last breeding record for the county.

Common Curlew- i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	2326	2761	2426	1534	2351	2276	1816
Cork Harbour	1093	1172	1153	650	1256	948	937
Ballymacoda	519	531	514	379		513	
Clonakilty Bay	335	394	257	130	350	354	321
Courtmacsherry, Broadstrand & Dunworley	252	381	237	236	271	121	

Ballycotton Shanagarry	242	294	430	85	93	354	40
Bandon Estuary	186	248	99			248	151
Inishcarra Reservoirs	179	253	160	190	210	140	134
Stick Estuary (Oysterhaven)	128	32	230		101	128	151
Ringabella Creek	95	126	74		90	82	101
Ballydehob Estuary	80	78	109	85	95	71	46

Bar-tailed Godwit *Limosa lapponica*

Bar-tailed Godwit - iWeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	599	869	863	198	324	710	229
Ballymacoda	470	485	550	71		376	
Cork Harbour	327	430	490	154	283	212	219
Courtmacsherry, Broadstrand & Dunworley	64	46	25	37	41	144	
Ballycotton Shanagarry	37	16	16	92	47	64	44
Clonakilty Bay	25	31	15	11	15	29	35
Ilen Estuary	11	19	0	2	24	14	0
Rosscarbery	11	17	4	3	13	9	12
Stick Estuary (Oysterhaven)	131	175	127		119	140	96
Ringabella Creek	125	127	44		0	278	174

Black-tailed Godwit *Limosa limosa* (subspecies: *islandica*; *limosa*)

Black-tailed Godwit - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	4548	5368	6354	3808	3427	4340	3251
Cork Harbour	3002	2559	3807	2976	2563	3160	2920
Ballymacoda	1006	1051	1236	489		731	
Clonakilty Bay	955	1256	870	985	762	932	954
Courtmacsherry, Broadstrand & Dunworley	565	646	572	412	521	522	
Bandon Estuary	434	290	370			620	454
Rosscarbery	180	101	90	200	230	124	357
Ringabella Creek	170	159	135		122	190	243
Ballycotton Shanagarry	170	231	136	2	88	317	80
Stick Estuary (Oysterhaven)	168	60	206		147	202	226

Woodcock *Scolopax rusticola*

Records of fifty-four birds were received. Apart from breeding season birds at Bottle Hill and Capeen, all were between November and March. Additionally, 312 Woodcock were ringed in 2019–23, in autumn and winter. A recent nationwide survey found thirteen sites in Cork where roding male Woodcock were present in the breeding season from 2019 to 2021. These were mostly located in the east and north-east of the county, with only one observed at a site further west than Cork City. A modelling analysis of the national survey data showed that the county lies outside the core breeding range of the species in Ireland (O'Neill et al., 2026) <https://doi.org/10.1111/ibi.70040>.

Estimated density distribution of breeding Woodcock in Ireland, produced from abundance estimates predicted from a GAM using six explanatory predictor variables for 1-km² squares with at least 0.1km² woodland across the estimated distribution (produced using 'biomod2'; Fig. 4b), based on surveys undertaken at 133 separate randomly selected sites in May and June of 2017, 2019, and 2021. Outlying records of birds displaying breeding behaviour, including occupied survey sites and casual sightings from the same time periods, which were located at least 5km from the estimated distribution, are included for illustrative purposes. The outlines of the 10×10km squares where Woodcock were recorded for the 2007–11 atlas (Balmer et al. 2013) are overlaid so that the results of this study may be compared against the previous most recently recorded distribution (O'Neill et al. 2026).

Jack Snipe *Lymnocyptes minimus*

Sixty-seven birds reported, most of which were single birds, with five at Ballycotton in February 2019. Additionally, twenty-two birds were ringed.

Common Snipe *Gallinago gallinago*

Maximum counts - 200 at the Gearagh on 5 January 2023 and 100 on 22 January; 100 at Harper’s Island in 2019. No breeding records were received.

Long-billed Dowitcher *Limnodromus scolopaceus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
28	0	27	1

Juvenile at White’s and Clogheen Marsh, Clonakilty from 14 September to 22 October 2023. Numbers appear to have declined in recent years.

Long-billed Dowitcher – five-year periods – 2019–23

Short-billed Dowitcher *Limnodromus griseus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
1	0	0	1

A second calendar-year bird at Ring, Clonakilty from 2–27 July 2021, was the first county record.

Wilson’s Phalarope *Phalaropus tricolor*

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County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
29	0	28	1

Just one bird, a juvenile at Ballycotton on 19 October 2023, was the first since 2012.

Grey Phalarope *Phalaropus fulicarius*

Low numbers, with a maximum of eight on 5 September 2022 and a total of fifty-eight in 2019–23. A few winter records but the majority in September and October. All were coastal records apart from one at the Gearagh on 5 September 2022.

Grey Phalarope – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Ballycotton				4	1
Bantry					1
Cape Clear	1				3
Clonakilty					1
Crookhaven					1
Cunnamore		3			
Dursey Island	1				
Galley Head		2		7	
Garinish Point	1			8	
Mizen Head				2	3
Old Head of Kinsale			1		2
the Gearagh				1	
Toe Head				12	
Toormore				1	
Total	3	5	1	35	12

Grey Phalarope – 2004–2023

Common Sandpiper *Actitis hypoleucos*

Peak autumn counts were fifteen at Harper's Island on 26 July 2023 and twelve near Dunkettle on 16 July 2020.

Birds in suitable breeding locations - two at Ballydonegan on 11 June 2019, two at Dunmanus Castle on 19 May 2019 and Glanbeg Lough on 20 May 2023.

One or occasionally two birds recorded in winter months, particularly on Great Island, Skibbereen, Cork City docks, Ballydehob, Goleen, Aghada, Dunisky, Schull, Clonakilty and Saleen. Maximum

Top: Short-billed Dowitcher *Limnodromus griseus*, Ring, July 2021, R.T. Mills
Bottom: Long-billed Dowitcher *Limnodromus scolopaceus*, Whites Marsh, September 2023, R.T. Mills

Common Sandpiper - nocturnal passive recording - 2020–23 – Sundays Well –
Trekellan

of three at Leap on 26 November 2023.

Nocturnal passive recording at Sundays Well reflects the main spring passage in early autumn in the county.

Spotted Sandpiper *Actitis macularius*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
18	0	17	1

A juvenile at Castletownbere on 15 October 2022, the eighteenth record. All have occurred between 7 July and 27 November, with most in October.

Spotted Sandpiper – 1959–2023

Green Sandpiper *Tringa ochropus*

Average numbers in 2019–23, with 148 birds recorded - there may be some double counting of birds. May was the only month without records. Birds arrive from late June, peak in August, and many over-winter. Typically, the peak counts were from Dunisky with twelve on 11 July 2022. The species is probably under-recorded on rivers inland.

Green Sandpiper – 2019–23 – site totals

Dunisky	44	Youghal	3	Cape Clear	1
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The Gearagh	30	Ballycotton	2	Castlelyons	1
Cork City	11	Ballydehob	2	Conna	1
Rathduff	7	Bateman's Lake	2	Courtmacsherry	1
Timoleague	6	Belgooly	2	Kilcolman	1
Clonakilty	5	Rossmore	4	Killeagh	1
Enniskeane	5	Ballinascarthy	1	Lissagriffin	1
Ballincollig	4	Ballymacoda	1	Newcestown	1
Dunkettle	4	Barry's Head	1	Owenahincha	1
Harper's Island	3	Toons Bridge	1	Sherkin Island	1

Wood Sandpiper *Tringa glareola*

Thirty-two birds in 2019–23 is above average, and numbers have been increasing in recent years. The maximum count was of four birds at Harpers Island on 21–26 August 2023. Birds occurred between 5 April and 9 September, with a peak in September.

Wood Sandpiper – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Ballinascarthy			1			1
Ballycotton			2	3		5
Ballydehob					1	1
Clonakilty		3	1	1	3	8
Dunmanway				1		1
Harpers Island	1				5	6
Lissagriffin	1		2	1		4
Lough Beg	1					1
Rosscarbery					1	1
The Gearagh			1	2	2	5
Total	3	3	7	8	12	33

Wood Sandpiper – 2004–2023

Common Redshank *Tringa totanus*

Common Redshank- i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	2538	2646	2323	1868	2362	2914	2447
Cork Harbour	1761	1493	1597	1417	1748	2222	1747
Clonakilty Bay	235	274	166	187	280	227	229
Ballymacoda	212	255	176	99		204	
Bandon Estuary	196	201	177			218	189
Courtmacsherry, Broadstrand & Dunworley	135	230	114	99	98	99	
Rosscarbery	132	84	125	95	220	91	140

Ilen Estuary	118	111	143	27	142	190	6
Ballydehob Estuary	90	90	55	88	80	106	119
Ballycotton Shanagarry	87	80	73	54	88	130	65
Glandore Harbour/Union Hall	87		70	62	88	62	127

Lesser Yellowlegs *Tringa flavipes*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
65	0	56	9

Lesser Yellowlegs records have gradually increased, and nine in 2019–23 is in line with this. Six birds were juveniles. Records were almost evenly spread between spring and autumn, with two in April, one in May, one in August, four in September, and one in October.

Adult Clonakilty, 20 April 2019; adult Kinsale Marsh 4–12 August 2019; juvenile Lissagriffin 17–20 September 2019; adult Harper’s Island, 9 May 2020; juvenile Lissagriffin, 17–20 September 2020; juvenile Baltimore, 23 September 2020; juvenile Ballycotton, 30 October 2021; adult Clonakilty, 13 April 2022 and presumed same Rosscarbery 16–20 April 2022 and Timmoleague, 6–8 May 2022; juvenile Rosscarbery, 16–18 October 2022; Rosscarbery 8 September to 12 October 2023.

Lesser Yellowlegs *Tringa flavipes* Lissagriffin, September 2020, Richard T. Mills

Lesser Yellowlegs — 1959—2023

Spotted Redshank *Tringa erythropus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
-	-	-	41

Forty-one birds were recorded in 2019–23, a below-average showing in the period 2004–23; however, this is well below the peak counts in the 1970s and 1980s. Three at Harper’s Island on 22 August 2021 were the peak count. Birds were recorded in all months, with most in August and September

Spotted Redshank – maximum flock count – Cork five-year periods – 1959–2023

Spotted Redshank – 2004–2023

Spotted Redshank – site totals - 2019–23

Harper's Island	8	Timoleague	5	Rossleague	1
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Clogheen Marsh	6	Ballycotton	3	Saleen	1
Lough Beg	6	The Gearagh	2	Schull	1
Rosscarberry	6	Kinsale	1	Sherkin Island	1

Greenshank *Tringa nebularia*

Greenshank - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	243	233	208	154	264	248	262
Cork Harbour	140	103	120	73	178	145	154
Clonakilty Bay	35	36	38	17	48	19	32
Bandon Estuary	25	22	17			35	25
Ballycotton Shanagarry	14	21	12	21	12	18	6
Courtmacsherry, Broadstrand & Dunworley	14	19	13	15	14	9	
Rosscarberry	13	18	10	15	6	19	13
Croagh Bay	12	10	11	14	11	14	12
Ballymacoda	10	5	12	16		14	
Ilen Estuary	10	15	12	13	7	11	5

Turnstone *Arenaria interpres* (subspecies: *interpres*)

Turnstone - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	186	214	275	127	115	183	141
Cork Harbour	95	95	124	108	84	79	95
Ballymacoda	84	64	108	0		80	
Ballycotton Shanagarry	42	58	108	15	6	28	8
Bere Haven	22	29	29	18	25	25	2
Ardgroom Harbour	17	19	6		12	24	26
Bantry Bay	15	14	8	10	17	15	20
Courtmacsherry, Broadstrand & Dunworley	13	14	14	8	14	10	
Clonakilty Bay	12	11	21	6	8	9	11

Ruff *Calidris pugnax*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
-	-	-	155

About 155 Ruff were recorded in 2019–23, about average numbers. The largest flock was eleven birds at Timoleague on 5–6 September 2021. Small numbers occur in the winter, but September is

the main passage month.

Ruff – site totals – 2019–23

Clonakilty	38	Rosscarbery	3	Galley Head	1
The Gearagh	37	Courtmacsherry	2	Garryvoe	1
Harpers Island	21	Kinsale Marsh	2	Glengariff	1
Timoleague	20	Lough Beg	2	Kilbrittain	1
Ballycotton	8	Oysterhaven	2	Lissagriffin	1
Duniskey	5	Ballymacoda	2	Myross	1
Ballinascarthy	4	Coomhola	1	Skibbereen	1
Rosscarbery	3			Union Hall	1

Ruff – 2019–23

Ruff – 2008–2023 – yearly totals

Red Knot *Calidris canutus* (subspecies: *islandica*)

Red Knot- i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total	337	84	559	151	343	361	340
Clonakilty Bay	175	30	269	113	121	200	255
Cork Harbour	164	78	215	26	220	90	217
Ballymacoda	106	55	150	13		113	

Ballycotton	13	2	1	62	0	51	10
Shanagarry							
Rosscarbery	10	0	0	1	30	0	20

Sharp-tailed Sandpiper *Calidris acuminata*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
4	0	3	1

Adult at Clogheen Marsh, Clonakilty on 17–19 August was the fourth county record and the first away from Ballycotton.

Curlew Sandpiper *Calidris ferruginea*

305 Curlew Sandpipers were recorded in 2019–23; typically, there were wide fluctuations between years— eight in 2019 and 101 in 2021. Peak counts were twenty-four in Rosscarbery on 18 September 2020 and twenty at Ballycotton on 6 September 2023. There were single records in February and June; the remaining records were between 19 August and 2 November.

Curlew Sandpiper – 2004–2023

Curlew Sandpiper – site totals – 2019–23

Clonakilty	74	Garretstown	5	Rath / An Ráth	3
Ballycotton	57	Pilmore	5	Saleen	2
Rosscarbery	57	Timoleague	5	Bere Island	1
The Gearagh	32	Baltimore	4	Cape Clear	1
Harpers Island	19	Dunisky	4	Cork City	1
Owenahincha	11	Millcove	4	Crookhaven	1
Kinsale Marsh	9	Harbour View	3	Lough Beg	1
Coolmain Beach	5	Lissagriffin	3	Sherkin Island	1

Temminck's Stint *Calidris temminckii*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
4	0	3	1

A juvenile at Ballycotton from 8–14 September was the fourth county record.

Buff-breasted Sandpiper *Calidris subruficollis*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
105	0	90 (88 in BOC)	15

Fifteen birds were recorded in 2019–23, and apart from one at Clonakilty on 28 May 2022, the remainder occurred between 21 August and 10 October. The peak count was of four at Lissagriffin on 17 September 2020.

One at Ballycotton, 28 August 2020; juvenile Harbour View, 4–5 September 2020; juvenile Garretstown, 9 September 2020; four juveniles at Lissagriffin on 17 September 2020; one at Clonakilty, 21 August 2021; juvenile at Skibbereen, 20 September 2021; juvenile at Lissagriffin on 26–27 September 2021; juvenile at Mizen Head, 10 October 2021; adult at Clonakilty, 28 May 2022; juvenile at Ballycotton, 10 September 2022 and two juveniles at Pilmore, 2023.

Buff-breasted Sandpiper – 1959–2023

Sanderling *Calidris alba*

Sanderling - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total	143	163	257	69	59	173	65
Ballymacoda	132	131	108	3		156	
Ballycotton	98	118	179	69	59	67	65
Shanagarry							

Dunlin *Calidris alpina* (subspecies: *schinzii*; *alpina*)

Dunlin - iWeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total	7442	5988	6389	2556	6476	11497	6858

Cork Harbour	5193	3965	4249	1565	5171	6798	5784
Ballymacoda	1952	2281	1614	182		1962	
Clonakilty Bay	630	929	418	652	170	899	735
Courtmacsherry , Broadstrand & Dunworley	582	526	250	217	579	973	
Bandon Estuary	504	595	410			550	460
Ballycotton Shanagarry	328	147	499	190	282	516	195
Rosscarbery	179	72	30	90	185	355	253
Inishcarra Reservoirs	118	43	54	71	200	150	145
Ballydehob Estuary	74	65	46	84	69	78	114
Ringabella Creek	60	18	0		0	160	120

Purple Sandpiper *Calidris maritima*

Typical small numbers recorded on the coast in west Cork - peak count was nine at Sheep's Head on 13 February 2022.

Baird's Sandpiper *Calidris bairdii*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
43	0	35	8

Eight birds recorded in 2019–23, the joint highest in a five-year period since 1959. All were juveniles, apart from unaged bird at Harpers Island. The Harpers Island record was the first for the

Baird's Sandpiper *Calidris bairdii*, Clonakilty October 2021, J.Lynch
Cork Bird Report 2019–23

site, along with a White-rumped Sandpiper, also a first, in the same flock. All birds occurred between 3 September and 22 October.

Kilbrittain, 8–15 September 2020; Clonakilty, 3 September to 1 October 2021; Timmoleague, 17 September 2021; Ballycotton, 8 September 2022; Ballycotton 6 October 2022; Clonakilty, 16 October 2023; another Clonakilty, 16 October to 3 November 2023 and Harpers Island 22–23 October 2023.

Baird's Sandpiper – 1959–2023

Little Stint *Calidris minuta*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
-	-	-	56

Fifty-six birds were recorded in 2019–23, a bit above average, though there were none in 2019. Five at Clonakilty on 15–19 September 2021 were the peak count. There were single records in April, May, and June, with most in September.

Little Stint – 2004–23

Little Stint – 2019–23 – total site counts

Ballycotton	18	Harpers Island	3	Baltimore	1
Clonakilty	16	Kinsale Marsh	3	Duniskey	2
Rosscarbery	4	Harbour View	2	Garretstown	1
The Gearagh	4	Ballytrasna	1	Lissagriffin	1

Least Sandpiper *Calidris minutilla*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
6	0	5	1

The sixth county record was a juvenile trapped and ringed at Harbour View on 7 October 2020.

White-rumped Sandpiper *Calidris fuscicollis*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
86	0	77	9

Nine birds were recorded in 2019–23, an average number of records but with birds in 2019 and 2023 only. The seven in 2019 were the most recorded in a single year. All birds were between 1 September and 22 October.

One at Myrtleville, 1 September 2019; one at Lissagriffin, 12 September 2019; juvenile at Lissagriffin, 9 October 2019; one at Ballycrenane, 16 October 2019; adult at Ballycrenane, 16–26 October 2019; juvenile at Lissagriffin, 21 October 2019; juvenile at Ballycotton, 22 October to 10 November 2019; juvenile at Owenahincha, 21 October 2023 and juvenile at Harper’s Island 22–23 October 2023

White-rumped Sandpiper – 1959-2023

Pectoral Sandpiper *Calidris melanotos*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
280	0	246	34

Thirty-four birds occurred in 2019–23, about average numbers. There were no birds in 2019, the first blank year since 1997. April records are rare - one at Ballycotton on 3–7 April 2022. The remainder of records were between 10 July and 29 October, and most in September. Notably, the Gearagh had the highest number of birds.

Pectoral Sandpiper – 2019–23 – site totals

The Gearagh	9	Ballymacoda	2	Courtmacsherry	1
Clonakilty	6	Cape Clear	2	Dursey Island	1
Ballycotton	5	Kinsale Marsh	1	Galley Head	1

Lissagriffin 5 Ring Strand 1

Pectoral Sandpiper – 2019–23

Semipalmated Sandpiper *Calidris pusilla*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
60	0	53	10

Ten records in 2019–23, typical of recent years. All birds were juveniles and were recorded between 3 September and 8 October.

Juvenile the Geragh, 8 October 2019; juvenile Inchadoney, 9 September 2020; juvenile Rosscarbery, 13–18 September 2020; juvenile Ballycotton, 17 September 2020; juvenile Lissagriffin, 4 August 2023; juvenile Clonakilty, 3–4 September 2023; juvenile Owenahincha, 5–6 September 2023; juvenile Rosscarbery, 6–11 September 2023; juvenile Clonakilty, 21–21 September 2023; juvenile Ballycotton, 8–28 October 2023.

Semipalmated Sandpiper – 1959–2023

Collared Pratincole *Glareola pratincola*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
1	0	0	1

A second calendar-year bird at the Gearagh on 18–20 April 2020 was the first county record.

Pratincole sp., probably a Collared Pratincole, was near Dunmanus on 8 May 2022.

Arctic Tern *Sterna paradisaea*

Relatively few records received, with maximum counts of 260 at Seven Heads on 4 August 2020 and 50 there on 22 August 2020. Earliest and latest dates: 14 April and 15 October. Recorded on six dates at the Gearagh, involving nine birds— singles in May and September, the rest in August.

The Irish population has stayed relatively stable, in contrast to very large declines in Scotland.

Arctic Tern - breeding AON - Seabird 2000 and Seabirds Count (2015-21)

Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count	
Dunmanus Bay	5	0	
Bantry Bay Islands	24	8	
Roaringwater Bay (Inner and Outer)	0	50	
Survey totals and % change	29	58	100%

Common Tern *Sterna hirundo*

Low numbers recorded with maximums of forty-five at Dunkettle on 7 August 2023 and forty-three at Corkbeg Bay on 14 May 2019.

The continued conservation work on breeding Common Terns in Cork Harbour has paid off with the population doubling.

	Earliest date	Latest date
2019	24 April	30 September
2020	6 April	12 September
2021	1 May	5 September
2022	30 April	30 August
2023	20 April	24 October

Common Tern - breeding AON - Seabird 2000 and Seabirds Count (2015-21)

Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count	Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count
Beara Peninsula - Outer	3	0	Bantry Bay Islands	28	40
Dunmanus Bay	97	0	Cork Harbour	102	220
Survey totals and % change			13%	230	260

Top: Sharp-tailed Sandpiper *Calidris acuminata* Clogheen Marsh August 2023, R.T. Mills
Bottom: Pectoral Sandpiper *Calidris melanotos*, Galley Head, September 2021 R.T. Mills

Common Tern pairs breeding Cork Harbour 1983–2023 at Raffeen Creek, Ringaskiddy Port, Fota Martello Tower and nearby Barges

1983	23	1997	89	2011	75
1984	27	1998	81	2012	89
1985	26	1999	70	2013	120
1986	50	2000	58	2014	117
1987	60	2001	0	2015	157
1988	55	2002	23	2016	109
1989	90	2003	53	2017	132
1990	84	2004	53	2018	147
1991	91	2005	62	2019	116
1992	53	2006	46	2020	70
1993	88	2007	37	2021	90
1994	36	2008	18	2022	131
1995	102	2009	39	2023	139
1996	63	2010	34	2024	104

Little Tern *Sternula albifrons*

Little Terns are very scarce, with one report at the Old Head of Kinsale on 27 April 2022.

Gull-billed Tern *Gelochelidon nilotica*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
8	-	4	4

With only four previous records, four in 2019–23 was quite notable. Birds have occurred from 26 April to 26 July.

At least a third calendar year at Ballycotton from 21 June to 5 July 2020 and was also recorded at the Gearagh on 21–25 August, as well as various dates in Wexford in July and August.

Adult at Harper’s Island on 17–19 May 2022. One at Ring Strand on 6 June and an adult at Kilkerran on 18 July, both 2023.

Caspian Tern *Hydroprogne caspia*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
6	0	5	1

An adult at the Gearagh from 20–25 July 2023, was the fifth record (six individuals). All have occurred between 20 June and 14 August.

Black Tern *Chlidonias niger*

Four records of singles is the lowest in a five-year period since 1959 - Owenahincha on 29 August 2019; the Gearagh on 9–10 2021; Galley Head on 21 September 2022 and Ballycotton on 16 September 2023. Numbers peaked in the 1970s and 1980s and have declined since then.

Black Tern – five-year periods – 1959-2023

White-winged Tern *Chlidonias leucopterus*

Two records in 2019–23 - First calendar bird, caught and ringed on 2 September 2021 at Lough Beg. Juvenile at Ballin Lough, near Leap 5–11 November 2023.

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
21	0	19	2

Roseate Tern *Sterna dougallii*

Eighteen birds - Pilmore two on 2 August, seven on 12 August and one on 29 August 2020; one at Ringaskiddy on 4 July 2021; one at Pilmore on 29 August 2021; Ringaskiddy 27 June 2022 and five on 27 August 2022.

Sandwich Tern *Thalasseus sandvicensis*

	Earliest date	Latest date
2019	27 March	12 October
2020	12 March	28 September

White-winged Tern *Chlidonias leucopterus*, Ballin Lough, November 2023, R.T. Mills

2021	15 March	11 November
2022	22 March	18 October
2023	14 March	19 October

Peak counts - not in i-WeBS - 694 Lough Beg, 29 August 2020; 680 Lough Beg, 25 August 2019 and similar numbers around those dates in both years. The only count of over 100 birds outside Cork Harbour was 120 at Garretstown on 1 September 2020.

Sandwich Tern- i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total	156	418	187	77	80	80	13
mean peak							
Cork Harbour	79	199	110	5	75	3	9
Ballycotton	38	137	52	0	0	0	0
Shanagarry							
Ballymacoda	24	58	13	46		0	

Black-legged Kittiwake *Rissa tridactyla*

There have been substantial declines at some breeding sites in Ireland and Britain, including in Waterford, so relative stability is welcome news.

Kittiwake- breeding AON - Seabird 2000 and Seabirds Count (2015-21)

Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count	Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count
Bull Rock	0	150	Galley Head / Seven Heads	0	20
Brow Head/ Mizen Head	20	661	Old Head of Kinsale	1188	711
Baltimore to Glandore Harbour	0	0	Ringabella to Kinsale	112	37
Survey totals and % change				20%	1320
				1320	1579

Little Gull *Hydrocoloeus minutus*

Thirty-two birds in 2019–23 is a bit above recent years but still well below the peaks of the 1970s and 80s. Birds were recorded in all months apart from July, with a peak in October

Little Gull – 2004–23

Little Gull – site totals – 2019–23

Ballycotton	3	Ballinwilling	1	Clonakilty	1
Bantry	2	Ballybrannigan	1	Cork Harbour	1
Clogheen Marsh	2	Ballylickey	1	Crookhaven	1
Galley Head	2	Charleville Lagoons	1	Eyeries	1
Inchydoney Bay	2	Garrylucas	1	Rostellan	1
Mizen Head	2	Garryvoe	1	Whitegate	1
Myross	2	Harper's Island	1	Red Strand	1
Rosscarbery	2	Kilkeran Lake	1		

Sabine's Gull *Xema sabini*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
509	0	476	32

Thirty-two birds were recorded in 2019–23, in line with a decline since the 1990s and 2000s. All birds occurred between 7 July and 29 October. All counts were of one other two birds apart from ten on a rather early date of 28 July 2022.

Sabine's Gull – five-year periods – 1959–2023

Sabines Gull – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Ballycotton				2	2
Cape Clear					3
Cork Harbour		1			
Galley Head		3		10	4
Garinish Point	1		1	1	
Lough Mahon		1			
Mizen Head			1		
Seven Heads					1
Toe Head				2	
	1	5	2	15	10

Top: Caspian Tern *Hydroprogne caspia* The Gearagh, July 2023, R.T. Mills

Bottom: Gull-billed Tern *Gelocheilidon nilotica*, The Gearagh, August 2020, R.T. Mills

Bonaparte's Gull *Chroicocephalus philadelphia*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
32	0	17	15

Fifteen birds were recorded in 2019–23, with seventeen in total prior to this. Some birds have probably been counted more than once. Eleven birds were adults.

Adult, Garretstown, 4–17 September 2020; Adult, Long Strand, 11 September 2020; Adult, Whiddy, 2 March 2021 and presumed same Bantry on 17 March 2021; Great Island and presumed same at Whitegate 6–7 March 2021; second calendar-bird Ringaskiddy, 18 July 2021; second calendar-bird Whitegate, 18 August 2021; Garretstown, Long Strand and Ownahincha, presumed returning adult, 18 August to 28 October 2021; first-winter Harbour View, 4 March 2022; Adult The Lough, 15 May 2022; Adult Harper's Island 27–28 July 2022; adult Whitegate 29 August 2022; adult Bantry, 2 January 2023; adult Ballydehob 13–29 April 2023; adult Harper's Island, 25–28 August 2023; adult Garretstown, 26–29 August 2023 and first-winter Sherkin Island, 16 September 2023

Bonaparte's Gull *Chroicocephalus philadelphia* Ballydehob, April 2023
M.Shorten

■ New arrivals ■ Late stayers

Bonaparte's Gull – 2019–23

Mediterranean Gull *Ichthyaetus melanocephalus*

In 2019–23, Mediterranean Gull numbers continued to increase. Birds usually appear from late June at Harper’s Island, with up to 200 birds occurring, before rapidly declining. Most birds move on to the Whitegate, Roche’s Point area, and also fields on the coast to the east of Roche’s Point. Here, numbers usually peak in October (maximum 520 at Roche’s Point on 4 October 2022), with few birds remaining by January.

Mediterranean Gull – 2000–23 – maximum counts in Cork Harbour

Black-headed Gull *Chroicocephalus ridibundus*

Formerly a regular breeder inland - a pair at Toormoore 2019–23; two nests Raffeen 2022 (one failed), one nest 2023.

Black-headed Gull - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	6348	7649	5841	6503	6212	6052	5988
Cork Harbour	4134	4044	3768	4356	3908	4054	4894
Courtmacsherry Broadstrand & Dunworley	1077	1665	862	873	820	961	
Ballymacoda	611	574	725	1256		535	
Ballycotton Shanagarry	425	498	595	67	589	375	67
Clonakilty Bay	425	544	453	196	469	398	262
Bantry Bay	376	130	258	65	500	398	596
Rosscarbery	273	750	131	200	202	97	186
Bandon Estuary	185	285	222			162	70
Lough Aderry	172	59	254	107		215	160
Ilen Estuary	169	238	147	44	254	139	69

Common Gull *Larus canus*

Typically, a scarce breeding bird in Cork with six AONs in Kenmare Bay Islands.

Common Gull - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	1487	1059	1526	967	2070	1297	1485
Courtmacsherry Broadstrand & Dunworley	908	520	1203	769	1205	704	
Cork Harbour	515	252	248	125	451	252	1374
Ballymacoda	344	572	83	81		377	
Clonakilty Bay	145	283	73	108	91	162	118
Ballycotton Shanagarry	83	64	220	94	46	65	20
Lissagriffin Lake	75	188	30	37	65	65	25
Ballydehob Estuary	47	57	22	40	41	52	65
Crookhaven	41	29	11	36	100	42	22
Ringabella Creek	39	32	1		40	73	48
Bandon Estuary	30	6	4			104	4

Ring-billed Gull *Larus delawarensis*

Thirty-six birds were recorded - twenty-one adults and eleven first-winter, three first-summer, and one second-winter. Recurring birds have been removed where possible, but more than likely some birds are double-counted. Most records are between November and March, with the peak in early spring. Ring-billed Gulls have declined from peaks in the 1980s and 1990s, and the decline in first-winter birds was particularly noticeable. ~There was an uptick in records in 2022 - though none in 2023.

Ring-billed Gull – 2019–23

Ring-billed Gull – 2019–23 - yearly totals

2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
8	6	5	14	3

Yellow-legged Gull *Larus michahellis* (subspecies: *michahellis*; *atlantis*)

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
428	1	315 (minimum)	112

One hundred and twelve birds in 2019–23, returning birds have been excluded where possible. Numbers peak in the autumn, with a smaller spring peak. Numbers have increased over the years, with a peak of thirty-four birds in 2020. A bird ringed at the Camargue, France, appeared as a juvenile in September 2020 at Kennedy Quay, Cork city, returned each September, and remained until November or December into 2023. Most birds recorded are adults.

Yellow-legged Gull – 2004–2023

Yellow-legged Gull – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Cork City	2	10	6	3	7	28
Cork Harbour	6	11		6	1	24
The Gearagh	8	6	4	0	4	22
Timoleague		5		4	3	12
Ballycotton	6	1	1	1		9
Rosscarbery	3	1		2		6
Clonakilty	1		1	2	1	5
Blackrock					2	2
Kinsale Marsh	2					2

Baltimore			1			1
Youghal					1	1
Total	28	34	13	18	19	112

Yellow-legged Gull – 2004–2023

Glaucous Gull *Larus hyperboreus*

Fifty birds were recorded in 2019–23 - seven in 2019, twenty-two in 2020, five in 2021, ten in 2022, and six in 2023. The species has declined over the years, probably due to milder winters and changes in fishing practices. Almost all were single birds, with two together on just two dates. Castletownbere had the highest total with seven birds over the period.

Glaucous Gull – 2004–2023

Lesser Black-backed Gull *Larus fuscus*

Very large increase in breeding numbers recorded - from 227 AON in Seabird 2000 to 2542 AON in Seabirds Count (2015-21). While there was better coverage in the latter survey, the species increased substantially in Ireland. These do not include Cork City birds (see Urban Breeding Gulls in Cork City pp153)

Lesser Black-backed Gull - breeding AON - Seabird 2000 and Seabirds Count (2015-21)

Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count	Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count
Dursey Island, Beara	4	31	Baltimore to Glandore Harbour	0	368

Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count	Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count
Kenmare River and Islands	13	103	Rosscarbery Bay	0	4
Beara Peninsula - Outer	0	12	Galley Head	0	1
Bere Island (Bear Island)	0	30	Galley Head / Seven Heads	0	4
Brow Head/Mizen Head	0	163	Old Head	0	3
Dunmanus Bay	0	25	Kinsale	0	310
Bantry Bay Islands	0	50	Ringabella to Kinsale	0	17
Roaringwater Bay (Inner and Outer)	0	1383	Cork Harbour to Youghal Harbour	6	12
Cape Clear	204	26			
Survey totals and % change			1020%	227	2542

Lesser Black-backed Gull— i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
<u>County total mean peak</u>	2606	1751	3226	2964	1975	5146	933
Ballymacoda	1631	328	1456	651		3108	
Courtmacherry , Broadstrand & Dunworley	1165	1004	855	1550	1584	1217	
Ballycotton Shanagarry	586	445	1544	143	52	821	70
Inishcarra Reservoirs	280	400	200	203	254	150	395
Cork Harbour	232	220	124	153	307	178	330
Lissagriffin Lake	191	355	195	16	140	130	136
Clonakilty Bay	186	95	154	2	248	195	237
Rosscarbery	151	185	75	330	115	220	159
Bateman's Lough	89	27	40	22	230	60	
Ballybutler	86	142	96	0		0	106

European Herring Gull *Larus argentatus*

There was a substantial increase in breeding numbers recorded - from 289 AON in Seabird 2000 to 2,866 AON in Seabirds Count (2015–21). However, coverage was better in the latter survey. These do not include Cork City birds.

Herring Gull - breeding AON - Seabird 2000 and Seabirds Count (2015-21)

Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count	Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count
Bull Rock	0	20	Roaringwater Bay (Inner and Outer)	0	231
Dursey Island, Beara	20	36	Cape Clear	46	26
Beara Peninsula - North	0	12	Baltimore to Glandore Harbour	0	503
Kenmare River and Islands	65	20	Rosscarbery Bay	0	32
Beara Peninsula - Outer	0	91	Galley Head	0	20
Bere Island	0	219	Galley Head / Seven Heads	0	90
Brow Head/Mizen Head	30	156	West Cork	23	121
Brow Head	0	4	Old Head	15	50
Sheep's Head	0	34	Kinsale	0	304
Dunmanus Bay	0	180	Ringabella to Kinsale	4	129
Bantry Bay Islands	19	462	Cork Harbour to Youghal Harbour	67	126
Survey totals and % change			892%	289	2866

Herring Gull - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	2058	2235	2218	1931	2126	1937	1776
Courtmacsherry, Broadstrand & Dunworley	562	320	596	938	628	706	
Bear Haven	338	437	434	411	344	214	263
Ilen Estuary	330	804	566	1	151	127	2
Stick Estuary (Oysterhaven)	267	80	23		30	327	873
Bantry Bay	241	147	239	46	204	257	357

Clonakilty Bay	215	210	120	101	306	256	184
Lissagriffin Lake	209	202	282	196	210	140	210
Cork Harbour	182	129	181	253	196	171	232
Ballymacoda	156	98	183	45		186	
Ballycotton Shanagarry	152	263	233	169	33	148	85

American Herring Gull *Larus smithsonianus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
38	0	36	2

Two birds recorded - Castletownbere 6–28 February 2020 and Sherkin Island on 31 January, and later at Baltimore on 6 February 2023.

Iceland Gull *Larus glaucooides* (subspecies: *glaucooides*; *kumlieni*)

One hundred birds were recorded in 2019–23. Birds occurred widely along the coast from almost forty locations, with sixteen from Cork City accounting for the highest totals. Five birds were recorded twice, at Tivoli on 14 February 2020 and Gearhies, on 12 December 2020.

Kumlien's Gull –1959–2023

Kumlien's Gull *Larus glaucooides kumlieni*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
54	0	50 individuals (48 in BOC)	4

Four recorded in 2019–23 - first-winter at Cahermore on 20 January 2019; second-winter at Eyries on 28 February 2019; first-winter Cork City on 6 February and an adult at Bantry on 4 April 2023.

Great Black-backed Gull *Larus marinus*

There was a substantial increase in breeding numbers recorded - from 201 AON in Seabird 2000 to 480 AON in Seabirds Count (2015-21). As with other gull species, coverage improved, but numbers have also increased around Ireland.

Great Black-backed Gull - breeding AON - Seabird 2000 and Seabirds Count (2015-21)

Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count	Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count
Bull Rock	0	2	Bantry Bay Islands	8	22
Dursey Island, Beara	0	5	Roaringwater Bay (Inner and Outer)	0	107
Beara Peninsula - North	0	2	Cape Clear	41	12
Kenmare River and Islands	7	66	Baltimore to Glandore Harbour	0	121
Beara Peninsula - Outer	0	30	Rosscarbery Bay	0	1
Bere Island	0	18	Galley Head / Seven Heads	0	6
Bere Island	0	7	West Cork	12	16
Brow Head/ Mizen Head	0	24	Kinsale	0	8
Sheep's Head	1	1	Ringabella to Kinsale	0	4
Dunmanus Bay	0	9	Cork Harbour to Youghal Harbour	132	19
Survey totals and % change			139%	201	480

Great Black-backed Gull - iWeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24-1

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	479	457	692	1084	317	618	312
Ballymacoda	225	74	279	796		323	
Cork Harbour	127	179	136	95	131	104	87
Bantry Bay	85	29	240	10	80	46	31

Ballycotton Shanagarry	81	73	121	61	30	80	101
Courtmacsherry , Broadstrand & Dunworley	67	53	63	43	115	38	
Ilen Estuary	57	117	88	5	26	53	3
Bear Haven	55	50	118	64	34	30	44
Lissagriffin Lake	52	51	32	21	53	42	82
Myross Island & Inlet (Blind Harbour)	36	51	20	15	17	30	61
Dunmanus Bay	29	13	4	4	26	46	54

Long-tailed Skua *Stercorarius longicaudus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
126	0	78	48

Forty-eight birds were recorded in 2019–23, a notable increase. Eight birds in a day occurred twice, at Galley Head - 28 June 2022 and 6 September 2022. Most birds occur in September, but a considerable number are in July. Three birds were seen over The Lough on 31 July 2023, during a period when birds were being seen on the coast. All birds were seen between 3 June and 11 November.

Long-tailed Skua – 2004–2023

Long-tailed Skua – 2004–2023

Long-tailed Skua - 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Cape Clear			4	1		5
Cork City					3	3
Galley Head		3		21	3	27
Garinish Point	1				1	2
Mizen Head			1		1	2
Seven Heads					1	1
Toe Head	1			4	3	8
Total	2	3	5	26	12	48

Arctic Skua *Stercorarius parasiticus*

Two-hundred and seventy-eight birds were recorded in 2019–23, the majority in the latter two years. Peak counts were twenty-one at Cape Clear on 3 October 2022 and fourteen at Galley Head on 28 June 2022. All records were between 20 April and 11 November.

Arctic Skua - 2008–23

Arctic Skua - 2019–23

Arctic Skua - 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Ballycotton		1	4	12	3	20
Bantry					1	1
Cape Clear	15	1	9	39	42	106
Castletownsend					1	1
Cork Harbour				1		1
Dursey Island					3	3
Galley Cove		2				2
Galley Head		2		34	20	56
Garinish Point	3		2	1	2	8
Lehanemore	1					1
Mizen Head	1		5		4	10
Old Head of Kinsale	1				1	2
Seven Heads	2	2			10	14
Toe Head	13	8	1	23	6	51
Union Hall					2	2
Total	36	16	21	110	95	278

Pomarine Skua *Stercorarius pomarinus*

In 2019–23, 106 birds were recorded, below average, with four in 2019 the lowest since at least 2004. Maximum count was seven birds at Galley Head on 7 July 2023. All birds were recorded between 11 May and 11 November, with peak numbers in July

Pomarine Skua – 2004–2023

Pomarine Skua – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Ballycotton	2		5	8	4	19
Buttevant				1		1
Cape Clear	2	1	3	2	1	9
Galley Head		6	3	5	40	54
Garinish Point					1	1
Mizen Head			3			3
Old Head of Kinsale					1	1
Seven Heads		2			1	3
Sherkin Island					1	1
Toe Head		5		4	11	20
Total	4	14	14	20	60	106

Great Skua *Stercorarius skua*

In 2019–23, 355 birds were recorded, with forty-eight in 2023, the lowest number since at least 2008. The species has declined, and this predated the Bird Flu pandemic that affected Great Skua populations. Maximum counts were twenty-eight on 12 September 2021 and twenty-six on 21 September 2019, both at Cape Clear. All birds were recorded between 10 April and 11 November, with peak numbers in August and September.

Great Skua – 2004–2023

Great Skua – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Ballycotton		1	3	7	3	14
Cape Clear	87	3	50	42	18	200
Castletownsend			1			1
Dursey Island					2	2
Galley Cove		4				4
Galley Head	2	27		10	11	50
Garinish Point	1	14		1		16
Knockadoon Head	1					1
Mizen Head	1	1	8		1	11
Old Head of Kinsale		1			1	2
Seven Heads	3	5			1	9
Sherkin Island					6	6
Toe Head	12	20		2	2	36
Union Hall					3	3
Total	107	76	62	62	48	355

Puffin *Fratercula arctica*

Many counts of twenty to fifty birds from seawatches, with maximum counts at Cape Clear of 301 on 3 October 2022; 2,501 on 10 April 2022; 3,500 on 2 May 2019. Galley Head 121 on 7 July 2023; Ballycotton 120 on 10 April 2022.

No evidence of breeding was received.

Black Guillemot *Cephus grylle* (subspecies: *arcticus*)

Black Guillemot breeding in Cork appears to have increased in line with the Irish population.

Black Guillemot - breeding individuals - Seabird 2000 and Seabirds Count

Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count	Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count
Dursey Island -	0	1	Kedge Island area	54	56
			-		

Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count	Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count
Beara Peninsula -	131	196	Lough Hyne - Glandore -	23	51
Kenmare River -	42	58	Seven Head -	0	20
Mizen Head -	24	40	Seven Heads -	0	4
Dunmanus Bay South -	8	34	Kinsale area -	6	0
Sheep's Head Peninsula -	91	101	Ringabella - Kinsale -	81	37
Cape Clear -	111	108	Cork (East) -	2	11
Roaringwater Bay -	82	72			
Survey totals and % change			21%	655	789

Razorbill *Alca torda* (subspecies: *islandica*; *torda*)

The Irish population has increased from Seabird 2000, though still lower than Operation Seafarer 1969–70.

Razorbill - breeding individuals - Seabird 2000 and Seabirds Count

Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count	Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count
Cape Clear	25	9	Ringabella to Kinsale	13	119
Brow Head/ Mizzen Head	0	8	Old Head of Kinsale	83	352
Dursey Island, Beara	7	0	Galley Head / Seven Heads	0	45
Bull Rock	0	15	Baltimore to Glandore Harbour	0	23
Survey totals and % change			346%	128	571

Common Guillemot *Uria aalge*

Substantial increase in individuals recorded between the two breeding surveys, reflecting increases across Ireland.

Common Guillemot - breeding individuals - Seabird 2000 and Seabirds Count (2015-21)

Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count	Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count
Bull Rock	0	322	Galley Head / Seven Heads	0	1510
Brow Head/ Mizen Head	0	96	Old Head	3610	4157
Brow Head/ Mizen Head	0	53	Ringabella to Kinsale	121	233
Cape Clear	32	42			
Survey totals and % change			70%	3763	6413

Little Auk *Alle alle*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
-	-	509- ?	9

Nine birds were recorded in 2019–23. In Birds of Cork, a total of 509 birds for the period 1959–2018 was given; however, some records are under review, and records for August and September will probably be removed.

One at Dursey Island, 24 October 2021; two at Garretstown, 9 November 2021; one at Ballycotton, 8 December 2021; one at Dursey Island, 15 January 2022; two at Ballycotton, 10 April 2022; one at Ballycotton, 17 December 2023 and one at Ballycotton, 24 December 2023.

Red-throated Diver *Gavia stellata*

Highest count was 100 birds on 10 January 2021, with other counts of forty to sixty birds in the Toormore/Crookhaven area; eighteen at Ballybranagan on 16 January 2022; fifty-nine at Barleycove on 14 March 2022.

One at Gearagh on 10 October 2023 appears to be only the second inland record.

Red-throated Diver - iWeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
Crookhaven	17	1	35	0	10	20	20
Barley Cove Bay	16	15	5	0	59	0	2

Black-throated Diver *Gavia arctica*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
263	0	218	45

Forty-five birds were recorded in 2019–23, an average showing, with typically most birds to the west of Galley Head. Bantry Bay, near the airstrip, is the most consistent site in the county. There were no counts of more than two birds. All records were between 4 October and 23 May. Some are probably returning birds.

Black-throated Diver – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Adrigole				2		2
Ballycotton	1		1	2	1	5
Ballylickey	1					1
Bantry bay	2	1	2	2	2	9
Coolemaine Head	2					2
Crookhaven	1	2				4
Crow Head					1	1
Heir Island					1	1
Long Strand		2		4		6
Owenahincha				3	1	4
Rosscarbery		1			1	2
Schull		2			1	3
Sherkin Island					2	2
Toormore	1	1	1		1	4
Total	8	9	4	13	11	45

Pacific Diver *Gavia pacifica*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
1	0	1	0

The bird first recorded on 18 January – 18 April 2018 at Crookhaven, has continued to return - 7 October 2018 – 28 March 2019; 19 October 2019 – 3 March 2020; 31 October 2021 – 19 March 2022; 20–21 May 2023 and 27 October – 4 November. The bird continued into 2025.

Leach's Petrel *Anodroma leucorhoa*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
-	-	-	18

Eighteen birds recorded in 2019–23 - sixteen in 2022 and two in 2020. The species is not recorded every year and thirty-five birds in 2006 was the last influx. All birds were recorded between 5 September and 23 November, apart from one at Gearagh on 12 April 2020.

Leach's Storm Petrel – 2019–23

Ballycotton	2 November 2022	1	Garnish Point	21 October 2020	1
Ballycotton	11 November 2022	4	Garnish point	30 September 2022	1
Ballycotton	13 November 2022	1	Garnish point	5 October 2022	1
Ballycotton	23 November 2022	2	Roches Point	13 November 2022	1
Galley Head	7 September 2022	1	The Gearagh	12 April 2020	1
Galley Head	11 November 2022	2	Toe Head	5 September 2022	2

Fulmar *Fulmarus glacialis*

The Irish population of Fulmar has been stable between the two recent surveys, though the British population has seen substantial declines.

Northern Fulmar - breeding AOS - Seabird 2000 and Seabirds Count (2015-21)

Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count	Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count
Dursey Island, Beara	575	487	Rosscarbery Bay	0	49
Beara Peninsula - North	0	12	Galley Head	0	19
Beara Peninsula - Outer	0	35	Galley Head / Seven Heads	0	182

Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count	Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count
Bere Island (Bear Island)	0	111	West Cork	18	11
Brow Head/Mizen Head	46	275	Old Head	40	115
Sheep's Head	11	158	Kinsale	0	7
Roaringwater Bay (Inner and Outer)	0	135	Ringabella to Kinsale	228	571
Cape Clear	466	527	Cork Harbour to Youghal Harbour	185	91
Baltimore to Glandore Harbour	0	365			
Survey totals and % change			101%	1569	3150

Gadfly petrel species *Pterodroma sp*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
88	0	70	18

Eleven birds recorded in 2019–23. Two passed Galley Head on 24 August 2022, and the presumed same two birds passed Myross Island and Cape Clear later that day. Birds were recorded between 6 July and 19 September.

One, Baltimore pelagic, 20 August 2019; One, Galley Head, 5 August 2020; One, Galley Head, 20 August 2020; At least two: Two, Galley Head, 24 July 2022, and presumed same, Cape Clear Island, 24 July and Myross Island, 24 July. One, off Ballycotton, 6 July 2023; Off Galley Head: One, 6 July, 2023, One, 30th July 2023, One, 19 August 2023; One, off Mizen Head, 19 August 2023; One, off Cape Clear Island, 19 September 2023.

Cory's Shearwater *Calonectris borealis*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
101,747	0	53,077	48,670

The year 2023 saw the start of a very large influx of large shearwaters in autumn that continued into 2024 and 2025. The total of 39,774 in 2023 was the highest recorded - 1980 with 14,356 was the previous peak year. Maximum counts were 4,542 at Toe Head on 11 August and 4,140 at Galley Head on 28 July, both 2023. All birds were between 25 June and 18 November (the only record for that month).

Cory's Shearwater – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Ballycotton				2,867	5,299	8,166
Black Ball Head		2				2
Brow Head					15	15
Cahermore		1				1
Cape Clear	145	10	67	3,125	9,012	12,359
Dursey Island		1		1	1,027	1,029
Fastnet Rock		6				6
Galley Cove					15	15
Galley Head	39	463		1,818	11,300	13,620
Keameen Point					284	284
Knockadoon head					35	35
Mizen Head	1				3,770	3,771
Myross Island					18	18
Old Head of Kinsale	1				645	646
Seven Heads		23			1,454	1,477
Sherkin Island					17	17
Toe Head		300		26	6,843	7,169
Union Hall					40	40
Total	186	806	67	7,837	39,774	48,670

Sooty Shearwater *Ardenna griseus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
-	-	-	14,096

In 2019–23, 14,096 birds were recorded - the numbers in 2023 were one of the highest recorded in the county. At Cape Clear, the peak counts were 3,470 on 28 October 2023 and 1,345 on 7 October 2021. All records were between 24 June and 27 December. There was a notable early count of 230 birds at Galley Head on 28 June 2022. Typically, numbers peak in October, which is later than for the other large shearwaters.

Pacific Diver *Gavia pacifica*, Crookhaven, February 2020, R.T. Mills

Leach's Storm Petrel *Oceanodroma leucorhoa*, the Gearagh, April 2020, R.T.Mills

Sooty Shearwater – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Ballycotton		14	9	25	332	380
Brow Head		30				30
Cape Clear	468	186	2,387	363	4,234	7,638
Castletownshend		2				2
Dursey Island			4		306	310
Galley Head	1	234		436	848	1,519
Garinish Point	36	59	68	104	61	328
Keameen Point					6	6
Mizen Head	2	8	1,618	11	1,603	3,242
Old Head of Kinsale					66	66
Seven Heads	3	78			71	152
Toe Head	11	150	14	1	227	403
Union Hall					20	20
Total	521	761	4,100	940	7,774	14,096

later than for the other large shearwaters.

Sooty Shearwater – 2004–23

Sooty Shearwater – 2019–23

Scopoli's Shearwater *Calonectris diomedea*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
1	0	0	1

A pelagic off Baltimore on 12 August 2022 produced the first Irish record of Scopoli's Shearwater.

Great Shearwater *Ardenna gravis*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
-	-	80,231	7,082

Good numbers were recorded in 2022 and 2023, though the thirty-two in 2019 was the lowest since 2007. Peak counts were 3,007 at Cape Clear on 14 September 2023 and 1,500 at Galley Head on 7 September 2022. All records were between 28 June and 23 December - two on 23 December were the first for that month.

Great Shearwater – 2004–23

Great Shearwater – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Ballycotton	2	3	3	462	44	514
Brow Head		1				1
Cape Clear	27	1	76	203	145	452
Castletownsend			1		1	2
Crookhaven			50			50
Dursey Island				2	36	38
Fastnet Rock		1				1
Galley Head		216		1,643	3,384	5,243
Mizen Head			101		164	265

Seven Heads		3			62	65
Toe Head	3	100	1	2	345	451
Total	32	325	232	2,312	4,181	7,082

Manx Shearwater *Puffinus puffinus*

Some high counts

Galley Head 2,400 per hour 23 March 2023

Cape Clear 9,000 per hour 28 June 2022

Cape Clear 20,000 19 July 2019

Galley Head 10,000 7 July 2023

Mediterranean Shearwater *Puffinus mauretanicus*

Mediterranean Shearwaters have declined markedly in the last few years, and three in 2020 was the lowest since 1987, when there were no records. The highest count was six at Cape Clear on 21 July 2019. All were recorded between 25 June and 12 December, apart from one on 6 February

Mediterranean Shearwater – 2004–23

Mediterranean Shearwater – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Ballycotton	3	1	5	3	4	16
Cape Clear	6		2		1	9
Galley Head		1			3	4
Mizen Head	1				1	2
Seven Heads		1			4	5
Toe Head	3			1	2	6
Total	13	3	7	4	15	42

Great Shearwater *Ardenna gravis* and Sooty Shearwater *Ardenna griseus*, at sea 10 km south Toe Head August 2022, J. Lynch

Cory's Shearwater *Calonectris borealis*, at sea 10 km south Toe Head August 2022, J. Lynch and Seven Heads, August 2023, M.Shorten

Gannet, *Morus bassanus*

The Bull Rock, the only breeding site in Cork for Gannets, has continued to increase in population.

Northern Gannet- breeding AOS - Seabird 2000 and Seabirds Count (2015-21)

	S. 2000	G. Census 2003-05	2013-14 & 2015-21	2021 Estimate
Bull Rock	1,879	3,694	6,388	9,400

Great Cormorant, *Phalacrocorax carbo* (subspecies: *carbo*; *sinensis*)

The Irish population has been fairly stable (small decline) between surveys.

Great Cormorant - breeding AON - Seabird 2000 and Seabirds Count (2015-21)

Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count	Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count
Kenmare River and Islands	0	3	Roaringwater Bay (Inner and Outer)	0	64
Beara Peninsula - Outer	0	11	Baltimore to Glandore Harbour	0	64
Brow Head/Mizen Head	0	3	Galley Head / Seven Heads	0	10
Dunmanus Bay	0	18	West Cork	60	48
Bantry Bay Islands	52	18	Cork Harbour to Youghal Harbour	254	233
Survey totals and % change			29%	366	472

Great Cormorant - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24-1-1

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
Cork Harbour	431	189	342	26	401	728	495
Bantry Bay	123	122	80	3	251	87	74
Ballymacoda	30	31	29	43		29	
Crookhaven	29	16	24	28	25	42	37
Courtmacsherry, Broadstrand & Dunworley	19	27	11	27	24	13	
Inishcarra Reservoirs	18	24	7	20	28	16	14
Glandore Union Hall	16		6	10	11	24	21
Ardgroom Harbour	15	16	16		11	8	22

Scopoli's Shearwater *Calonectris diomedea*, off Baltimore August 2022,
P.Connaughton

European Shag, *Phalacrocorax aristotelis*

The substantial increase in breeding numbers has been reflected in other colonies in Ireland.

European Shag- breeding AON - Seabird 2000 and Seabirds Count (2015-21)

Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count	Site	Seabird 2000	Seabirds Count
Dursey Island, Beara	12	21	Roaringwater Bay (Inner and Outer)	0	61
Beara Peninsula - North	0	28	Cape Clear	64	65
Kenmare River and Islands	0	12	Baltimore to Glandore Harbour	0	66
Beara Peninsula - Outer	0	30	Rosscarbery Bay	0	2
Bere Island (Bear Island)	0	50	Galley Head	0	7
Brow Head/ Mizen Head	17	29	Galley Head / Seven Heads	0	9
Sheep's Head	0	58	Old Head	30	56
Dunmanus Bay	0	3	Ringabella to Kinsale	16	87
Bantry Bay Islands	82	89			
Survey totals and % change			204%	221	673

Highest counts were from Cape Clear, with regular counts of over 100 birds in September and October 2019 and a peak of 463 on 14 September. Elsewhere, at Roche's Point, there was a peak of 174 birds on 10 November 2019.

Single birds at Gearagh on 6 August 2019 and 26 August 2020, the first inland records in the county.

Shag - iWeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24-1

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
Bantry Bay	35	32	34	34	29	29	53
Barley Cove Bay	29	15	38	49	30	36	25
Cork Harbour	20	12	5	3	13	23	47
Bear Haven	18	13	9	6	19	26	25
Clonakilty Bay	17	22	20	3	8	31	4
Crookhaven	11	7	3	10	16	20	11

Glossy Ibis, *Plegadis falcinellus*

The increase in birds that started in 2011 has continued, with totals of twenty-two in 2019, seven in 2020, sixteen in 2021, forty-seven in 2022, and seventeen in 2023. Birds were recorded at about thirty sites, with peak counts of twenty-one at Nohoval on 1–4 January 2022 and nine at Clonakilty from 11 January to 14 March 2019. Most birds were recorded within a few kilometres of the coast, though there were small numbers at Ballineen/Enniskeane and the Gearagh. Birds arrived from September, but the main arrival was in January, with one bird at Pilmore remaining from 11 November 2019 to 30 August 2020.

Glossy Ibis *Plegadis falcinellus*, White’s Marsh, January 2019, S.Cronin

Spoonbill *Platalea leucorodia*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
55	25	30	1

Despite increasing numbers being recorded elsewhere in Ireland, the species remains scarce, with just one record - 16 May 2019 at Courtmacsherry.

Great Bittern *Botaurus stellaris*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
-	-	6	1

One record of a bird at the Gearagh from 4–24 January 2023 - the first record since 2014. This former breeder remains very rare.

Great Bittern *Botaurus stellaris*, the Gearagh
January 2022, S.Cronin and J.Lynch

Night Heron *Nycticorax nycticorax*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
67	8	31	28

An unprecedented influx of twenty-seven birds in 2023 - four in 1994 was the previous maximum in a year. In 2023, twenty birds were in April, singles in August and May, and three in July.

A bird present at Crookhaven on 30 April and 1 May 2019.

2023 - twenty-seven records - Immature, North Harbour, Cape Clear, 4–8 April, when joined by an adult, with both present until 9 April; One, between Union Hall and Leap, 4 April; Adult, Dursey Island, 5 April; Adult, River Bandon at Upper Manch, 7 April; Adult, Mizen Head, 10 April, with two present on 11 April; Adult, Ballydehob, 13th–17th April; Adult, Rostellan Lake, 15–23 April, photographed; Adult, River Blackwater, near Fermoy, 16–21 April; Adult, Toormore, 17 April, photographed; Adult, Long Strand, 17 April; Up to four, River Ilen, Skibbereen, 20th April to 3rd May, with all four present, 27 April, photographed; Adult, Owenacurra River, Midleton, 22 April to 13 June; Adult, Ballyvergan Marsh, near Youghal, 22 April to 7 May; Adult, Ballinacarriga Lake, near Dunmanway, 23 April; Adult, Oysterhaven Biodiversity Reserve, 1 May; Up to four (two adults and two first-summers), The Gearagh, 20 July to 1 August, with all four present, 22 July, photographed; Second calendar-year, Clogheen Marsh and Muckcross EsTuary, near Clonakilty, 21 July, and, presumed same, Muckcross Estuary and White’s Marsh, Clonakilty, 22 July; Adult, Lissagriffin, 22 July; Second-summer, River Blackwater at Fermoy, 13 August.

Little Egret *Egretta garzetta*

Notable that Little Egret is more frequent than Grey Heron on many i-WeBS counts.

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
241	19	113	109

Little Egret - i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	267	230	217	278	257	355	278
Cork Harbour	151	134	127	145	113	190	193
Clonakilty Bay	31	16	20	5	40	51	28
Courtmacsherry, Broadstrand & Dunworley	25	15	29	32	39	17	
Ballymacoda	24	15	18	28		39	
Ilen Estuary	17	9	14	4	23	34	5
Inishcarra Reservoirs	16	21	7	16	17	19	17
Rosscarbery	16	12	6	18	23	20	20
Ballycotton Shanagarry	11	14	11	4	6	16	7

Squacco Heron *Ardeola ralloides*

Squacco Heron *Ardeola ralloides*, White’s Marsh, May 2023, S.Cronin

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
8	5	2	1

An immature bird was at White’s Marsh from 27 May to 8 June 2023.

Great Egret *Ardea alba* (subspecies: *alba*)

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
61	0	22	39

Thirty-nine new birds were recorded in 2019–23; however, there were a number of long-staying birds - at the Gearagh, with two birds presumed to be continuing from 2018. Given the long-staying birds, it is difficult to know how many birds are actually involved. October is the main month of arrival, and most birds are gone by the end of April.

Great Egret – 2019–23

Great Egret – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Ballycotton		1				1
Bantry			1			1
Buttevant					1	1
Carrigtwohill			1			1
Castlefreke			1			1
Clonakilty			1	4	1	6
Courtmacsherry			2			2
Enniskeane		1				1
Glandore			1			1
Great Island				1		1
Halfway			1			1

Harper's Island					2	1
Kilcolman Fen					1	1
Kilkeran Lake				1		1
Killeena		2				2
Kinsale				1		1
Lissagriffin		2	1			3
Lough Aderra			1			1
Old Court			1			1
River Ilen Estuary		4				3
Rosscarbery	1					1
Rostellan	1		1			2
Schull		1				1
The Gearagh	1	2	0	1	0	4
Total	3	11	12	8	5	39

Western Cattle Egret *Bubulcus ibis*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
329	0	198 (214 in BOC)	131

The first influx of Cattle Egrets began in 2007–09 and the more recent influx starting in 2016. Most records are within a few kilometres of the coast. The largest and most consistent flock is at Timoleague, with birds present regularly there since 2019 (there were previous records there from 2008–09 and 2017) with peak numbers of nineteen birds in December 2022 to April 2023 and November 2023. Birds were recorded in all months, with main arrival in October and also November and December, many overwintering. Almost all birds depart by the third week of April.

Cattle Egret – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total	
Baltimore			1			1	
Bantry					3	3	
Cape Clear					1	1	
Carrigaline	4	2				6	
Clonakilty				2	3	2	7

East Ferry	2	1				3
Enniskeane				1		1
Fota	1					1
Galley Head				3		3
Glengarriff	1					1
Harper's Island					1	1
Kikeran Lake				0		0
Kinsale Marsh		1				1
Lackahane	3					3
Leap				4		4
Lisheen		3				3
Little island	3					3
Lough Aderra					5	5
Lough Clubir	1	5	0	4	2	12
Macroom	1					1
Old Head of Kinsale				2		2
Rosscarbery			1	7	1	9
Rossleague	3					3
Rostellan					4	4
Skibbereen				2		2
Slatty's bridge	2				4	6
The Lough				1		1
Timoleague	8	4	8	20	0	40
Youghal		2	2			4
Total	29	19	13	47	23	131

Grey Heron *Ardea cinerea*

Grey Heron- i-WeBS counts 2018/19 to 2023/24-1

	Mean_peak	2018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
County total mean peak	194	242	168	157	168	174	218
Cork Harbour	109	100	99	105	103	94	150

Courtmacsherry, Broadstrand & Dunworley	15	16	14	17	22	9	
Ilen Estuary	14	10	17	5	21	22	2
Ballymacoda	13	12	18	7		8	
Clonakilty Bay	13	16	12	3	12	10	13
Inishcarra Reservoirs	12	12	9	8	11	12	17

Purple Heron *Ardea purpurea*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
20	0	14	6

Six birds in 2019–23 were above average. Apart from two birds in 1987, 2023 is the only year with more than one bird. All records have been between 19 March and 13 June, with single records in August and October. Rostellan on 19 May 2019; Dunworley from 22 May to 3 June 2021; Clogheen on 15 May and 5 June 2022, and presumed same at White’s Marsh 27–30 May 2022; Cape Clear on 7–10 April 2023; Mizen Head on 10 April 2023, and Rostellan on 22 June 2023.

Osprey *Pandion haliaetus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
160	10	93	57

Fifty-seven Ospreys were recorded in 2019–23, eight in 2019, three in 2020, nine in 2021, seventeen in 2022, and a record twenty in 2023. Birds were very widely recorded from about thirty locations. Most favoured were Timoleague (8), The Gearagh (6), Cape Clear (4), and Harper’s Island (4). All birds recorded between 17 April and 7 November. Spring peak is in April and September in autumn. The increase in records ties in with the recommencement of Osprey breeding in Ireland in recent years.

Most records were coastal, particularly on estuaries, though one remained at the Gearagh from 20 July to 7 August 2023.

Osprey – 1959–2023

Honey Buzzard *Pernis apivorus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
3	0	2	1

A juvenile seen passing east over Dursey Island on 1 October 2023, the third county record.

Osprey *Pandion haliaetus*, Courtmacsherry, September 2021, S.Cronin

Honey Buzzard *Pernis apivorus* Dursey Island October 2023, N.Linehan

Goshawk *Accipiter gentilis*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
-	1	22	1

An adult at an undisclosed location on 13 April 2019. Still a rare bird in Cork.

Montagu's Harrier *Circus pygargus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
12	0	11	1

A second-calendar male was at Currahy Marsh, Dunworley on 30 April 2019 and presumably the same at Ballyvergan on 17 May.

Pallid Harrier *Circus macrourus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
5	0	4	1

A juvenile at Three Castles Head on 23 October 2022 was the fifth county record.

Hen Harrier *Circus cyaneus*

The decline of Hen Harrier as a breeding species continues. Particularly concerning is the Ballyhours, formerly the main haunt in Cork, and their extinction in the Nagles. In the 2005 survey, about 25% of the Irish population bred in the areas listed in the table below, with just about 14% in 2022 - of a reduced Irish population (Ruddock, M. 2024)

Hen Harrier Regional population estimates - not all pairs are in Cork

County region	Total pairs 1998-2000	Total pairs 2005	Total pairs 2010	Total pairs 2015	Total pairs 2022	Change since 2015 (%)
Ballyhours	6-8	17-19	10-15	10-12	6-7	-42%
Boggeraghs, Derrynasaggarts	4-5	5	6-8	2-4	5	25%
East Cork and Waterford	0-1	2	1	1	0-1	0%
Knockmealdowns, Kilworth, Comeraghs	3-7	2-4	2	5-7	1-2	-27%
Nagles	3-5	9	7-11	5	0	-100
West Cork	0	0	0	0-1	0	-100

Northern Harrier *Circus hudsonianus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
1	0	0	1

A juvenile at Barry’s Head, Nohoval on 2–12 October 2020 was the first county record.

Marsh Harrier *Circus aeruginosus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
-	-	129	13

An average number of records, though seven in 2021 is a record. All were females or immature birds.

Marsh Harrier –2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2023	Total
Ballinascarty				1	1
Ballycotton		1	2		3
Clonakilty	1		2		3
Lough Beg			1		1
Mizen Head				1	1
Owenahinca			1		1
Rathduff		1			1
The Gearagh	1		1		2
Total	2	2	7	2	13

Red Kite *Milvus milvus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
-	-	28	13

Thirteen birds in 2019–23 is a notable increase in records. There has been no evidence of breeding in Cork, though there have been suggestions of it happening in Waterford. Apart from the Inchy Bridge bird, all birds remained for a day or two at most.

Red Kite – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Baltimore				1		1

Belgooley		1				1
Inchy Bridge/Bandon		1				1
Bishopstown	1					1
Cape Clear	1				1	2
Castlelyons		1				1
Drimoleague				1		1
Fermoy			1			1
Galley Head	2					2
Inchy Bridge		1				1
Sherkin Island	1					1
Total	5	4	1	2	1	13

Black Kite *Milvus migrans*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
10	0	7	3

Three records in 2019–23 - at least a second-calendar bird at Cape Clear on 24 August 2021 and presumably the same at Garinish on 30 August. One at Knockadoon on 12 April 2022. An at least second-calendar bird at Lissagriffin on 22 April 2022.

Fig. 1 Movement of 2023 White-tailed Eagle, Killarney release male tag 29, Aug-Dec 2023.

White-tailed Eagle *Haliaeetus albicilla*

White-tailed Eagles have nested almost annually at Glengarriff since 2014, with a second site occupied by a trio (one male and two females) in 2018 and by a single female in 2019–2020. Single chicks fledged from the Glengarriff site in three of the five years (Table 1). Interestingly, a new female ousted the original breeding female at Glengarriff in 2019, while a new male took up residence there in 2021.

Table 1. Breeding data for White-tailed Eagles in Co. Cork, 2019–2023.

Year	Territories	Active nests	Hatching	Fledged
2019	2	1	1	0
2020	2	1	1	1
2021	1	0	0	0
2022	1	1	1	1
2023	1	1	1	1

While the Irish population increased slowly during the period from nine to thirteen territorial pairs (seven-to-ten, nesting) across six counties, there were no additional pairs in Cork. However, multiple birds, including Irish-bred eagles, have spent extensive time along the south-west and south coast, especially the Beara peninsula (Fig. 1).

One satellite-tagged Glengarriff check (2020 Sunniva) spent much of 2022–2023 exploring the west coast from SW Cork to Mayo, spending extensive periods of time in the Wild Nephin National Park area of Mayo.

Common Buzzard *Buteo buteo*

Now a widespread breeding species in the county. There are clear signs of southwesterly movement in the autumn. Mapping with eBird and BirdTrack 2015–23 (using frequency of occurrence in complete checklists) shows that Buzzard is the commonest bird prey in the county, though more

Map 1. Buzzard - occurrence in completed checklists - eBird and BirdTrack 2015–23

scarce to the west of the county. Peak counts all came from Mizen Head - seventy-two on 15 October 2023; fifty-two on 12 October 2021; twenty-nine on 15 October 2021 and twenty-five on 16 August 2023.

Barn Owl *Tyto alba*

In McCarthy (2023), Barn Owl population status and trends in County Cork, 383 sites were surveyed and 143 occupied Barn Owl sites were found (Map 1), of which 114 were confirmed breeding sites. Eighty-nine (62%) of the occupied sites were traditional Barn Owl sites which were known to be previously used by Barn Owl during the last 32 years. Fifty-four sites (38%) were confirmed for the first time in 2023. A comparison of the current confirmed Barn Owl breeding range to the breeding range as defined by the first Breeding Atlas (1968-1972) shows a long-term increase in breeding range of 346% over the 50-year period (Sharrock, 1976). The short-term confirmed breeding range change indicates an increase in confirmed Barn Owl breeding range of 132% over the past ten years. Confirmed breeding was recorded in 25 10km squares during the Bird Atlas (2007-2011) compared to 58 10km squares in 2023 (Map 2 and 3).

Map 4. – Barn Owl Breeding Range in 2007–11

Map 5. – Barn Owl Breeding Range in 2023

Map 3. – Barn Owl Nest sites in 2023

Short-eared Owl

Asio flammeus

Good numbers of birds recorded, with ten in 2019, two in 2020, seven in 2021, ten in 2022, and twenty-five in 2023. One bird was seen in the Ballyhours Mountains on 30 April and 1 May 2021, and was possibly breeding. The remaining birds were seen between 8 August and 5 May. November is when most birds arrive, with relatively few birds overwintering. Ballycotton, Dursley Island, Mizen Head, and Sherkin Island had five records each.

Short-eared Owl – 2004–23

Snowy Owl *Bubo scandiacus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
3	1	0	2

Two records in 2019–23 - extraordinary, as the last record was in 1827!

Female at Bere Island on 5 September 2019. An immature/female bird seen at Cobh on 7 November 2020 and at Aghada on 21–30 November was found dead beside the N25 near Harper's Island on 10 March 2021 - a presumed road casualty.

Hoopoe *Upupa epops*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
-	-	263	44

Forty-four birds recorded in 2019–23 - 2019 (7), 2020 (7), 2021 (14), 2022 (6), 2023 (10). Birds were recorded from thirty-one locations, mostly within a few kilometres of the coast. Cape Clear (5), Mizen Head (3), and Sherkin Island (3) held the most birds - there was no count of more than one bird. Birds were recorded from 25 February to 7 May and 26 July to 14 November, with over half of the birds in April. Numbers have been increasing, and those in 2019–23 were the highest since the 1964–68 period.

Belted Kingfisher *Megaceryle alcyon*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
1	0	0	1

First-year male at Dunboy, Castletownbere from 9 November to 30 December 2020. The fifth Irish record and first county record, and was a welcome opportunity to travel and meet friends with the easing of Covid-19 travel restrictions.

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Top: Snowy Owl *Bubo scandiacus* Common Buzzard *Buteo buteo* Barn Owl *Tyto alba*, October 2021 P. Moore

Bottom: Snowy Owl *Bubo scandiacus*, Black-headed Gull, March 2021, A. Fleming

Belted Kingfisher *Megascops alcyon*, Dunboy November 2020, S.Cronin

Common Kingfisher *Alcedo atthis*

Most records were from coastal areas with lagoons and lakes - birds not in the breeding season. The highest number of records were in September and the lowest in May.

Bee-eater *Merops apiaster*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
27	10	12	5

Five birds recorded in 2019–23, the most in a five-year period since 1959. Previous sightings of multiple birds were two recorded together in 1955, and preceding this was seven birds in 1888. Mizzen Head on 20 April 2019; two birds at Sherkin Island on 9 May 2020; Owenahincha on 6 June 2021; Youghal on 6 June 2020

Eurasian Wryneck *Jynx torquilla*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
266	2	232	32

Thirty-two birds were recorded in 2019–23, with numbers reverting to more typical totals after a peak in 2009–13. All birds were between 12 August and 17 October, apart from one spring record

on 12 April 2022 at Toe head.

Wryneck – 1959–2023

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Ballycotton			1	1	1	3
Ballydehob	1					1
Brow Head			1			1
Cape Clear	1	1	1	1	3	7
Connagh			1			1
Dirk Bay					1	1
Dunowen			1			1
Dursey Island				2	1	3
Galley Head		1	1		1	3
Garinish		1	1			2
Lehanemore, West Beara					1	1
Lissagriffin			1			1
Mizen Head		1	1	2	2	6
Toe Head				1		1
Total	2	4	11	5	10	32

Wryneck – five-year periods – 1959–2023

Great Spotted Woodpecker *Dendrocopos major*

The first record of the species in Cork since 1950 was at Cape Clear on 19–20 April 2008. Details are sparse, but breeding probably took place in Blarney and Doneraile in 2021 and confirmed in later years.

Breeding was confirmed at Gearagh and Ballincollig in 2023, but this probably understates the distribution of the species in the county. There have been few records from southwest Cork so far. A very welcome return as a breeding species.

Birds seen/heard in the following locations: Aherla, Ballincollig, Ballyclough, Bandon, Bantry, Blarney, Bottlehill, Carritowhill, Castlelyons, Cork City, Doneraile, Dunmanway, the Geareagh, Glanmire, Glengarriff and Lough Beg.

Merlin *Falco columbarius*

About 130 records received, with an October peak. One in the Boggeraghs on 7 May 2021 was the only bird in potential breeding habitat. The remaining, mainly coastal records, were between 3 May and 19 August.

Hobby *Falco subbuteo*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
135	5	117	13

Thirteen birds recorded in 2019–23 - totals have reverted to more typical numbers after peaks in 2009–13. All were recorded on single days

Hobby – 2019–23

Knockadoon	22 Sept 2019	1	Galley Head	14 September 2022	1
Mizen Head	23 Sept 2019	1	Mizen Head	11 April 2023	1
Nohoval	16 August 2020	1	Red Strand	2 May 2023	1
Mizen Head	21 October 2020	1	Shanagarry	18 July 2023	1
Sherkin Island	23 July 2021	1	Gearagh	21 July 2023	1
Red Strand	30 April 2022	1	Ballycotton	25 July 2023	1
Ballymacoda	1 May 2022	1			

Common Kestrel *Falco tinnunculus*

Kestrel records from about 230 locations, mainly in coastal, upland areas, and around Cork Harbour. Some notable gaps in mid-west Cork and parts of east Cork.

Map 7. Kestrel - occurrence in completed checklists -eBird and BirdTrack 2015–23

Peregrine Falcon *Falco peregrinus*

Up to date information for Peregrine in Cork was unavailable for the Birds of County Cork (2022) and Tony Nagle has kindly supplied this.

The Peregrine population in County Cork appears to have been stable between 2002-2017 and there are indications of a slight population increase in the years since 2017.

The results of the 2002 National Peregrine Survey (Madden et al. 2009) revealed a breeding population of around sixty pairs for the county. The results of the 2017 National Survey (which remains unpublished) reveal a total of forty-nine breeding pairs of which thirty-four pairs bred successfully, one pair probably bred successfully, eleven pairs failed and the outcome of three pairs is unknown. Single birds were present at thirteen sites where breeding was not suspected. However, results are unknown from an additional nine sites that were either not surveyed or the surveyor did not complete the survey. Six of these sites are used regularly and it is likely that several breeding pairs were missed in the most recent survey. Combining the final result of forty-nine breeding pairs with the nine sites that were either not checked at all or were found to be inactive in March and not checked subsequently gives a similar total (approximately fifty-five+ pairs) which is fairly close to the sixty pairs recorded in 2002. In addition, thirteen sites were recorded as being occupied by single non-breeding birds (in some cases immature first-years) and this non-breeding population is normal as not every bird is able to find a mate or a suitable territory.

In any given year, a substantial number of pairs will not breed successfully. The reasons for failure are varied but poor weather conditions (especially prolonged rainfall) can result in chilling of eggs as well as poor hunting success. Rainfall was well above normal in the first two weeks of June (33-64%) and this may have been a factor. Disturbance can also contribute to failure and the increasing popularity of walking in coastal areas in spring and summer could potentially cause nest failures but it is not known how many sites are affected. Deliberate persecution is another cause of failure but no instances were recorded in 2017 but this of course does not mean that persecution did not occur.

The coastal population appears to be stable and there is little room for population expansion apart from the occasional use of sub-optimal cliff sites. Most suitable quarries are now occupied by Peregrines and therefore buildings (both old and new), provide the main potential for nesting sites in any future population expansion. In the years since 2017, Peregrines bred at five new sites (four castles/ruined buildings, one quarry and one modern building) where breeding had not been recorded previously. On a less positive note, three regular breeding sites in County Cork may be lost in the near future due to infilling at two quarries and the dismantling of an industrial building.

The Peregrine population in Cork appears to have been relatively stable in the 15-year period between the two national surveys and there are indications of ongoing increase. Nevertheless, the considerable gap in years between surveys renders accurate population analysis difficult and only broad generalisations can be given due to the lack of more regular data. Relatively few sites are checked annually and efforts should be made to improve the rate of population monitoring. Regular monitoring of breeding sites would provide useful information on the impacts of increasing numbers of people visiting breeding areas and monitoring would also serve to provide a greater insight on persecution levels.

Thanks to all who participated in the 2017 survey and particular thanks to Alan McCarthy, David Rees and Pat Smiddy for additional help in the preparation of this note.

Peregrine nesting sites in 2017 in County Cork.

Type of Nest Site	Number of Pairs	Type of Nest Site	Number of Pairs
Coastal Cliff	18	Castle	7
River Cliff	3	Church	2
Mountain Crag	1	Other Building	1
Quarry	14		

Red-eyed Vireo *Vireo olivaceus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
45	0	37	8

Eight birds in 2019–23 was an above-average showing.

One Mizen Head, 29 September to 2 October 2019; one Ballinacarraige, 30 September 2019; one Dirk Bay, 30 September 2019; one Lehanamore, 8–9 October 2019; one Cape Clear, 12–24 October

2019; one Lehanamore, 14–29 October 2022; one Mizen Head, 17–21 October 2022 and one

Red-eyed Vireo – five-year periods – 1959–2023

Dursey Island, 28–29 September 2023.

Golden Oriole *Oriolus oriolus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959–2018	2019–2023
135	18	86	4

Female/immature at Ballinacarriga, Garinish, 5 May 2020; female/second-calendar at Barley Cove on 6 May 2020; female/immature at Cape Clear on 8 May 2021; male Blackrock, Cork city on 2 June 2022.

Woodchat Shrike *Lanius senator* (subspecies: *senator*; *badius*)

County Total	pre-1959	1959–2018	2019–2023
56	1	46	9

Good numbers recorded in 2019–23; numbers recorded have increased over the years.

Woodchat Shrike – five-year periods – 1959–2023

Second-calendar male at Cape Clear on 19–23 April 2019; Mizen Head on 27 April 2019; first-calendar bird Cape Clear on 25 August to 13 September 2019; Cape Clear on 7 May 2020; second-calendar female at Crosshaven on 12–13 June 2020; Mizen Head on 10 May 2021; Mizen Head on 10 October 2022; adult female near Ardfield on 7–10 April 2023; Cape Clear on 14–22 April 2023.

Brown Shrike *Lanius cristatus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
1	0	0	1

First-winter bird at Rathduff, Mallow on 7–8 January 2020, was the first county and second Irish record. Unfortunately, the bird did not remain and was seen by few people.

Red-backed Shrike *Lanius collurio* (subspecies: *collurio*)

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
130	3	119	8

Eight in 2019–23 is a bit below recent trend. Cape Clear (62), Mizen Head (19) and Dursey Island (12) are where most birds have occurred.

Red-backed Shrike – five-year periods – 1959-2023

First-calendar year bird at Cape Clear on 7–9 September 2019; First-calendar year bird at Mizen Head on 1 October 2019; first-calendar year bird at Cape Clear on 19–26 September 2020; adult female on 8–10 May 2021; first-calendar year at Mizen Head on 10 September 2021; first-calendar year at Mizen Head on 18 September 2021; Mizen Head on 4 September 2022; Brow Head on 14 October 2022.

Chough *Pyrhcorax pyrrhcorax* (subspecies: *pyrrhcorax*)

A countrywide Chough survey showed that the Cork population appeared to be stable. In 2021, there were 173 confirmed and probable breeding pairs, and Cork accounts for about 44% of breeding pairs in Ireland. More were found in man-made structures in Cork (39%) than elsewhere. Chough nesting boxes have been installed at sties mainly in west Cork, and a colour ringing project has commenced.

Summary of Chough surveys: 1992, 2002 and 2021

Survey year	Confirmed/ Probable Pairs	All birds
1992	153	282
2002	134	257
2021	173	269

Colhoun, K., Rooney, E., Collins, J., Keogh, N.P., Lauder, A., Heardman, C., &

Cummins, S. (2024). The Status and Distribution of Chough in Ireland: Results of the National Survey 2021. Irish Wildlife Manuals, No. 151. National Parks and Wildlife Service, Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage, Ireland.

Chough – peak counts – 2019–23

Dursey Island	40	20 September 2020	Seven Heads	50	10 August 2023
Garrylucas	43	22 November 2020	Mizen Head	52	19 February 2023
Garylucas	43	28 December 2020			

Maximum counts of Choughs on Dursey Island 1978 to 2019, Derek Scott

Year	Maximum counts	Year	Maximum counts
1978	65	2002	50
1979	65	2003	50
1986	12	2004	41
1987	16	2005	45
1988	20	2006	51
1989	30	2007	45
1990	40	2008	40
1991	30	2009	25
1992	50	2010	25
1993	34	2011	50
1994	40	2012	62
1995	45	2013	36
1996	60	2014	30
1997	50	2015	62
1998	78	2016	44
1999	40	2017	30
2000	67	2018	20
2001	65	2019	32

Hooded Crow *Corvus cornix*

Abundant in the county - counts of over 100 birds - 120 at Cuskinny on 15 August 2023; 105 at Bantry on 4 August 2023, and 102 at Muckruss Estuary on 6 July 2022.

Carrion Crow *Corvus corone*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
-	-	276	5

Five birds recorded 2019–23 - Lissagriffin on 20 October 2019; Cork City on 19 November 2019; Ballycotton on 13–14 October 2021; Ringaskiddy on 7 September, and Mizen Head on 4 October 2023. Probably an under-recorded species but also regularly misidentified.

Raven *Corvus corax*

Widespread throughout the county, including a few pairs in Cork City. Peak counts were twenty-nine on the Beara Peninsula on 15 August 2022 and twenty-six in North Cork on 11 August 2019.

Bohemian Waxwing *Bombycilla garrulus*

Four birds were recorded in 2019–23 - all in autumn 2023 - one on Dursey Island on 20 October; one at Kealogue, West Beara on 28 October; two at Dursey on 3 November, one remaining until the following day. The last notable influx was in 2013.

Penduline Tit *Remiz pendulinus*, the Gearagh, January 2023 R.T.Mills

Coal Tit *Periparus ater* (subspecies: *hibernicus*; *ater*)

Highest counts in coastal areas in autumn - 130 at Mizen Head on 29 September 2020, fifty at Cape Clear on 14 October 2023 and thirty-five in Garninish area on 8 October 2020. All birds appeared to be *hibernicus*.

Penduline Tit *Remiz pendulinus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
4	0	0	4

Two birds at Gearagh on 1 January 2023, joined by another the following day, with three remaining until 25 January. Presumed same at Lough Beg on 26–31 March, when trapped and aged/sexed as two adult males and a first-winter male. Adult at Lough Beg on 23–26 December, trapped but sex was indeterminate.

One of the male birds ringed on 28th March was controlled at Donges, Loire-Atlantique, France on the following 15th October 2023.

These were the first Irish records.

Skylark *Alauda arvensis*, Toe Head, 18 April 2023, J Lynch

Skylark *Alauda arvensis*

At Cape Clear, October passage in 2019–23 was generally very light, with 100 on 14 October 2023, the only count of note. Highest counts come from Barry’s Head - 300 on 1 October 2023 and 200 on 20 October 2022. On Galley Head, 100 on 25 October 2023 and 100 at Owenahincha on 1 November 2022. No breeding records of note were received.

Northern Horned Lark*Eremophila alpestris alpestris/pratincola/hoyti*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
1	0	0	1

A bird at Dursey Island on 25 October 2021 was the first Cork and second Irish record (the first was on 3 October 2021 in Galway). The first Cork record of the North American taxa of Shore Lark, known as Northern Horned Lark. There are two previous records of Shore Lark of the European subspecies *Eremophila alpestris flava*.

Sand Martin *Riparia riparia*

	Earliest date	Latest date
2019	4 March	19 October
2020	21 March	17 September
2021	21 February	13 October
2022	18 March	5 November
2023	15 March	29 September

Counts of over 100 birds : 500 Lough Aderra on 19 April 2021; 200 the Gearagh on 20 July and 120 Rostellan on 21 April 2019.

A nest bank was constructed at Harper's Island in 2021, with 24 chambers. In 2022, sixty-seven birds were ringed (28 juvenile) and seventy-nine in 2023 (30 juvenile). <https://birdwatchcork.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/Harpers-Sand-Martin-Breeding-Season-Report-2023.pdf>

Barn Swallow *Hirundo rustica* (subspecies: *rustica*)

	Earliest date	Latest date
2019	15 February	24 November
2020	5 April	2 December
2021	31 March	14 November
2022	29 January	4 December
2023	16 January	29 October

Arrival and departure dates appear to be converging. A bird at Ballianscarthy on 29 December 2021 to 3 January 2022 was excluded from the table.

High counts included - 900 at Barry's Head on 1 October 2023; 300 at Cape Clear on 30 March 2021 and 300 at Harper's Island on 7 September 2023.

Western House Martin *Delichon urbicum*

	Earliest date	Latest date
2019	3 April	5 November
2020	7 April	29 November
2021	11 April	30 November
2022	12 April	6 December
2023	14 February	4 October

Maximum count was sixty-five at the Old Head of Kinsale on 1 September 2023, with many reports of flocks of thirty to sixty birds.

Red-rumped Swallow *Cecropis daurica*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
31	0	27	4

Four birds recorded in 2019–23 - Youghal on 7–10 March 2019; Mizzen Head on 27 March 2019; Knockadoon on 16 June 2019; Cape Clear on 9 April 2020.

American Cliff Swallow *Petrochelidon pyrrhonota*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
1	0	0	1

One at Garnish Point on 21 September 2023 was the first county record, with a mini influx of at least four birds recorded in a few days across Ireland. Unfortunately, a further six records have not been submitted.

Cetti’s Warbler *Cettia cetti*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
3	0	1	2

A presumed male at White’s Marsh on 21 March to 15 May 2022. Second-year bird (adult male in IRBR) at Clogheen Marsh, trapped on 19 February, to 19 June 2023. The second and third county records - the first was at Ballymacoda in May 2001. The bird was regularly heard in song. The species seems a likely candidate to breed and spread in the county in the next few years.

Wood Warbler *Phylloscopus sibilatrix*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
189	2	183	4

Only four records in 2019–23 - Toe Head on 7 October 2019; Cape Clear on 18–21 August 2022; Mizzen Head on 12 September 2022 and Garnish Point on 14 October 2020.

Wood Warbler – 2004–2023

Western Bonelli's Warbler *Phylloscopus bonelli*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
14	0	13	1

A single bird recorded at Three Castles Head on 9 September and presumed same on 20 September 2023.

Bonelli's Warbler sp. *Phylloscopus bonelli/orientalis*

One at Mizen Head on 21–22 September 2023. There have been five previous Bonelli's Warblers, which were not unidentified to species.

Hume's Leaf Warbler *Phylloscopus humei*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
3	0	2	1

One at Cape Clear on 4–7 November 2019, the third county record - the previous records were at Knockadoon in 2004 and Cape Clear in 2016.

Yellow-browed Warbler *Phylloscopus inornatus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
-	0	-	222

In 2019–23 there were 222 birds recorded - with 2019 (41), 2020 (58), 2021 (15), 2022 (79) and 2023 (29). Fairly average numbers, and some Octobers were without the sustained easterly wind flow necessary for the species to reach us in the far west of Europe. Birds were very widely recorded, from about thirty sites - Mizen Head (56), Firkeel/Garinish (51), Cape Clear (47) and Toe Head (13). The best day count was at Cape Clear on 10 October 2022 with ten birds. All birds were between 26 September and 17 December.

Yellow-browed Warbler – 2004–23

Pallas's Leaf Warbler *Phylloscopus proregulus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
19	0	18	1

A single record in 2019–23 at Mizen Head on 28–29 October 2022.

Radde's Warbler *Phylloscopus schwarzi*, Cape Clear, October 2021
J.Lynch

Radde's Warbler *Phylloscopus schwarzi*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
15	0	12	3

Three single birds in 2019–23, including the first September record, all previous records were between 14 October and 1 November. Cape Clear on 9–10 October 2021; Galley Head on 12 September 2022; Cape Clear on 14–23 October 2022.

Dusky Warbler *Phylloscopus fuscatus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
11	0	9	2

Two birds recorded in 2019–23 - typical October records - Cape Clear on 29 October 2022; Lehanamore, west Cork on 29 October 2022.

Willow Warbler *Phylloscopus trochilus* (subspecies: *trochilus*; *acredula*)

	Earliest date	Latest date
2019	13 March	23 October
2020	23 March	21 October
2021	30 March	20 October
2022	25 March	8 October
2023	2 April	30 October

No notable spring counts of Willow or Chiffchaff were received.

Iberian Chiffchaff *Phylloscopus ibericus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
1	0	0	1

The first county record of the species was at Caher East, Mizen Head on 22 September to 2 October 2023. The third Irish record.

Common Chiffchaff *Phylloscopus collybita* (subspecies: *collybita*; *abietinus*; *fulvescens*; *tristis*)

Maximum autumn count - 100 West Beara on 21 October 2020; seventy-five Cape Clear on 21 October 2019; sixty Cape Clear on 18–19 October 2023. Widespread in winter, with a maximum count of ten at Clonakilty on 19 February 2023.

Siberian Chiffchaff *Phylloscopus c. tristis*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
171	0	76	95

The subspecies was widely recorded in 2019–23 in greater numbers (ninety-five birds) than previous periods. Birds were recorded between 5 September and 9 April. Most birds arrived from mid-October with numbers reducing into spring. The high totals at Owenahincha and Clogheen are from regular ringing at the sites.

Siberian Chiffchaff – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Ballinacarriga Lake				2		2
Ballycotton				1		1
Brow Head			1			1
Cape Clear	4	2	2	1		9
Charleville Lagoons			2		1	3
Clogheen Marsh			1	1	6	8
Clogheenmilcon Fen			3	2		5
Cork City		6	7	5		18
Crookhaven			1		1	2
Crosshaven				1		1
Dursey Island	1		1		1	3
Enniskeane		1	1	1		3
Fountainstown			1			1

Ladysbridge		1		1		2
Midleton		1		1		2
Mizen Head		1				1
Owenahincha	7	2	4	9		22
Sherkin Island		1		1	1	3
The Gearagh		1			2	3
Toe Head	1			1		2
West Beara			3			3
Total	13	16	27	27	12	95

Siberian Chiffchaff – 2019–23

Siberian Chiffchaff – five-year periods – 1959–2023

Greenish Warbler

Phylloscopus trochiloides

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
31	0	29	2

Two single birds in 2019–23 - typical early September records: Mizen Head on 13 September 2020; Cape Clear on 5/9/2021.

Two-barred Warbler *Phylloscopus plumbeitarsus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
1	0	0	1

The first Irish record was a bird at Dursey Island on 26 October 2019.

Sedge Warbler *Acrocephalus schoenobaenus*

	Earliest date	Latest date
2019	20 April	14 September
2020	16 April	12 August
2021	14 April	9 September
2022	18 April	25 August
2023	13 April	21 September

Common Reed Warbler *Acrocephalus scirpaceus*

	Earliest date	Latest date
2019	28 April	14 October
2020	7 May	2 October
2021	1 June	9 October
2022	29 April	30 October
2023	25 April	28 October

Breeding noted from Kilkerran, Rostellan, the Gearagh, Blarney, Clogheen Marsh, Ballyvergan, Cuskinny, Long Strand reedbed, Garretstown, Shanagarry, Tramore Valley Park, Meenane (Watergrasshill), Slatty Bridge, Lough Beg, Conna and Rosscarbery. In the CBR 2005 and 2006, the only breeding sites noted were Ballyvergan, Pilmore and Rostellan. Notably, a number of inland records - Conna, Watergrasshill, the Gearagh and Blarney.

Booted Warbler *Iduna caligata*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
3	0	2	1

One at Galley Head on 5 September 2021, the third county record. The previous records were in Ballycotton in 2004 and Firkeel in 2016.

Melodious Warbler *Hippolais polyglotta*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
140	1	134	5

Five single birds were recorded in 2019–23 - all typical autumn records: Cape Clear on 11–14 October 2019; Dursey Island on 18 September 2020; Mizen Head on 31 August 2021; Galley Head on 4 September 2021; Dursey Island on 7 September 2023.

Five birds are low, and the species appeared to have declined since the 1980s and 1990s.

Melodious Warbler – five-year periods – 1959–2023

Icterine Warbler *Hippolais icterina*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
176	0	169	7

Seven individuals in 2019–23 - Cape Clear on 29 August 2019; one at Sheeps Cove, Ring, Clonakilty on 1 September 2020; Dursey Island on 27 August 2021; Cape Clear on 17 September

Icterine Warbler – five-year periods – 1959–2023

2021; Barry’s Head on 19–20 September; Galley Head on 12 September 2022 and presumed same on 18 September; Garnish Point on 21 September 2023.

There has been a steady decline in the species since the 1960s and 1970s.

Common Grasshopper Warbler *Locustella naevia*

	Earliest date	Latest date
2019	19 April	21 June
2020	8 April	28 July
2021	23 April	11 September
2022	23 April	25 July
2023	22 April	24 September

Maximum count was four birds at Gouganebarra on 2 May 2022. About fifty records received.

Garden Warbler *Sylvia borin*

Just thirty-nine birds were recorded in 2019–23, the majority at Cape Clear. Most birds were recorded between 4 September and 30 October, with one April record, two in May, and one in June. No birds were recorded in breeding habitat. Garden Warbler as a migrant at CCBO has declined markedly since the 1970s and 80s (CCBO closed 2013–15 and 2020).

Garden Warbler – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Barry's Head					1	1
Cape Clear	3	1	10	6	2	22
Dursey Island	2		4		1	7
Galley Head		2				2
Knockadoon Head			1			1
Mizen Head		2	2			4
Old Head of Kinsale			1			1
Roche's Point		1				1
Total	5	6	18	6	4	39

Garden Warbler – bird-days per year –1959–23

Barred Warbler *Curruca nisoria*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
131	0	123	8

Eight recorded in 2019–23, a decline from recent years. A typical range of dates and west Cork locations.

One Mizen Head, 8 October 2020; one Mizen Head, 30 September 2021; one Cape Clear, 17 October 2021; one Garinish, 17 October 2021; one Dursey Island, 18 October 2021; one Firkeel, 22 October 2022; one Ardfield, 1–5 November 2022 and one Mizen Head, 21–22 October 2023.

Barred Warbler -1959-2023 – five-year periods

Common Whitethroat *Curruca communis* (subspecies: *communis*)

	Earliest date	Latest date
2019	22 April	28 September
2020	19 April	12 September
2021	24 April	15 September
2022	21 March	10 October
2023	22 April	2 October

Peak counts of ten at Ballycotton cliffs on 17 June 2020 and 13 May 2023. At Cape Clear in 2023, regular counts of ten to twenty birds in June, July, and August, with sixty on 21 June.

Lesser Whitethroat *Curruca curruca* (subspecies: *curruca*)

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
423	0	347	76

Seventy-six birds recorded in 2019–23, about the average number of birds, though the species has increased markedly over the years. With twenty-five in 2022, the only year with more records was 2005 (29 birds). As usual, most birds were recorded at Cape Clear, Mizen Head, and Firkeel/Garnish. Most birds were seen between 8 August and 31 October, with one in April and six in May. Two birds were found in song in breeding locations, though with no further evidence of breeding - Balliadee on 10 May 2019 and Lower Kileens Road, near Cork City, on 31 May to 1 June 2020.

Lesser Whitethroat – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Ballinadee	1					1
Barry's Head	1			1	1	2
Cape Clear	3	3	7	11	3	27
Coolemaine Head	1					1
Dursey Island	1	1	3			5

Firkeel	1	4		3	3	11
Galley Head	2			2		4
Knockadoon Head					1	1
Mine Head	1					1
Mizen Head	5	1		8	2	16
Squince Harbour				1		1
Toe Head	1	1	1		1	4
Union Hall					1	1
Total	17	10	12	25	12	76

Lesser Whitethroat *Curruca curruca*, Toe Head, 9 September 2023, J. Lynch

Sardinian Warbler *Curruca melanocephala*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
4	0	3	1

An unaged male at Knockadoon Head on 21–23 April 2021. The fourth Cork record - all Irish records are from Cork and in the month of April. This is the second for Knockadoon - 14–21 April 1993.

Western Subalpine Warbler*Curruca iberiae* (subspecies: *iberiae* or *inornata*)

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
27	0	24	3

Three birds recorded - Second-calendar male at Cape Clear on 25 April 2019; One at Mizen Head on 4 October 2020; Male, Ballynacarriga, near Dunmanway, on 19 April 2023.

Dartford Warbler *Curruca undata* (subspecies: *dartfordiensis*)

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
8	0	7	1

A first-calendar male at Cape Clear on 21 October 2022, the first since a bird at Brow Head in March 2003.

Firecrest *Regulus ignicapilla*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
822	1	758	73

Average numbers recorded, seventy-three in 2019–23, with just one in 2020 when CCBO was closed. As usual, most birds were recorded by Cape Clear, followed by Mizen Head and Firkeel. Peak counts were twelve at Cape Clear on 10 October 2022 and seven at Mizen Head on 12 October 2022. Birds were recorded between 29 September and 31 October, with singles in February, March, April, and December.

Firecrest – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Cape Clear	9		1	15	5	30
Castlemartyr					1	1
Dursey Island			1	2		3
Firkeel	1		2	8	1	12
Galley Head	2					2
Lehanemore	1			2		1
Mizen Head	6			10		16
Owenahincha	1					1
Sherkin Island		1				1
The Geragh					1	1
Toe Head	1					1

Youghal					2	2
Total	21	1	4	37	10	73

Firecrest *Regulus ignicapilla*, The Gearagh Ballycotton January 2023, R.T.Mills

Common Starling *Sturnus vulgaris* (subspecies: *vulgaris*)

Maximum counts - 560 Ballybranagan on 10 September 2023; 500 at Knockadoon on 20 November 2023.

Rosy Starling *Pastor roseus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
64	0	46	18

Eighteen birds were recorded in 2019–23. Numbers have been increasing over the decades, mainly juvenile birds in the autumn. Fourteen adults in the period was exceptional.

Ballinahina, N of Cork City, 29 May 2020, adult; Owenahincha, 8 June 2020, adult; Ballycotton, 29 June to 12 July 2020, adult; Youghal, 6 July 2020, adult; Mizen Head, 2 June 2021, adult; Ballincollig, 5 June 2021, adult; Dursey Island, 5 June 2021, adult; Cape Clear, 11 June, adult; 2

Rosy Starling *Pastor roseus*, Common Starling *Sturnus vulgaris* Ballycotton July 2020, R.T.Mills

adults, Castletownbere, 11 June 2021, Garnish, 15 June 2021, adult; Schull, 18 June 2021, adult; Galley Head, 20 –21 July 2021, adult; Dursey Island, 31/7/2021, adult; Roches’s Point, 12 August to 25 September 2022, juvenile; Galley Head, 10 September 2023, juvenile; Cape Clear, 29 September to 12 October 2023 and Garretstown, 13 October 2023, Juvenile.

Rosy Starling – five-year periods – 1959–2023

Swainson’s Thrush *Catharus ustulatus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
7	0	6	1

One at Scott’s Garden, Dursey Island on 1 October 2020.

Hermit Thrush *Catharus guttatus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
3	0	2	1

One at Mizen Head on 3 November 2020, the third county record, the most recent being at Cape Clear in 2006.

Redwing *Turdus iliacus* | (subspecies: *iliacus*; *coburni*)

Maximum counts were - 3,000 moving west from Owenahincha on 17 November 2022; 900 in one field north Cork on 5 December 2021; regular counts of 200 to 500 per night with passive acoustic monitoring at Upper Rathduff, in early November 2020 to 2023.

Fieldfare *Turdus pilaris*

At Mizen Head on 20 October 2022, a flock of 2,000 was seen moving through, with a further 2,000 on 23 October. In north Cork, 1,200 birds were in one field on 8 November 2020. Near Skibbereen, 600 were moving on 29 November 2022, with a further 200 moving south out to sea near Lough Hyne.

Ring Ouzel – 2019–2023

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Ballycotton		1				1
Cape Clear	2			5	7	14
Carrigaline	1					1
Dunmanway			1			1
Dursey Island		1		1	9	11
Galley Head	2			1	2	5
Long Strand		1				1
Mizen Head	2	20		12		34
Sheep's Cove		1				1
Sherkin Island		1		2	1	4
Toe Head				1		1
West Beara		3			1	2
Total	7	30	1	18	20	79

Ring Ouzel *Turdus torquatus* (a subspecies: *torquatus*)

Seventy-nine birds recorded in 2019–23, with a small increase in recent years. Birds were recorded between 21 March and 28 April and 29 September and 11 November, with most birds in October. Nine at Mizen Head on 21 April 2020 was a high spring count, and the autumn peak of twelve birds was also at Mizen Head on 20 October 2022.

There were no birds recorded on previous breeding sites.

Ring Ouzel – 2004–2023

American Robin *Turdus migratorius*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
2	0	1	1

One at Dursey Island on 13 November 2023 is the second county record - the first was at Glengarriff on 16 January 1977.

Spotted Flycatcher *Muscicapa striata* (subspecies: *striata*)

	Earliest date	Latest date
2019	7 May	20 October
2020	7 May	6 September
2021	26 April	20 October
2022	24 May	30 October
2023	9 May	19 October

Birds recorded in breeding season at - UCC, Inishbeg (River Ilen), the Geragh, Glengarriff, Myross, Blarney Castle, Rathbarry, Gouganebarra, Reenascreena, Middleton, Kealfadda, Conna, Brookhill, Power Head, Ardnahinch, Drinagh, Lough Beg, Milleenanhillan, Ballyhilty Bridge, Mealagh Wood, Clogheenmilcon, Lough Aderra, Ballyvourney, Ladysbridge, Ballybrack Woods, Skibbereen, Doneraile Park, Lis Art Estate, Burnfort, Kilcatherine, Garnish Island, Currabinny, Knockgriffin, Cloyne and Croagh Bay.

106 bird-days on Cape Clear in September 2023, with a peak of thirty-one birds on 9 September.

Common Nightingale *Luscinia megarhynchos*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
15	0	13	2

Two records in 2019–23 - Mizen Head on 20 September 2023; Garnish Point on 29 September 2023.

Bluethroat *Luscinia svecica* (subspecies: *svecica*)

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
24	0	22	2

Dursey Island on 26 September 2020 and an unaged female west of the Gearagh on 21 October 2020.

Red-breasted Flycatcher *Ficedula parva*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
369	0	347	22

Twenty-two birds were recorded in 2019–23 - about average numbers, though perhaps showing a decline since the 2000s/2010s. All were autumn records, between 29 September and 27 October. All were single records apart from two at Cape Clear on 9 October 2021.

Red-breasted Flycatcher – 2004–2023

Red-breasted Flycatcher – 2019–2023

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Ballycotton		1				1
Cape Clear			5	1	3	9
Dursey Island			2		2	4
Firkeel	1		1		1	3
Galley Head				1		1
Mizen Head	1	1				2

Three Castles Head	1					1
Toe Head					1	1
Total	3	2	8	2	7	22

Pied Flycatcher *Ficedula hypoleuca*

In 2019–23, 147 birds were recorded, with quite low numbers in those years apart from 2023. Generally, there were one or two birds recorded, but ten at Cape Clear on 7 September 2023 was the peak. Birds were recorded between 21 March to 15 May and 18 August to 27 October. There were ten spring records, with most occurring in September.

Pied Flycatcher – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Ardfield					3	3
Cape Clear	15	3	12	8	34	72
Clonakilty		1	1		1	3
Courtmacsherry					1	1
Crookhaven				1	3	4
Dursey		3			5	8
Firkeel					6	6
Galley Head	1		3		7	11
Knockadoon Head	2				1	3
Lehanmore		1				1
Lough Cluhir					1	1
Mizen Head	1	3	3	2	12	21
Old Head of Kinsale	1	1			1	4
Rath					1	1
Roche's Point		1				1
Toe Head			4	1	2	7
Grand Total	20	13	23	13	78	147

Pied Flycatcher – 2004–23

Black Redstart *Phoenicurus ochruros*

Birds were widely recorded, mainly along the coast of the county, at about forty-five sites, with 154 birds recorded. There were single records on 19 April, 28 May, and 17 September, with the remainder between mid-October and the regular spring peak in March. Maximum count was nine at Cape Clear on 18 October 2022. Returning birds probably occur at regular winter sites such as Cobh and Kennedy Quay, Cork City.

Black Redstart – 2019–23

Common Redstart *Phoenicurus phoenicurus*

Forty birds were recorded in 2019–23, about average for this migrant. There were two spring records - at Galley Head on 6 May 2019 and 26 April 2021 at Mizen Head. The remaining records were between 4 September and 26 October, mainly in October.

Common Redstart – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Ballinascarthy		1				1
Ballycotton					1	1
Cape Clear	3	2	5	3	2	15
Crookhaven	1					1
Dursey Island	2	1		1	3	7
Galley Head	1			2		3
Garinish		1			1	2
Kinsale				1		1
Knockadoon Head			1			1
Mizen Head			2	2	2	6
Sherkin Island		1				1
Toe Head					1	1
Total	7	6	8	9	10	40

Whinchat *Saxicola rubetra*

Sixty-four birds were recorded in 2019–23, with numbers still appearing to be declining. Bird-days peaked in the 1960s–80s at CCBO and declined since. There was a single spring record, one at Cape Clear on 14 May 2022. The remainder of records were between 22 August and 3 November. There were no breeding season records.

Whinchat – 2004–23

Whinchat – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Barry's Head			3		1	4
Cape Clear	12	1	5	6	6	30
Crosshaven			1			1
Dursey Island	1		3			4
Galley Head			3	1	2	6
Knockadoon Head			4			4
Midleton				1		1
Mizen Head	2	2	3	4		11
Old Head of Kinsale			1	1		2
Toe Head			1			1
Total	15	3	24	14	9	64

Whinchat - CCBO - bird-days - 1959-2023

Northern Wheatear *Oenanthe oenanthe* (subspecies: *oenanthe*; *leucorhoa*)

Highest count was twenty-five birds at Ballycotton on 13 September 2022. Most records received were of migrants, with little data on breeding. Breeding was noted at Barleycove, Dursey, Ballyhours, Allihies, Bere Island, Blackball Head, Cape Clear, Healy Pass, Hungry Hill, Sheep's Head, Mushera, Mizen Head, and Three Castles Head.

	Earliest date	Latest date
2019	25 March	23 October
2020	24 March	23 October
2021	28 February	24 October
2022	11 March	21 October
2023	17 March	22 October

Winter record - 19 January 2020 Mizen Head

Isabelline Wheatear *Oenanthe isabellina*, Toe Head November 2022, S.Cronin

Isabelline Wheatear *Oenanthe isabellina*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
2	0	1	1

One at Toe Head on 24 October to 21 November 2022. The second county record after one at Mizen Mountain from 10–17 October 1992.

Tree Sparrow *Passer montanus*

Now rare in the county, with three records of five birds - Nohoval on 12 May 2021, three at Galley Head on 15 May 2022, and one near the Old Head of Kinsale on 24 May 2022. May is generally the month when the species is most likely to occur in Cork.

House Sparrow *Passer domesticus*

Widely reported throughout much of the county, with counts of more than thirty birds from - Baltimore (62); Lough Beg (50); Cape Clear (48); Roche’s Point (44); Ballycotton beach (40); Inch Strand (30); Barry’s Head (30); Carrigtwohill (30), Sarsfield Road (30); Belgooly (30); Kill An Oir (Fermoy, 30).

Western Yellow Wagtail *Motacilla flava* (subspecies: *flavissima*; *flava*; *thunbergi*)

Forty-two birds were recorded in 2019–23, which appears to show the continued gradual decline of the species as a migrant in Cork. A number of records, however, have not been submitted. There were just two in April and two in May, with most in September. Birds were recorded between 20 April to 20 May and 12 August to 24 October. Eight birds on Cape Clear on 20 October 2021 were the only notable influx.

Western Yellow Wagtail – 2004–23

Western Yellow Wagtail – CCBO bird-days – 1959-2023

Western Yellow Wagtail – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Ballycotton			1			1
Cape Clear	1	1	14	6	1	23
Dursey Island			1			1
Galley Head			1	1	2	4
Garretstown			1			1
Harperr's island			1			1
Lissagriffin				1	1	2
Mizen Head			1	1	1	3
Owenahincha	1			1		2
Pilmore					2	2
Union Hall					1	1
West Beara		1				1
Total	2	2	20	10	8	42

Blue Headed Wagtail *Motacilla flava flava*
 Unaged male at Mizen Head on 20 May 2022.

Citrine Wagtail *Motacilla citreola*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
10	0	9	1

First-winter at Cape Clear on 6–12 September 2022, the first record for the island.

Grey Wagtail *Motacilla cinerea*

No count of more than three birds was received.

Pied Wagtail *Motacilla alba* (subspecies: *yarrellii*; *alba*)

Peak counts, 100 birds of mixed *alba* and *yarrellii* at the Old head of Kinsale on 16 September 2020 and Ballycotton on 3 September 2023. No information was received in relation to roosts in Cork city.

Richard's Pipit *Anthus richardi*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
81	0	80	1

One at Ballydonegan, West Beara on 20 October 2022, one record in 2019–23 represents a sharp decline over recent years.

Richard's Pipit – 2019–23

Meadow Pipit *Anthus pratensis*

At Cape Clear, peak passage is in October - 2019 - 1,976 bird-days, peak 251 on 11 October; 2022 - 2,458 bird-days in October, peak of 350 on 9 October; 2023 - 2,432 bird-days in October, peak 501 on 2 October. Elsewhere, 300 at Barry's Head on 1 October 2023 was the only count of over 100 birds.

Tree Pipit *Anthus trivialis*

Twenty-eight birds were recorded in 2019–23 - typical small numbers, almost all coastal. Notably, one NoeMig record inland at Rathduff. Numbers peaked in the 1970s/80s and have appeared to decline since at CCBO. Birds were recorded between 7 April to 10 May and 21 August to 22 October, with most records in September.

Tree Pipit – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Ballinhassig	1					1
Ballycotton					1	1
Cape Clear	2		4	2	4	12
Clonakilty					1	1
Coolmaine Head	1					1
Dursey Island			1			1
Ennishkeane		1				1

Galley Head		1	0	1		2
Mizen Head					2	2
Owenahincha				1		1
Sherkin Island					1	1
Strawtown			1			1
Three Castle Head					1	1
Upper Rathduff, (nocturnal flight calls)				1		1
Total	4	2	6	5	10	27

Tree Pipit - CCBO bird days - 1959-2023

Tree Pipit – 2004–23

Red-throated Pipit *Anthus cervinus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
35	0	34	1

One record in 2019–23 - Mizen Head on 18 November 2021.

Water Pipit *Anthus spinoletta* (subspecies: *spinoletta*)

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
32	0	28	4

Four single records in 2019–23 - one at Pilmore on 7 November 2019; Ballycotton on 4 February 2022; Old Head of Kinsale on 10 March 2022 and Pilmore on 11 March 2023

Rock Pipit *Anthus petrosus* (subspecies: *petrosus*; *littoralis*)

Common on coastal beaches and salt marshes. High counts - fifty Lissagriffin on 7 October 2023; forty-six Ballinglanna 3–6 February 2019.

Birds of the Scandinavian race, *littoralis*, were recorded as follows: one on the Gearagh on 25 March 2019, a first inland record; one on Eyries on 27 February 2020 and 14 March 2023; two at Ballycotton on 10 April 2022; one at Pilmore on 11 March 2023; two at Sherkin Island on 26 February 2023, with one until 22 April 2023. There are records of twenty-five previous individuals.

A newly fledged Rock Pipit was seen at Camden Quay a number of years ago, and an adult was singing on Lavitt's Quay on 29 May 2023 (Sam Bayley).

Chaffinch *Fringilla coelebs* (subspecies: *gengleri*; *coelebs*)

At Cape Clear, passage was light apart from October 2019 with 2,865 bird-days, with 300 to 500 birds per day from 19–23 October. Over 100 birds passing Mizen Head on 12 October 2020 was the only other count of more than 100 birds.

Brambling *Fringilla montifringilla*

Almost all of the 126 birds in 2019–23 were spring and autumn migrants, with two in December and five in January. Most were single birds apart from a small influx in March 2022, with nineteen at Galley Head, twelve at Cape Clear, and seven at Sherkin Island. Totals - 2019 (26), 2020 (5), 2021 (20), 2022 (61), and 2023 (15)

Brambling – 2019–23

Hawfinch *Coccothraustes coccothraustes*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
97	11 (at least)	84	2

Just two records - Monkstown on 8 June 2020 and Dursey Island on 18 October 2021. Hawfinches have become more common but are erratic in their occurrence.

Hawfinch –1959–2023

Bullfinch *Pyrrhula pyrrhula*

The highest count was of eight at Rocky Bay on 3 December 2021. The only evidence of movement was small numbers at Cape Clear in autumn, one on 19–20 October and 7–8 November 2019; two on 9 October 2022; one on 23–24 October 2023 and one on 29 October 2023.

Common Rosefinch *Carpodacus erythrinus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
161	0	143	18

Typical spread of records in 2019–23. Autumn records were between 7 September and 25 October. There was a June record in 2021 and two in 2022. All records were of single birds.

Common Rosefinch – 1959–2023

Common Rosefinch – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Ballycotton					1	1
Cape Clear	2			1		5
Dursey Island	1			3		4

Firkeel		1				1
Knockadoon Head				1	1	2
Mizen Head			2			2
Old Head of Kinsale			1			1
Owenahincha			1			1
Toe Head					1	1
Total	3	1	8	2	4	18

European Greenfinch *Chloris chloris*

Cape Clear consistently had the highest numbers with counts of forty to sixty-five in July and August 2023, though lower in other years. Up to sixteen birds at Sherkin Island in December 2023; twenty at Barry's Head on 1 October 2023; fourteen at Harper's Island on 22 March 2019 and twelve at Rochestown on 29 January 2022.

Linnet *Carduelis cannabina* (subspecies: *cannabina*)

Counts of 150 birds or over - Cape Clear, 200 on 10 September 2022; 250 on 20 September 2022 and up to 160 on 8–13 October 2022; 140 to 180 birds on 8–11 September 2023. 200 at Knockadoon on 24 August 2023 and 505 at Ballybranagan on 16 January 2022.

Redpoll *Carduelis flammea*

Counts of twenty or more birds - Cape Clear, up to sixty birds on 12–18 October 2023; twenty at Rossmore on 9 February 2019; twenty at Tramore Valley Park on 13 January 2021; twenty at Lough Beg on 25 January 2019.

Red Crossbill *Loxia curvirostra*

Seventy-six birds recorded - ten or more birds - Twelve at Cleanrath on 11 January 2019; ten at Inchigeelagh on 25 April 2023; ten at Three Castles Head on 8 October; ten at Bottle Hill on 8 June 2020.

European Goldfinch *Carduelis carduelis*

Counts of over 100 birds - Cape Clear - 112 on 11 October 2019; 100 on 19 and 22 October and 200 on October 2022; 101 on 18 October 2023; Sherkin Island - 200 on 6–13 September 2023; Ballybranagan 200 on 18 September 2022.

Siskin *Spinus spinus*

Most counts are of less than ten birds.

Cape Clear - October 2022, 725 bird-days and peak 201 on 19 October; October 2023, 955 bird-days and peak 201 on 18 October. Lough Beg - forty regularly in January 2019 and November and December 2020. Munster Technological University - thirty on 24 February 2022.

Lapland Bunting *Calcarius lapponicus*

Twenty-four birds were recorded in 2019–23, a bit below average. There have been no significant influxes since 2010. Most birds were recorded between 20 September and 25 October, with single records in November and February and two in December.

Lapland Bunting – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Ballycotton					1	1
Brow Head						1
Cape Clear			1			1
Dunowen Head						2
Dursey Island	2		1	2		8
Galley Head	2		1	1		4
Lissagriffin			1			1
Mizen Head			1		1	3
Power Head					1	1
Ring			1			1
The Gearagh						1
Total	4	6	3	3	8	24

Lapland Bunting – 2004–23

Snow Bunting *Plectrophenax nivalis*

Typical low numbers recorded - thirty-six birds, Dursey Island as in most years, accounted for most birds. Birds were recorded between 23 September and 2 January, with twenty-three birds in October. Four on Dursey on 11 October 2019 was the maximum count.

Snow Bunting – 2019–23

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
Ballinwilling	2					2
Ballycotton	1		1			2
Beara Peninsula					1	1
Cape Clear	1		1	3		5
Clonakilty				1		1
Dursey Island	7		6	2	1	16
Galley Head			1			1
Knockadoon Head		2				2
Mizen Head		1		1	1	3
Sherkin Island				1		1
Toe Head				1		1
Youghal			1			1
Total	11	3	10	9	3	36

Yellowhammer *Emberiza citrinella*

The majority of records came from coastal areas from Barry's Head to Ballycotton and inland towards Midleton.

Cloyne: Eighty on 9 January 2022 (not mapped)
 Barry's Head: Counts of fifty birds in September and October 2022 and 2023
 Ringfinnan: Eighteen on 25 January 2023
 Inch: Sixteen on 2 August 2019

A recent study (Finch *et al.* 2022) of breeding densities of Yellowhammer in east Cork found a breeding density of 4.67 pairs per km square, with a population estimate of 215-289 pairs in the study area. The density was high compared to other Irish surveys though lower than recorded in the UK. The importance of tillage to the species was highlighted in the study.

Map 8. Yellowhammer - occurrence in completed checklists -eBird and BirdTrack 2015–23

Yellowhammer *Emberiza citrinella*, Power Head, 29 July 2023, J. Lynch

Ortolan Bunting *Emberiza hortulana*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
99	0	93	6

Six recorded in 2019–23, about an average haul. There has been a moderate decline since 1959–63 and perhaps masked by an increase in coverage in sites such as Dursey Island and Mizen Head. The first June record was one at Dursey Island on 6 June 2021.

One Mizen Head, 2 September 2019; one Galley Head, 17 September 2019; Mizen Head, 22 September 2019; one Dursey Island, 6 June 2021; one Mizen Head, 21–31 August 2021 and one Galley Head, 8–9 September 2021.

Ortolan Bunting - five-year periods - 1959-2023

Little Bunting *Emberiza pusilla*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
42	0	35	7

Seven records in 2019–23 is the second highest in five-year periods since 1959. There is a single prior April record - the first March records are of one at Long Strand on 2 March 2019, with one at Galley Head on 24 March and two together 25–26 March 2019 (one presumed same). One Galley Head, 15 October 2020; one Dursey, 6 October 2021; one Dursey, 9 October 2021; one Dursey, 8 October 2023 and one Cape Clear on 22 October 2022.

Rustic Bunting *Emberiza rustica*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
20	0	19	1

One at Cape Clear on 21–22 October 2022 was the 12th record for the island.

Reed Bunting *Emberiza schoeniclus*

Generally small numbers recorded but the highest were in coastal counts in arable areas.

Barry's Head	Fifty on 7 September 2023 and 1 October 2023.
Galley Head	Fifty on 30 January 2023
Skibbereen	Thirty on 31 January 2022

Bobolink *Dolichonyx oryzivorus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
2	0	1	1

One at Garinish on 1 October 2022 was the second county record.

Baltimore Oriole *Icterus galbula*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
4	0	2	2

A first calendar-year bird at Lehanemore, Beara on 11 October 2019 and a first-winter bird at Dursey Island on 29 September, were the third and fourth county records.

Black-and-white Warbler *Mniotilta varia*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
2	0	1	1

A first calendar male at Firkin Glen on 10 October 2023 was the second county record, after the first at Cape Clear on 18 October 1978.

Rose-breasted Grosbeak *Pheucticus ludovicianus*, Cape Clear, October 2021, J. Lynch

Blackpoll Warbler *Setophaga striata*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
7	0	5	2

First calendar-year birds at Three Castles Head on 8–11 October 2020 and Galley Head 10–11 October 2021, were the sixth and seventh county record, and first for the site. All records have been between 6 and 24 October.

Rose-breasted Grosbeak *Pheucticus ludovicianus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
9	0	7	2

Two records - first calendar-year male, Cape Clear on 7–9 October 2021 and first-winter male near Shepperton Lake, Skibbereen, 5 November 2023. All records have been between 29 September and 5 November, in west Cork.

Appendix 1: Category D1 records

Species that would otherwise appear in Categories A or B, except there is a reasonable doubt that they have ever occurred in a natural state.

Snow Goose *Anser caerulescens*

Adult white morph, Coolmaine, 10th September 2021.

Egyptian Goose *Alopochen aegyptiaca*

One (unaged), The Gearagh, 31st August to 23rd October 2021; One, Reen Pier, 21st October 2021.

Ruddy Shelduck *Tadorna ferruginea*

Two, Shanagarry, 10th June 2020.

Appendix 2: Category E records

Lesser Grey Shrike *Lanius minor*

First calendar year, Galley Head, 8–14 September 2021. This was a captive-reared bird released as part of a conservation scheme in Catalunya, Spain.

References

Burke, B., Fitzgerald, N., Kelly, S. and Lewis, L.J. (2020) *Greylag and Pink-footed geese in Ireland 2017/18–2019/20*. Irish Wetland Bird Survey (I-WeBS) Report. BirdWatch Ireland, Wicklow.

Burke, B., Kennedy, J., Gadd, R., Fitzgerald, N., Lynch, A., Caffrey, B., Walsh, A., Murray, T. and Kelly, S.B.A. (2025) *The status and distribution of wintering waterbirds in Ireland in 2023: results from the Irish Wetland Bird Survey (I-WeBS)*. Irish Wildlife Manuals, No. 162. National Parks and Wildlife Service, Ireland.

Burke, B., McElwaine, J.G., Fitzgerald, N., Kelly, S.B.A., McCulloch, N., Walsh, A.J. and Lewis, L.J. (2021) *Population size, breeding success and habitat use of Whooper Swan *Cygnus cygnus* and Bewick's Swan *Cygnus columbianus bewickii* in Ireland: results of the 2020 International Swan Census*. BirdWatch Ireland, Kilcoole, Co. Wicklow.

Finch, D., Moore, P. and Lusby, J. (Year unknown) *Breeding densities and habitat associations of Yellowhammer *Emberiza citrinella* in their core range in an arable landscape in east Cork*. *Irish Birds*, 44, pp. 45–54.

McCarthy, A., Ó Teangana, D., Nagle, T., Bayley, S., Heardman, C., Rees, D., Deasy, C., Riordan, N., McDonnell, B. and Lusby, J. (2023) *Barn Owl population status and trends in County Cork*. BirdWatch Ireland.

Madden, B., Hunt, J. and Norriss, D. (2002) *The 2002 survey of the Peregrine *Falco peregrinus* breeding population in the Republic of Ireland*. *Irish Birds*, 8, pp. 543–548.

O'Neill, J., Holloway, P., Darby, J., Hoodless, A. and Quinn (2020) *Modelling the national breeding distribution and population size of an elusive forest bird, the Eurasian Woodcock (*Scolopax rusticola*)*. *Ibis*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/ibi.70040>

Ruddock, M., Wilson-Parr, R., Lusby, J., Connolly, F., Bailey, J. and O'Toole, L. (2024) *The 2022 National Survey of breeding Hen Harrier in Ireland*. Irish Wildlife Manuals, No. 147. National Parks and Wildlife Service, Ireland.

Smiddy P., Shorten M and Heselden R. (2022) *The Birds of County Cork*, CUP.

Pink-footed Goose, Barnacle Goose, Russian Greater White-fronted Goose and Greylag Goose, Toons Valley, Jan 2021 J.Lynch
Cork Bird Report 2019–23

Urban Breeding Gulls in Cork City

Mark Shorten, 106 Sundays Well Road, Cork. Mshorten@gmail.com

In 2021, a National Urban Gull Survey was commissioned by the National Parks and Wildlife Service (Keogh, N. T. & Lauder, A. W. 2021), during which:

1. Primary data was collected using a stratified random sample of 1km squares across the range of urban habitats in order to inform national-level population modelling to be carried out by JNCC at a later date as part of the Seabirds Count analysis and final publication.
2. Additional data was collected for specially selected towns in order to derive population estimates of nesting gulls for those areas.

Herring Gull *Larus argentatus* – Cork City centre, 3 June 2023, Mark Shorten

However, in Cork City, the stratified random sample of squares did not include the urban core, while some suburban sites were covered. As a result, no breeding gulls were recorded in the Cork urban area. Breeding of gulls in Cork City had been suspected, but as of 2021, there was no proof. In spring 2023, I went to the roofs of several buildings in the centre of the city, mainly multi-storey car parks, and found that both Herring Gulls *Larus argentatus* and Lesser-black-backed Gulls *Larus fuscus* were holding territory or nest building. I revisited and extended the survey in June and July 2023.

Methods

Birds were observed from the Apple Building, City Hall car park, Copley Street car park, Elisabeth Fort, Grand Parade car park, Merchants Quay car park, and North Main Street. Apparently occupied nests, chicks, territorial behaviour, and nest site type were counted. The names of the buildings

where the birds appeared to be nesting were collected along with approximate lat./long coordinates. Additional nests were found by Sean Ronane (SR) and Cork City Council staff (CHS).

Results

This brief survey found that gulls do breed in Cork City and that there were at a minimum twenty

Herring Gull chicks *Larus argentatus*– Cork City centre, 1 July 2023, Mark Shorten

confirmed or probable breeding Herring Gulls and a minimum of fourteen confirmed or probable breeding Lesser-black-backed Gulls. This is a minimum figure as many buildings could not be checked due to poor vantage points. Some areas such as the north quays— Sullivan’s Quay, St. Patrick’s Quay, and Kennedy Quay— appeared to hold birds, but breeding status could not be confirmed. Most birds were nesting on flat roofs (26), followed by chimney pots (6), church domes (1), and what might be described as a cliff site in a machine area (1).

Discussion

There has been significant media discussion about gull and human interaction in Dublin and other cities in Europe. Urban gull breeding in Cork is possibly a recent phenomenon, and so far, there have been no significant negative reports of gull and human interactions in Cork. In Cork, gulls are not typically found scavenging on the streets— black plastic bags containing food waste are generally not left on the streets, and gulls have reduced opportunities to create waste. This is beyond the scope of this note, but perhaps the feeding on the River Lee and surrounding areas is sufficient to maintain the possibly growing population.

Conclusions

In all likelihood, this is a growing population, and the chances of human and gull interactions will probably increase. The local authority, Cork City Council, is aware of the gull population, and the details of this survey have been supplied to them. Regular surveys should be carried out on a regular basis.

Keogh, N. T. & Lauder, A. W. (2021) *National Urban Gull Survey 2021: Technical Report*. National Parks & Wildlife Service of the Department of Housing, Local Government & Heritage.

Gulls breeding in Cork City in 2023

	Herring Gull (HG)	Lesser-black Backed Gull (LB)
AON	13	7
Nest with chicks	4	3
Territorial Behaviour/nest building	3	4

Species		last date of Observation	Status	Site Type	Observer
HG	Castle Street	1/7/2023	3 chicks	Chimney pot	MS
HG	North Main Street	1/7/2023	1 chick min	Chimney pot	MS
HG	St Francis Church	1/7/2023	uncertain, pair still there	Church dome	MS
HG	Paul Steet	3/6/2023	AON	Chimney pot	MS
HG	South Mall	3/6/2023	AON, deserted on 1.7.23 ??	Flat Roof	MS
HG	South Mall	15/4/2023	nest building	Flat roof	MS
HG	Father Mathew Quay	19/6/2023	AON	Chimney Pot	MS
HG	McCurtain St	3/6/2023	AON	Chimney Pot	MS
HG	BT Building	3/6/2023	2 chicks	Flat Roof	MS
HG	BT Building	3/6/2023	AON	cliff'	MS
HG	BT Building	3/6/2023	AON	Flat Roof	MS
HG	Maylor st	3/6/2023	AON	Flat Roof	MS
HG	Debenhams	3/6/2023	AON	Flat Roof	MS
HG	Debenhams	3/6/2023	AON	Flat Roof	MS
HG	Apple Building	15/6/2023	chick	Flat Roof	SR
HG	City Hall	15/6/2023	Territorial adult	Flat Roof	MS

HG	Brooks Haughton	15/6/2023	AON	Flat Roof	MS
HG	South Mall	13/6/2023	AON	Flat Roof	MS
HG	South Mall	19/6/2023	AON	Flat roof	MS
HG	South Mall	19/6/2023	AON	Flat Roof	MS
LB	South Mall	3/6/2023	AON	Flat Roof	MS
LB	McCurtain St	1/7/2023	2 chicks	Chimney Pot	MS
LB	Merchants Quay C P	3/6/2023	territorial adult diving	Flat Roof	MS
LB	Merchants Quay C P	1/7/2023	territorial adult diving	Flat Roof	MS
LB	Merchants Quay C P	1/7/2023	territorial adult diving	Flat Roof	MS
LB	Debenhams	3/6/2023	AON	Flat Roof	MS
LB	Debenhams	3/6/2023	AON	Flat Roof	MS
LB	Apple Building	15/6/2023	Chick	Flat Roof	SR
LB	Dazzle Building	15/6/2023	AON	?	CHS
LB	City Hall	15/6/2023	chick	Flat roof	CHS
LB	Anglesy st Courthouse	15/6/2023	AON	Flat Roof	MS
LB	Brooks Haughton	15/6/2023	chick	flat roof	MS
LB	St John's College	15/6/2023	AON	flat roof	MS
LB	School of Music	13/6/2023	territorial adult diving	flat roof	MS
LB	RTE	19/6/2023	AON	flat roof	MS

County Cork Ringing Report 2019-2023

Barry O'Mahony

This report continues the custom of reporting the annual Bird Ringing effort as part of the Cork Bird Report and follows the previous publication which covered years to 2007. The absence of publication for the intervening year is unfortunate but the numbers of birds ringed between 2007 and 2019 are included in the Grand Total numbers reported here..

Since the previous report the ringing effort has increased very significantly with more ringers being active, new ringers in training, new projects in progress and new techniques, e.g. thermal imaging, being utilised. The Annual Totals strongly reflect these extra efforts.

Cape Clear Bird Observatory, whose ringing territory includes the islands of Roaringwater Bay, continues to contribute a significant proportion of the ringing totals.

The added value of colour marking, using leg rings or wing tags, allows regular tracking of individual birds with greater ease. The popularity of bird watching and use of precision optics and camera equipment adds greatly to the re-sighting rates.

Active colour ring projects in Co. Cork include: Mute Swan, Grey Heron, Little Egret, Moorhen, Coot, Ringed Plover, Whimbrel, Black-tailed Godwit, Herring Gull, Lesser Black-backed Gull, Rock Dove, Swift, Kestrel, Peregrine, Chough, Rook, Raven, Starling and Pied Wagtail. These and many other international projects opportunities to find colour-ringed birds.

A selection of recoveries is included showing some of the most interesting movements since ringing. As it covers a five-year period and publication space is limited, the list is, understandably, incomplete

A number of species were ringed for the first time in Co Cork since the previous report and are listed below

	Year		
Arctic Warbler	2009	Hume's Warbler	2019
Pallas's Warbler	2010	Baird's Sandpipe	2020
Woodcock	2013	Least Sandpiper	2020
Tufted Duck	2014	Iberian Chiffchaff	2020
Shoveler	2015	Wigeon	2021
White-tailed Eagle	2015	Sanderling	2021
Mediterranean Gull	2015	White-winged Black Tern	2021
Lesser Yellowlegs	2017	Tree Sparrow	2022
Common Rosefinch	2017	Penduline Tit	2023
Arctic Tern	2018	Cetti's Warbler	2023

A Top Five Species list is a convenient way of seeing the annual ringing effort at a glance.

2019		2020		2021		2022		2023	
Blue Tit	643	Goldfinch	837	Sedge Warbler	47	Sedge Warbler	35	Swallow	96
Great Tit	595	Great Tit	402	Great Tit	35	Lesser Black-	21	Sedge	31
Chaffinch	519	Chaffinch	388	Goldfinch	31	Common Tern	19	Chaffinch	28
Chiffchaff	488	Sedge	384	Chaffinch	30	Goldfinch	19	Common	21
Goldfinch	463	Blue Tit	311	Lesser Black-backed Gull	24		18		19
					4	Dunlin	8	Barn Owl	9

Table 2. Top Five species ringed in each year

Annual Totals per Species are listed below to show *pulli* (nestlings) and adult birds both separately and combined. In keeping with the traditional format of this county report, the Grand Total since

Penduline Tit *Remiz pendulinus*, Lough Beg, March 2023
B.O'Mahony

1975 is calculated. As the first Irish Ringing Report was compiled in 1975, it has been prudent for the Cork Ringing Report to follow suit although the former does not include a similar Grand Total calculation.

Woodcock *Scolopax rusticola* B.O'Mahony, Churchtown, February 2026

	2019		2020		2021		2022		2023		Totals 1975-2023		
	Pul l.	F.g. al	Pull.	F.g.	Total								
Canada Goose												42	42
Mute Swan	8	8	5	5	1	1	7	7	8	8	8	1039	1047
Whooper Swan												1	1
Shelduck											15	11	26
Shoveler												2	2
Wigeon					1	1			1	1		2	2
Mallard	2	2	5	5					10	10		29	29
Teal	3	3	3	3	2	2			3	3		28	28
Pochard												2	2
TuftedDuck							2	2	6	6		9	9
Great Northern Diver												1	1
Storm Petrel	210	210			15	15	6	6	18	18		16777	16777
Leach's Petrel												3	3
Fulmar											70	15	85
Manx Shearwater												93	93
Great Shearwater												1	1
Grey Heron									1	1	36	4	40
Little Egret	1	1							4	4	7	3	10
Gannet											127	43	170
Shag	2	2									54	1	55
Cormorant									1	1	1360	3	1363
Sparrowhawk	1	1	4	4	4	4	2	2	7	7	51	79	130
HenHarrier	6	6									88	4	92
White-tailed Eagle			1	1			1	1	1	1	5		5
Buzzard	3	3	5	5	11	12	4	5	2	2	89	31	120
Water Rail	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	6	6	2	45	47
Cornerake												1	1
Moorhen	2	2			2	2	3	3				66	66
Coot	6	6	6	6			17	17	6	6		102	102
Spotted Crane												2	2
Oystercatcher	4	4	10	10	1	1	1	1	7	7	1	509	510
Lapwing					1	1			24	24	3	58	61

	2019		2020		2021		2022		2023		Totals 1975-2023				
	Pul l.	Tot al	Pull.	F.g.	Total										
Golden Plover	2	2	1	1	2	2			4	4		26	26		
Grey Plover	1	1	2	2			1	1				9	9		
Ringed Plover	9	9	35	35	10	10	30	30	32	32	43	155	198		
Whimbrel	19	19	2	2	30	30	14	14	15	15		124	124		
Curlew	19	19	8	8	1	1			62	62		1281	1281		
Bar-tailed Godwit									1	1		53	53		
Blackt Godwit	15	15	12	12	11	11	13	13	47	47		197	197		
Turnstone									1	1	214	18	232		
Knot	9	9	2	2			1	1	2	2		28	28		
Ruff												15	15		
Curlew Sandpiper			4	4			2	2	1	1		42	42		
Sanderling					1	1	1	1	1	1		3	3		
Dunlin	135	135	178	178	105	105	188	188	70	70		2132	2132		
Baird's Sandpiper			1	1								1	1		
Little Stint			2	2								13	13		
Least Sandpiper			1	1								1	1		
Woodcock	58	58	134	134	68	68	20	20	32	32		336	336		
Jack Snipe			6	6	4	4	5	5	7	7		27	27		
Snipe	40	40	57	57	69	69	35	35	69	69		344	344		
Pectoral Sandpiper									1	1		179	179		
Common Sand			2	2					4	4	4	14	18		
Spotted Sandpiper												2	2		
Green Sandpiper												1	1		
Redshank	51	51	32	32	30	30	24	24	83	83		1053	1053		
Lesser Yellowlegs												1	1		
Spotted Redshank												2	2		
Greenshank	2	2	5	5	5	5			2	2		36	36		
Wilson's Phalarope												1	1		
Black-headed Gull	5	5	5	5	1	1	2	7	9	3	5	8	18	261	279
Med gull												1	1		
Common Gull							1	1				4	4		
Great Black-backed Gull	1	1			1	1	3	3	6	6	808	10	818		

	2019			2020			2021			2022			2023			Totals 1975-2023			
	Pul l.	F.g.	Tot al	Pull.	F.g.	Total													
Herring Gull	7		7	5		5	1		1	2		2	29		29	2492	44	2536	
Lesser Black-backed Gull	314		314	69		69	244		244	213		213	79		79	1833	8	1841	
Little Gull																	1	1	
Sabine's Gull																	1	1	
SandwichTern		4	4					3	3								58	58	
Common Tern	106	9	115	74	9	83	130	1	131	198		198	208	9	217	2532	313	2845	
Arctic Tern	1		1													28		28	
Black Tern																	3	3	
White-winged Black Tern								1	1								1	1	
Great Skua																	1	1	
Guillemot																	4	4	
Razorbill																3	2	5	
Black Guillemot																9		9	
Rock Dove		11	11					13	13		73	73		18	18	1	192	193	
Stock Dove	2		2	1		1				2		2				32		32	
Woodpigeon	1	9	10		14	14		2	2		3	3		2	2	28	82	110	
Turtle Dove																	2	2	
Collared Dove		1	1					4	4		1	1		7	7	5	38	43	
Barn Owl	26	4	30	102	5	107	57	9	66	84	4	88	184	15	199	594	57	651	
Long-eared Owl	3		3					2	2		2	2	4		14	14	17	26	43
Short-eared Owl														6	6		9	9	
Scops Owl																	1	1	
Swift				2		2										2	4	6	
Kingfisher		3	3		4	4		3	3		3	3		6	6		36	36	
Hoopoe																	1	1	
Wryneck																	5	5	
Yellow-bellied Sapsucker																	1	1	
Great Spotted Woodpecker																			
Kestrel				8		8	6	1	7	14		14	5		5	56	8	64	
Red-footed Falcon																	1	1	
Merlin																	2	2	

	2019			2020			2021			2022			2023			Totals 1975-2023		
	Pul l.	E.g.	Tot al	Pull.	E.g.	Total												
Peregrine							2		2	1		1			4	2	6	
Red-eyed Vireo																11	11	
Golden Oriole																3	3	
Red-backed Shrike																3	3	
Jay		4	4				2	2		8	8					59	59	
Magpie		1	1	4	8	12	2	1	3	3	3	3			26	61	87	
Chough															10	22	32	
Jackdaw	5	62	67	4	107	111	4	77	81	3	32	35	8	12	20	55	352	407
Rook		92	92		174	174		48	48		41	41		96	96		722	722
Hooded Crow		3	3	1	5	6	3	8	11		7	7		2	2	74	38	112
Raven	6		6				16		16	13		13	2		2	44	2	46
Coal Tit	165	167	332		124	124	8	29	37		6	6		17	17	1044	2069	3113
Blue Tit	326	317	643	21	290	311	34	145	179	8	100	108	24	155	179	3413	4870	8283
Great Tit	325	270	595	11	391	402	130	229	359	16	65	81	24	111	135	2592	3600	6192
Penduline Tit														4	4		4	4
Skylark					3	3		12	12		45	45		111	111	28	180	208
Sand Martin		13	13		23	23		12	12	3	89	92		103	103	15	5557	5572
Swallow	9	26	35	9	42	51	21	28	49	27	130	157	44	921	965	2349	12447	14796
House Martin		16	16		41	41		2	2		1	1				3	185	188
Cetti's Warbler														1	1		1	1
Long-tailed Tit		62	62		106	106		42	42		12	12		52	52		926	926
Willow Warbler	2	189	191	3	143	146	107	107		65	65		84	84	25	3386	3411	
Chiffchaff		488	488		5	246	251	187	187		122	122		170	170	6	3641	3647
Iberian Chiffchaff					1	1											1	1
Wood Warbler																	25	25
Western Bonelli's Warbler																	2	2
Dusky Warbler																	1	1
Radde's Warbler																	1	1
Pallas's Warbler																	2	2
Yellow-browed Warbler		4	4		2	2				1	1		2	2			182	182
Hume's Warbler		1	1														1	1

	2019			2020			2021			2022			2023			Totals 1975-2023		
	Pul l.	F.g.	Tot al	Pull.	F.g.	Total												
Arctic Warbler																	1	1
Sedge Warbler	371	371		2	382	384	5	474	479	2	350	352	2	308	310	36	20689	20725
Reed Warbler	17	17		53	53		54	54		51	51		60	60	25	2500	2525	
Greenish Warbler																		
Marsh Warbler																	2	2
Olivaceous W																	1	1
Melodious W																	12	12
Icterine Warbler																	11	11
Grasshopper W	3	3		9	9		7	7		2	2		1	1	8	83	91	
Pallas's G Warbler																	1	1
Blackcap	218	218		133	133		103	103		78	78		1	104	105	1	1630	1631
Garden Warbler							4	4									103	103
Barred Warbler																	2	2
Lesser Whitethroat	1	1					1	1									22	22
Whitethroat	41	41		12	12		29	29		13	13		12	12	4	463	467	
Subalpine Warbler																	1	1
Gray-ch Thrush																	3	3
Goldcrest	430	430		140	140		134	134		5	61	66		120	120	5	5831	5836
Firecrest	2	2															75	75
Wren	205	205		1	138	139		120	120		118	118		109	109	15	3709	3724
Treecreeper	7	7		1	1		2	2		2	2		3	3	3	122	125	
Starling	7	7		9	20	29	17	12	29	5	13	18	10	23	33	101	322	423
Ring Ouzel																	1	1
Blackbird	4	129	133	1	126	127		101	101	1	57	58		100	100	135	2353	2488
Fieldfare	2	2		1	1		1	1		2	2		3	3	1	89	90	
Redwing	29	29		51	51		18	18		3	3		18	18		299	299	
Song Thrush	1	42	43	5	37	42		41	41		28	28	2	57	59	119	951	1070
Mistle Thrush	2	2								1	1		1	1		15	8	23
Spotted Flycatcher	2	2					1	1		4	4					70	193	263
Robin	6	168	174		138	138	1	113	114		113	113	8	108	116	380	3084	3464
Thrush Nightingale																	1	1
Pied Flycatcher							3	3					5	5		190	190	

	2019			2020			2021			2022			2023			Totals 1975-2023			
	Pul l.	E.g.	Tot al	Pull.	E.g.	Total													
Red-b Flycatcher																	12	12	
Redstart																	20	20	
Black Redstart																	83	83	
Whinchat																	1	1	
Stonechat		26	26		38	38		31	31		44	44		5	5	516	433	949	
Wheatear											2	2		4	4	7	19	26	
Pied Wheatear																	1	1	
Dipper	40	9	49		2	2	24	12	36	24	4	28	18	2	20	4712	1026	5738	
Duncock		109	109	3	115	118		122	122		72	72		65	65	19	2232	2251	
House Sparrow	11	54	65	10	78	88	33	88	121	16	50	66	9	20	29	100	1303	1403	
Tree Sparrow											2	2					2	2	
Pied/White Wagtail	5	10	15		16	16		21	21		13	13		2	2	42	606	648	
Grey Wagtail	5	7	12		9	9	5	24	29		6	6	5	3	8	577	175	752	
Meadow Pipit	1	41	42		188	188		83	83		82	82		30	30	62	1033	1095	
Tree Pipit		1	1					1	1								7	7	
Rock Pipit					2	2					5	5		2	2		83	83	
Chaffinch		519	519		388	388		309	309		99	99		283	283	6	3888	3894	
Brambling		3	3					1	1		1	1		2	2		77	77	
Hawfinch																	3	3	
Bullfinch		52	52		31	31		18	18		4	4		24	24	1	444	445	
Common Rosefinch								1	1								2	2	
Greenfinch		400	400		196	196		116	116		51	51		60	60	5	3466	3471	
Linnet		21	21		20	20		32	32		12	12		2	2	4	343	347	
Goldfinch		463	463		837	837		319	319		191	191		68	68	13	3650	3663	
Redpoll (Common/Lesser)		76	76		46	46		14	14		8	8		16	16		509	509	
Common Crossbill								2	2								55	55	
Siskin	1	199	200		257	257		104	104		151	151		7	7	1	2961	2962	
Yellowhammer														1	1	2	1	13	14
Ortolan Bunting																	1	1	
Little Bunting																	1	1	
Snow Bunting																	2	2	

	2019			2020			2021			2022			2023			Totals 1975-2023		
	Pul l.	F.g.	Tot al	Pul l.	F.g.	Tot al	Pul l.	F.g.	Tot al	Pul l.	F.g.	Tot al	Pul l.	F.g.	Tot al	Pull.	F.g.	Total
Lapland Bunting																	1	1
Reed Bunting	24		24	38		38	37		37	27		27	20		20		977	977
Rustic Bunting																	1	1
Bobolink																	1	1
Blackpoll Warbler																	2	2
Yellow-rumped Warbler																	2	2
Rose-breasted Grosbeak																	6	6
Indigo Bunting																	1	1
Totals	1384	6050	7434	356	5764	6120	752	3889	4641	650	2915	3565	681	4105	4786	27307	130828	158135

Selected Recoveries

Recovery details have been largely selected from the BTO Online Ringing and Nest Recording Reports supplemented by contributing ringers and observers.

All recoveries are listed in the standard format detailing ring number, age, date and place of ringing on the first line, followed on the next line(s) by recovery method, date, location, distance and direction travelled. Recovery methods are described as reported by the finder. Where a bird has been identified by colour rings the recovery method states “Alive (c-r)”; if the metal ring has been read in the field the recovery method states “Alive (r-r)”

Whooper Swan

XY2634 Adult Female
25-02-2016 Martin Mere Swan Pipe: 53°37'N 2°52'W (Lancashire)
Freshly dead
27-01-2023 Awbeg River, Ballyheia: 52°17'N 8°41'W (Cork) 416km WSW 6y 11m 2d
(disease)

Mallard

GC60446 Adult Male
05-10-2018 Dunster Beach, near Minehead: c. 51°11'N 3°25'W (Somerset)
Freshly dead
27-01-2019 Fermoy: 52°8'N 8°15'W (Cork) 349km WNW 0y 3m 22d
(shot)

Red-throated Diver

1440422	Nestling	21-07-2019	Hoy: 58°49'N 3°17'W (Orkney)
	Freshly dead (on netting)	15-12-2020	Courtmacsherry Bay: 51°37'N 8°40'W (Cork) 870km SSW 1y 4m 24d
Storm Petrel			
2735551	Adult Male	04-08-2018	Old Head of Kinsale: 51°37'N 8°32'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	07-07-2019	Annagh Head, Bellmullet: 54°14'N 10°7'W (Mayo) 308km NNW 0y 11m 3d
2722829	Adult	22-07-2018	Skokholm Island: 51°41'N 5°17'W (Pembrokeshire)
	Caught by ringer	17-08-2019	Cape Clear Bird Observatory: 51°25'N 9°30'W (Cork) 294km W 1y 0m 26d
2496892	Adult	24-07-1999	Leganagh Point, Seven Heads: 51°33'N 8°43'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	15-06-2022	Beniguet: 48°21'N 4°51'W (Finistere) France 452km SE 22y 10m 22d
	Caught by ringer	17-08-2023	Battery Point, Lundy Island: 51°10'N 4°40'W (Devon) 338km E 6y 0m 4d
2709939	Adult	08-07-2018	Old Head of Kinsale: 51°37'N 8°32'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	09-07-2021	Eilean Nan Ron: 58°33'N 4°20'W (Highland) 816km NNE 3y 0m 1d
Manx Shearwater			
ET01766	First-year	29-08-1997	Copeland Bird Observatory: 54°41'N 5°32'W (Down)
	Dead	31-05-2018	Cork Harbour, near Roches Point: 51°47'N 8°13'W (Cork) 369km SSW 20y 9m 2d
Little Egret			
GC81725	Nestling	29-05-2009	Ardfry, Oranmore: 53°16'N 8°58'W (Galway)
	Alive (c-r)	16-08-2020	Rosscarbery: 51°33'N 9°1'W (Cork) 186km S 11y 2m 18d
Gannet			
1395414	Adult	29-06-2011	Bull Rock: c. 51°35'N 10°17'W (Cork)
	Freshly dead (storm)	12-09-2020	Aberffraw: 53°10'N 4°28'W (Isle of Anglesey) 432km ENE 9y 2m 14d
263742	Nestling	11-07-1986	Skarvlakken, Andoy: 69°9'N 15°40'E (Nordland) Norway
	Freshly dead	28-12-2021	Ballynamona: 51°49'N 8°10'W (Cork) 2,305km SW 35y 5m 17d
Shag			
1349516	Nestling	05-05-1998	Great Saltee Island: 52°7'N 6°36'W (Wexford)

	Unknown (ring only)	05-04-2019	near Lisheen, Roaringwater Bay: 51°31'N 9°23'W (Cork) 202km WSW 20y 11m 0d
Cormorant			
5179291	Nestling	29-06-1999	Sovereign Islands, Oysterhaven: 51°40'N 8°27'W (Cork)
	Unknown (ring only)	18-03-2020	Cork: 51°52'N 8°25'W (Cork) 23km N 20y 8m 18d
5266579	First-year	18-06-2022	Ireland's Eye: 53°24'N 6°4'W (Dublin)
	Alive (c-r)	30-08-2023	Raffeen: c. 51°50'N 8°21'W (Cork) 232km SW 1y 2m 12d
Sparrowhawk			
EZ04806	First-year Female Freshly dead (hit glass)	03-11-2017	Bottle Hill, near Rathduff: 52°3'N 8°32'W (Cork)
		30-06-2023	Newgrove, Whitechurch: 52°0'N 8°33'W (Cork) 4km 5y 7m 27d
White-tailed Eagle			
XY0043	Nestling	22-06-2022	Confidential Site: c. 51°54'N 8°50'W (Cork)
	Alive (c-r)	22-04-2023	Confidential Site: c. 52°7'N 9°43'W (Kerry) 36km N 0y 10m 0d
	Alive (wing-tag seen)	27-06-2023	Confidential Site: c. 53°21'N 8°56'W (Galway) 195km N 1y 0m 5d
ZY3428	Nestling Male Alive (satellite- tagged)	28-06-2016	Confidential Site: c. 51°54'N 8°50'W (Cork)
		23-07-2017	Confidential Site: c. 52°7'N 9°43'W (Kerry) 78km WNW 1y 0m 25d
	Long dead	11-06-2018	Confidential Site: c. 52°7'N 9°43'W (Kerry) 71km NW 1y 11m 14d
Buzzard			
GC95874	Nestling	21-06-2013	Glandoran Upper: 52°40'N 6°20'W (Wexford)
	Freshly dead	11-01-2021	East Ferry: 51°50'N 8°12'W (Cork) 156km SW 7y 6m 21d
GR38768	Nestling	17-06-2012	Buckstown: c. 51°49'N 8°11'W (Cork)
	Freshly dead	23-03-2023	Unnamed Site: 51°51'N 8°14'W (Cork) 6km NW 10y 9m 6d
AJ57403	Nestling	13-06-2011	Croaghturigeen, near Ballyclough: 52°8'N 8°47'W (Cork)
	Freshly dead	13-03-2018	Leperstown, Dunmore East: 52°9'N 7°2'W (Waterford) 120km E 6y 9m 0d
Coot			
AJ57420	Adult	26-12-2013	The Lough, Cork City: 51°53'N 8°29'W (Cork)

	Alive (c-r)	15-05-2021	The Lough, Cork City: 51°53'N 8°29'W (Cork)	0km	7y 4m 19d
GR26351	First-year	26-12-2013	The Lough, Cork City: 51°53'N 8°29'W (Cork)		
	Alive (c-r)	02-10-2023	The Lough, Cork City: 51°53'N 8°29'W (Cork)	0km	9y 9m 6d

Oystercatcher

FP59982	Adult	20-03-2011	Loch of Bosquoy, Harray: 59°2'N 3°13'W (Orkney)		
	Caught by ringer	19-09-2019	Harper's Island, Cork Harbour: 51°54'N 8°18'W (Cork)	855km	SSW 8y 5m 30d
4118700	Adult	31-05-2020	Audsholt, Arnarbaeli, Olfus: 63°55'N 21°12'W (Árnessýsla)	Iceland	
	Alive (c-r)	23-10-2020	Rosscarbery: 51°34'N 9°1'W (Cork)	1,549km	SSE 0y 4m 22d
FJ56466	Adult	07-03-2021	Myroe Levels, Lough Foyle: 55°6'N 7°0'W (Londonderry)		
	Alive (r-r)	07-01-2022	Owenahincha Strand, Rosscarbery: 51°33'N 8°59'W (Cork)	415km	SSW 0y 10m 0d
4118518	Nestling	30-05-2021	Laugarvatn: 64°12'N 20°43'W (Árnessýsla)	Iceland	
	Alive (c-r)	13-04-2022	near Dunkettle, Cork City: 51°54'N 8°23'W (Cork)	1,543km	SSE 0y 10m 14d
	Alive (c-r)	03-05-2022	L.Beg, Ringaskiddy: 51°49'N 8°18'W (Cork)	1,554km	SSE 0y 11m 3d
4108261	Adult	29-05-2013	Sandur, Bolungarvík: 66°7'N 23°13'W (Norður-Ísafjarðarsýsla)	Iceland	
	Alive (c-r)	11-10-2023	Owenahincha Strand, Rosscarbery: 51°33'N 8°59'W (Cork)	1,807km	SSE 10y 4m 12d

Lapwing

DK12592	Adult	24-08-2002	Ythan Estuary, Newburgh, Aberdeen: 57°19'N 2°0'W		(Aberdeenshire)
	Freshly dead (cold weather)	12-01-2010	Flaxfort: 51°38'N 8°41'W (Cork)	764km	SW 7y 4m 19d

Ringed Plover

NW86370	Nestling	25-07-2020	Wig, near Bangor: 53°13'N 4°3'W (Gwynedd)		
	Caught by ringer	01-11-2021	Kilbrittain: 51°38'N 8°41'W (Cork)	361km	WSW 1y 3m 7d
NW86377	Adult	06-09-2020	Llanfairfechan: 53°14'N 4°0'W (Conwy)		
	Alive (c-r)	31-01-2022	near Crookhaven: 51°27'N 9°44'W (Cork)	437km	WSW 1y 4m 25d
NW67459	Adult Male	01-10-2022	Kilbrittain: 51°38'N 8°41'W (Cork)		

	Alive (c-r)	21-08-2023	Heacham: 52°53'N 0°27'E (Norfolk) 639km ENE 0y 10m 20d
NP07074	First-year	04-09-2022	Kilbrittain: 51°38'N 8°40'W (Cork)
	Alive (c-r)	04-08-2023	Gibraltar Point NNR: 53°5'N 0°20'E (Lincolnshire) 633km ENE 0y 11m 0d
Whimbrel			
EX28159	Adult	05-05-2013	The Gann: c. 51°43'N 5°10'W (Pembrokeshire)
	Alive (c-r)	21-01-2017	Ga Maior Beafada: 11°34'N 15°25'W (Guinea Bissau) Guinea Bissau 4,558km SSW 3y 8m 16d
	Alive (c-r)	30-04-2019	Clonakilty / Cloich Na Coillte: 51°36'N 8°51'W (Cork) 256km W 5y 11m 25d
EZ04824	Adult	24-04-2018	Harper's Island, Cork Harbour: 51°54'N 8°18'W (Cork)
	Alive (c-r)	27-04-2021	Harper's Island, Cork Harbour: 51°54'N 8°18'W (Cork) 0km 3y 0m 3d
	Alive (c-r)	28-04-2022	Harper's Island, Cork Harbour: 51°54'N 8°18'W (Cork) 0km 4y 0m 4d
	Alive (c-r)	04-05-2022	Harper's Island, Cork Harbour: 51°54'N 8°18'W (Cork) 0km 4y 0m 10d
EZ04881	First-year	25-04-2019	Harper's Island, Cork Harbour: 51°54'N 8°18'W (Cork)
	Alive (c-r)	29-04-2022	Harper's Island, Cork Harbour: 51°54'N 8°18'W (Cork) 0km 3y 0m 4d
EZ33712	Adult	16-05-2017	The Gann: c. 51°43'N 5°10'W (Pembrokeshire)
	Alive (c-r)	04-05-2023	Confidential Site: c. 51°54'N 8°50'W (Cork) 215km W 5y 11m 18d
Curlew			
FJ33467	Adult Female	20-03-2021	Dolydd Hafren, Forden,montgomery: 52°35'N 3°10'W (Powys)
	Alive (c-r)	12-06-2021	Lagoon 4, Rutland Water: 52°39'N 0°42'W (Rutland) 167km E 2m 23d
	Alive (c-r)	30-10-2021	Kealfadda Bridge: 51°31'N 9°39'W (Cork) 461km WSW 0y 7m 10d
FH49895	Adult	28-09-2014	Lough Beg, Ringaskiddy: 51°49'N 8°19'W (Cork)
	Freshly dead	08-05-2021	Handog, Lit: 63°18'N 14°58'E (Jämtland) Sweden 1,876km NE 6y 7m 10d
FJ10849	Adult Female	11-03-2017	Dolydd Hafren, Forden,montgomery: 52°35'N 3°10'W (Powys)
	Alive (c-r)	05-12-2022	Adrigole Harbour: 51°41'N 9°43'W (Cork) 460km W 5y 8m 24d
FJ33468	Adult Male	01-04-2021	Birchope, near Bridges, Shrewsbury: 52°33'N 2°55'W (Shropshire)
	Alive (c-r)	23-11-2022	Ring, Clonarkilty: 51°36'N 8°51'W (Cork) 419km WSW 1y 7m 22d
FJ89016	Nestling	02-06-2023	Dallowgill Moor, Pateley Bridge: 54°8'N 1°44'W (North Yorkshire)

SS87878	Caught by ringer	24-08-2023	Harper's Island, Cork Harbour: 51°54'N 8°18'W (Cork) 506km WSW 0y 2m 22d
	Adult Male	20-05-2023	Foelasfechan, Gwytherin: 53°7'N 3°42'W (Conwy)
FJ69207	Alive (c-r)	04-09-2023	Sherkin Island: 51°28'N 9°24'W (Cork) 430km WSW 0y 3m 15d
	Adult Male	09-05-2023	Bridges,Wentnor: 52°33'N 2°53'W (Shropshire)
FJ10852	Alive (c-r)	02-09-2023	Inchydoney Causeway: 51°35'N 8°53'W (Cork) 424km WSW 0y 3m 24d
	Adult Female	11-03-2017	Dolydd Hafren, Forden,montgomery: 52°35'N 3°10'W (Powys)
	Alive (c-r)	13-04-2019	Weston Farm,binweston: 52°37'N 3°2'W (Shropshire) 10km ENE 2y 1m 2d
	Alive (c-r)	07-09-2020	Ring, Clonarkilty: 51°36'N 8°51'W (Cork) 403km WSW 3y 5m 27d
	Alive (c-r)	25-03-2021	Priest Weston: 52°33'N 3°3'W (Powys) 9km ESE 4y 0m 14d
CT020635	Alive (c-r)	19-09-2021	Ring, Clonarkilty: 51°36'N 8°51'W (Cork) 403km WSW 4y 6m 8d
	Alive (c-r)	19-02-2023	Dolydd Hafren, Forden,montgomery: 52°35'N 3°10'W (Powys) 0km 5y 11m 8d
	Alive (c-r)	29-08-2023	Ring, Clonarkilty: 51°36'N 8°51'W (Cork) 403km WSW 6y 5m 18d
	Nestling	15-07-2021	Temmes, Pohjois-Pohjanmaa: 64°37'N 25°37'E (Oulu) Finland
	Alive (c-r)	19-03-2023	Whitegate: 51°49'N 8°14'W (Cork) 2,417km WSW 1y 8m 4d
4023489	Nestling	08-06-1981	Hammel, Lastrup: 52°48'N 7°46'E (Weser-Ems) Germany
FB01606	Freshly dead	07-01-2010	Cobh: 51°50'N 8°18'W (Cork) 1,096km W 28y 6m 30d
	Adult Male	26-03-2017	River Severn, Caersws: c. 52°31'N 3°24'W (Powys)
FH49950	Alive (c-r)	10-07-2019	Rosscarbery, near Cork: 51°33'N 8°59'W (Cork) 397km WSW 2y 3m 14d
	First-year	24-03-2018	Lough Beg, near Ringaskiddy: 51°48'N 8°19'W (Cork)
FH87198	Caught by ringer	27-03-2019	Dolydd Hafren, Forden,montgomery: 52°35'N 3°10'W (Powys) 362km ENE 1y 0m 3d
	Adult	16-01-2016	Wensley Ings, near Leyburn: 54°17'N 1°52'W (North Yorkshire)
	Alive (c-r)	23-09-2019	Rosscarberry: 51°33'N 9°0'W (Cork) 566km WSW 3y 8m 7d
	Alive (c-r)	02-01-2020	West Haremire, Preston-under-Scar: 54°18'N 1°53'W (North Yorkshire) 2km 3y 11m 17d
	Alive (c-r)	20-06-2020	Collier Gate, W Bolton Moor, Wensleydale: 54°19'N 2°0'W (North Yorkshire) 9km WNW 4y 5m 4d
	Alive (c-r)	11-09-2020	Rosscarberry: 51°33'N 9°0'W (Cork) 566km WSW 4y 7m 26d

Bar-tailed Godwit

7218261	First-year Male	08-09-2018	Revtangen, Klepp: 58°45'N 5°28'E (Rogaland) Norway
	Alive (c-r)	31-03-2019	Ardnahinch Beach, Ballycotton: 51°49'N 8°1'W (Cork) 1,148km SW 0y 6m 23d
K06821	First-year Female	31-08-2019	Revtangen, Klepp: 58°45'N 5°28'E (Rogaland) Norway
	Alive (c-r)	23-09-2019	Ballymacoda: 51°54'N 7°53'W (Cork) 1,136km SW 0y 0m 23d
Knot			
SK02140	First-year	27-02-2020	Harper's Island, Cork Harbour: 51°54'N 8°18'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	21-09-2020	Griend: 53°13'N 5°15'E (Griend) The Netherlands 929km ENE 0y 6m 25d
SR99120	Adult	30-03-2018	Altcar Rifle Range Foreshore, Hightown: 53°31'N 3°5'W (Merseyside)
	Alive (c-r)	26-05-2018	Dyrafjordur: 65°51'N 23°18'W (Vestur-Ísafjarðarsýsla) Iceland 1,768km NNW 0y 1m 26d
	Alive (c-r)	11-08-2018	Ainsdale: 53°38'N 3°1'W (Merseyside) 14km NNE 0y 4m 12d
	Alive (c-r)	22-09-2018	Altcar Ranges, near Southport: 53°32'N 3°5'W (Merseyside) 2km 0y 5m 23d
	Alive (c-r)	19-12-2018	Thurstaston Shore, Dee Estuary, Wirral: 53°20'N 3°9'W (Merseyside) 23km SSW 0y 8m 19d
	Alive (c-r)	16-01-2019	Blackrock, Cork City: 51°53'N 8°21'W (Cork) 400km WSW 0y 9m 17d
ST99075	Adult	04-03-2022	Ainsdale Foreshore: 53°36'N 3°3'W (Merseyside)
	Alive (c-r)	30-05-2022	Arctic Bay, Baffin Island: 73°1'N 85°5'W (Canada) Canada 4,466km NNW 0y 2m 26d
	Alive (c-r)	17-11-2022	Blackrock, Cork City: 51°53'N 8°21'W (Cork) 406km WSW 0y 8m 13d
Dunlin			
BT94902	First-year	28-09-2019	Ynyslas National Nature Reserve, borth: 52°31'N 4°3'W (Ceredigion)
	Caught by ringer	17-11-2019	Harper's Island, Cork Harbour: 51°54'N 8°18'W (Cork) 299km WSW 0y 1m 20d
NT97688	First-year	23-08-2021	Filey Brigg Country Park: c. 54°12'N 0°15'W (North Yorkshire)
	Alive (c-r)	11-09-2021	Clonakilty : 51°37'N 8°52'W (Cork) 646km WSW 0y 0m 19d
NT63453	First-year	20-10-2020	Kilbrittain: 51°39'N 8°40'W (Cork)
	Alive (r-r)	10-05-2021	Dawlish Warren: 50°35'N 3°26'W (Devon) 384km ESE 0y 6m 20d
NB04398	First-year	05-12-2017	Harper's Island, Cork Harbour: 51°54'N 8°18'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	23-01-2022	Belgrano, Abergele: 53°17'N 3°33'W (Conwy) 357km ENE 4y 1m 18d
BX80292	Adult	23-12-2021	Harper's Island, Cork Harbour: 51°54'N 8°18'W (Cork)

	Caught by ringer	21-07-2022	Ujscie Wisly, Swibno: 54°21'N 18°57'E (Pomorskie) Poland 1,838km ENE 0y 6m 28d
8N64295	First-year	26-08-2021	Revtangen, Klepp: 58°45'N 5°28'E (Rogaland) Norway
	Caught by ringer	11-11-2022	Kilbrittain: 51°38'N 8°40'W (Cork) 1,194km SW 1y 2m 16d
BT63236	Adult	05-01-2018	Harper's Island, Cork Harbour: 51°54'N 8°18'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	12-07-2023	Ottenby: 56°12'N 16°24'E (Öland) Sweden 1,680km ENE 5y 6m 7d
3597512	Adult	20-07-2016	Ottenby: 56°12'N 16°24'E (Öland) Sweden
	Caught by ringer	05-01-2018	Harper's Island, Cork Harbour: 51°54'N 8°18'W (Cork) 1,672km W 1y 5m 16d
Little Stint			
2773902	First-year	07-10-2020	Kilbrittain: 51°38'N 8°40'W (Cork)
	Alive (r-r)	08-10-2020	Between Stags Head Rock, and Old Head of Kinsale: 51°39'N 8°40'W (Cork) 0km 0y 0m 1d
	Alive (r-r)	20-10-2020	Biotope de Iñurritza, Zarautz: 43°16'N 2°9'W (Guipuzcoa) Spain 1,051km SSE 0y 0m 13d
Woodcock			
EA08614	Adult	14-03-2018	Lanarth: c. 50°2'N 5°7'W (Cornwall)
	Freshly dead (shot)	26-12-2019	Tralispean: 51°28'N 9°16'W (Cork) 332km WNW 1y 9m 12d
EA68272	Adult	05-02-2020	Chimneyfield: 52°4'N 8°28'W (Cork)
	Freshly dead (shot)	22-03-2020	Vitebsk: 55°12'N 30°10'E (Vitebsk Oblast) Belarus 2,568km ENE 0y 1m 17d
EA59760	First-year	20-02-2021	Warrencourt, Kilmurry: 51°50'N 8°53'W (Cork)
	Freshly dead (shot)	07-05-2021	Basharovo: 58°30'N 49°15'E (Kirov Oblast) Russian Federation 3,753km NE 0y 2m 17d
EA59729	First-year	12-12-2020	Warrencourt, Kilmurry: 51°50'N 8°54'W (Cork)
	Freshly dead (hit glass)	14-03-2021	Utrecht: 52°4'N 5°6'E (Utrecht) The Netherlands 960km E 0y 3m 2d
Snipe			
794577	Full-grown Female	20-06-2021	Syðst, Hrísey: 66°0'N 18°22'W (Eyjafjarðarsýsla) Iceland
	Freshly dead (shot)	06-01-2022	Lehena: 51°51'N 8°53'W (Cork) 1,659km SSE 0y 6m 17d
Redshank			

DE39722	Adult	29-01-2017	Harper's Island, Cork Harbour: 51°54'N 8°18'W (Cork)
	Freshly dead (cat)	10-06-2019	Balinoe, Tiree: 56°28'N 6°55'W (Argyll and Bute) 516km N 2y 4m 12d
DE39684	Adult	25-03-2019	Harper's Island, Cork Harbour: 51°54'N 8°18'W (Cork)
	Freshly dead	11-06-2022	Balranald RSPB, North Uist: 57°35'N 7°30'W (Western Isles) 636km N 3y 2m 17d
Kittiwake			
FX25870	Nestling	08-07-2018	Cleden-Cap-Sizun: 48°1'N 4°37'W (Finistere) France
	Freshly dead	09-07-2019	The Long Strand: 51°33'N 8°58'W (Cork) 500km NW 1y 0m 1d
Black-headed Gull			
3651356	Nestling	23-06-2006	Veluwemeer, Harderwijk: 52°22'N 5°37'E (Ijsselmeerpolders) The Netherlands
	Alive (c-r)	02-02-2020	Whitegate: 51°49'N 8°14'W (Cork) 949km W 13y 7m 10d
EZ13047	Adult	16-01-2016	Confidential Site in Essex: c. 51°32'N 0°31'E (Essex)
	Alive (c-r)	15-07-2018	Cork: 51°52'N 8°28'W (Cork) 620km W 2y 5m 29d
	Alive (c-r)	19-10-2018	Newport: 52°0'N 4°50'W (Pembrokeshire) 371km W 2y 9m 3d
	Alive (c-r)	24-09-2020	Cork City: 51°53'N 8°27'W (Cork) 619km W 4y 8m 8d
EY09064	Nestling	08-06-2013	Hosehill Lake: c. 51°25'N 1°4'W (West Berkshire)
	Alive (c-r)	14-02-2020	River Lee: 51°53'N 8°28'W (Cork) 515km W 6y 8m 6d
EK08024	Second-year	27-05-2010	Carr Vale: c. 53°13'N 1°18'W (Derbyshire)
	Alive (r-r)	21-10-2020	Cork City: 51°53'N 8°27'W (Cork) 506km WSW 10y 4m 24d
EA65564	Nestling	07-06-2020	Martin Mere, Burscough: 53°37'N 2°52'W (Lancashire)
	Alive (c-r)	29-03-2021	The Lough, Cork, Ireland: 51°52'N 8°29'W (Cork) 424km WSW 0y 9m 22d
EB42361	Adult	14-11-2012	The Lough, Cork City: 51°53'N 8°29'W (Cork)
	Freshly dead (hit by car)	30-03-2021	Vinderup: 56°28'N 8°43'E (Ringkøbing) Denmark 1,229km ENE 8y 4m 16d
HA00177	Nestling	16-06-2006	Kalviu Karjerai, Klaipėdos: 55°37'N 21°16'E Lithuania
	Alive (r-r)	02-01-2018	The Lough, Cork City: 51°53'N 8°29'W (Cork) 1,984km W 11y 6m 17d (Map)
5T82046	Nestling	31-05-2013	Lissewege: 51°18'N 3°12'E (West-Vlaanderen) Belgium

ST24144 2	Alive (r-r)	13-10-2021	Cork City: 51°53'N 8°27'W (Cork) 808km W 8y 4m 12d
	Nestling	21-06-2020	Kokkola, Keski-Pohjanmaa: 63°57'N 23°18'E (Vaasa) Finland
K10944	Alive (r-r)	28-11-2021	Kinsale: 51°42'N 8°31'W (Cork) 2,306km WSW 1y 5m 7d
	Nestling	11-06-2017	Killingen, Oslo: 59°54'N 10°39'E (Akershus) Norway
5T8204	Alive (c-r)	19-12-2021	Whitegate: 51°49'N 8°14'W (Cork) 1,476km WSW 4y 6m 8d
	First-year	02-01-1991	Zele-Heikant: 51°4'N 4°1'E (Oost-Vlaanderen) Belgium
AC3819	Alive (r-r)	15-12-2022	Cork City: 51°53'N 8°27'W (Cork) 870km WNW 31y 11m 13d
	Adult Male	01-11-2011	Sortedams Soe, Copenhagen: 55°40'N 12°34'E (København) Denmark
	Alive (r-r)	02-02-2022	The Lough, Cork City: 51°53'N 8°29'W (Cork) 1,444km W 10y 3m 1d
EZ33048	Nestling	20-06-2017	Elvanfoot: 55°25'N 3°39'W (South Lanarkshire)
	Alive (c-r)	22-11-2022	Glengarriff Harbour: 51°45'N 9°33'W (Cork) 564km SW 5y 5m 2d
EZ93146	Nestling	15-06-2021	Marsh Lane Reserve, near Hampton in Arden: 52°25'N 1°41'W (West Midlands)
	Alive (c-r)	03-10-2022	Cork City: 51°53'N 8°27'W (Cork) 466km W 1y 3m 18d
EA83657	Nestling	14-06-2022	Goats Island, Lough Ree, Co. Longford: 53°37'N 8°1'W (Longford)
	Alive (c-r)	18-08-2022	The Lough, Cork City: 51°53'N 8°29'W (Cork) 197km S 0y 2m 4d
6H3836	Adult Male	19-03-2009	Svanemollebugten, Copenhagen: 55°43'N 12°34'E (København) Denmark
	Alive (c-r)	05-09-2010	Mistley: 51°56'N 1°4'E (Essex) 864km WSW 1y 5m 17d
	Alive (c-r)	18-12-2010	Cork: 51°52'N 8°28'W (Cork) 1,446km W 1y 8m 29d
	Alive (c-r)	31-07-2011	Mistley: 51°57'N 1°4'E (Suffolk) 863km WSW 2y 4m 12d
EW6738 3	Alive (c-r)	08-10-2023	Mistley, River Stour: 51°56'N 1°4'E (Essex) 863km WSW 14y 6m 19d
	Alive (c-r)	29-11-2023	The Lough, Cork City: 51°53'N 8°29'W (Cork) 1,446km W 14y 8m 10d
	Nestling	13-06-2009	Lough Mask: 53°38'N 9°18'W (Mayo)
	Alive (c-r)	30-01-2023	Garinish Pier: 51°36'N 10°8'W (Cork) 231km SSW 13y 7m 17d
	EY21711	Nestling	29-06-2013
	Alive (c-r)	23-03-2020	Castle Semple Loch, Lochwinnoch: 55°47'N 4°37'W (Renfrewshire) 100km W 6y 8m 23d
	Alive (c-r)	09-09-2023	near Youghal: 51°57'N 7°50'W (Cork) 528km SW 10y 2m 11d

EZ02461	Nestling	20-06-2017	Elvanfoot: 55°25'N 3°39'W (South Lanarkshire)
	Alive (c-r)	25-09-2017	Lanark: 55°39'N 3°44'W (South Lanarkshire) 27km NNW 0y 3m 5d
	Alive (c-r)	23-06-2023	Clonakilty: 51°37'N 8°52'W (Cork) 547km SW 6y 0m 3d
EY21711	Nestling	29-06-2013	Broad Law, Moorfoot Hills: c. 55°46'N 3°3'W (Scottish Borders)
	Alive (c-r)	23-03-2020	Castle Semple Loch, Lochwinnoch: 55°47'N 4°37'W (Renfrewshire) 100km W 6y 8m 23d
	Alive (c-r)	09-09-2023	near Youghal: 51°57'N 7°50'W (Cork) 528km SW 10y 2m 11d
EP23338	Nestling	29-05-2019	Attenborough Nature Reserve: c. 52°54'N 1°13'W (Nottinghamshire)
	Alive (r-r)	14-01-2023	The Lough, Cork City: 51°53'N 8°29'W (Cork) 506km W 3y 7m 16d
EZ66042	Nestling	21-06-2022	Ibsley Water, Blashford Lakes: 50°52'N 1°47'W (Hampshire)
	Alive (c-r)	31-08-2022	Chew Valley Lake: 51°19'N 2°38'W (Bath and N. E. Somerset) 78km NW 0y 2m 10d
	Alive (c-r)	01-02-2023	Horgan's Quay, Cork City: 51°54'N 8°27'W (Cork) 476km WNW 0y 7m 11d
EZ93018	Nestling	21-06-2018	Confidential Site in West Midlands: c. 52°25'N 1°40'W (West Midlands)
	Alive (c-r)	03-07-2018	Olton Mere: 52°25'N 1°48'W (West Midlands) W 0y 0m 12d
	Alive (c-r)	29-11-2023	Atlantic Pond, Cork City: 51°53'N 8°25'W (Cork) 464km W 5y 5m 8d
EA30752	First-year	07-12-2018	Atlantic Pond, Cork City: 51°53'N 8°25'W (Cork)
	Alive (r-r)	19-06-2023	Leliesingel, Groningen: 53°13'N 6°33'E (Groningen) The Netherlands 1,023km ENE 4y 6m 12d
Mediterranean Gull			
FS63061	Adult	01-06-2006	le Platier, Oye-Plage: 50°58'N 2°1'E (Pas-de-Calais) France
	Alive (c-r)	03-09-2019	Whitegate: 51°49'N 8°13'W (Cork) 717km WNW 13y 3m 2d
EZ04801	Adult	11-08-2015	Lough Beg, Ringaskiddy: 51°49'N 8°19'W (Cork)
	Alive (r-r)	13-04-2017	Zwillbrocker Venn, Flamingo-Insel: 52°1'N 6°42'E (Munster) Germany 1,030km E 1y 8m 2d
	Caught by ringer	25-03-2018	Berendrecht: 51°21'N 4°19'E (Antwerpen) Belgium 874km E 2y 7m 14d
	Alive (r-r)	21-07-2019	Erith Pier, London: 51°27'N 0°13'E (Greater London) 587km E 3y 11m 10d
IA13337 7	Adult Male	25-05-2016	Riether Werder: 53°42'N 14°16'E (Mecklenburg - Vorpommern) Germany
	Alive (c-r)	23-10-2016	Cork Port: 51°53'N 8°27'W (Cork) 1,540km W 0y 4m 28d
	Alive (c-r)	17-08-2019	Passage West: 51°52'N 8°20'W (Cork) 1,533km W 3y 2m 23d

E915893	Nestling	27-05-2009	Kieldrecht: 51°16'N 4°10'E (Oost-Vlaanderen) Belgium
	Alive (c-r)	04-10-2020	Whitegate: 51°49'N 8°14'W (Cork) 860km W 11y 4m 7d
EY76671	Nestling	28-06-2017	Langstone Harbour: 50°50'N 0°56'W (Hampshire)
	Alive (c-r)	30-07-2018	Camel Estuary: 50°32'N 4°53'W (Cornwall) 278km W 1y 1m 2d
	Alive (c-r)	19-04-2019	Pett Level, Sussex: 50°54'N 0°40'E (East Sussex) 118km E 1y 9m 22d
	Alive (c-r)	16-09-2020	Garretstown Beach: 51°38'N 8°34'W (Cork) 536km WNW 3y 2m 19d
IA18856 0	Nestling	08-06-2018	Kiesgrube, Rehbach: 51°16'N 12°16'E (Leipzig) Germany
	Alive (c-r)	02-02-2020	Whitegate: 51°49'N 8°14'W (Cork) 1,419km WNW 1y 7m 25d
FS95493	Nestling	29-06-2012	Polder Sebastopol, Barbatre: 46°55'N 2°9'W (Vendee) France
	Alive (c-r)	31-07-2013	Confidential Site: c. 52°7'N 9°43'W (Kerry) 799km NW 1y 1m 2d
	Alive (c-r)	19-02-2014	Whitegate, Cork Harbour: 51°49'N 8°13'W (Cork) 699km NW 1y 7m 21d
	Alive (c-r)	10-05-2014	Marbury, Northwich: 52°59'N 2°40'W (Cheshire & Wirral) 676km N 1y 10m 11d
	Alive (c-r)	03-09-2015	Ballinskelligs: 51°48'N 10°15'W (Kerry) 799km NW 3y 2m 5d
	Alive (c-r)	18-03-2016	Lady's Island Lake: 52°12'N 6°22'W (Wexford) 660km NNW 3y 8m 18d
	Alive (c-r)	23-01-2017	Whitegate, Cork Harbour: 51°49'N 8°13'W (Cork) 699km NW 4y 6m 25d
	Alive (c-r)	28-08-2020	Ballinskelligs: 51°48'N 10°15'W (Kerry) 799km NW 8y 1m 30d
	Alive (c-r)	18-03-2021	Brockholes Quarry: 53°45'N 2°37'W (Lancashire) 760km N 8y 8m 17d
	Alive (c-r)	07-11-2021	Gerahies Fish Processing Plant (Sheeps Head): 51°38'N 9°35'W (Cork) 752km NW 9y 4m 9d
5416987	Nestling	15-06-2013	Zwillbrocker Venn, Vreden: 52°1'N 6°42'E (Munster) Germany
	Alive (c-r)	03-10-2021	Whitegate: 51°49'N 8°14'W (Cork) 1,024km W 8y 3m 18d
3745960	Adult	12-05-2021	Ventjagersplaten, Haringvliet: 51°42'N 4°19'E (Zuid-Holland) The Netherlands
	Alive (c-r)	21-11-2021	Whitegate: 51°49'N 8°14'W (Cork) 865km W 0y 6m 9d
E929704	Nestling	17-05-2011	Antwerpen: 51°13'N 4°22'E (Antwerpen) Belgium
	Alive (c-r)	14-11-2022	Whitegate: 51°49'N 8°14'W (Cork) 874km W 11y 5m 28d
5431684	Adult Female	29-05-2021	Pionierinsel Luhe, Elbe, Grunendeich: 53°34'N 9°36'E (Lunenburg) Germany
	Alive (c-r)	14-11-2022	Whitegate: 51°49'N 8°14'W (Cork) 1,216km W 1y 5m 16d

EX52494	Nestling	16-06-2015	Confidential Site: c. 52°27'N 6°34'W (Wexford)
	Alive (c-r)	29-11-2023	Togher, Cork City: 51°52'N 8°29'W (Cork) 149km WSW 8y 5m 13d
3745965	Adult	12-05-2021	Ventjagersplaten, Haringvliet: 51°42'N 4°19'E (Zuid-Holland) The Netherlands
	Alive (c-r)	14-02-2023	Rostellan: 51°50'N 8°11'W (Cork) 861km W 1y 9m 2d
FN74296	Nestling	26-05-2012	Zb. Topola, Topola, Dolnoslaskie: 50°28'N 16°54'E (Dolnoslaskie) Poland
	Alive (c-r)	02-08-2013	Rostellan: 51°50'N 8°11'W (Cork) 1,755km WNW 1y 2m 7d
EY76625	Nestling	28-06-2017	Langstone Harbour: 50°50'N 0°56'W (Hampshire)
	Alive (c-r)	04-01-2018	Coroso Beach, Ribeira, A Coruña: 42°34'N 8°59'W (Coruna) Spain 1,100km SW 0y 6m 7d
	Alive (c-r)	07-01-2018	Ave River/Estuary: 41°20'N 8°44'W (Porto) Portugal 1,210km SSW 0y 6m 10d
	Alive (c-r)	16-06-2018	Confidential Site: c. 51°54'N 8°50'W (Cork) 521km WNW 0y 11m 19d
	Alive (c-r)	26-08-2018	Kinnegar Beach, Belfast Lough: 54°38'N 5°51'W (Down) 535km NW 1y 1m 29d
EY76716	Nestling	25-06-2018	Langstone Harbour: 50°50'N 0°56'W (Hampshire)
	Alive (c-r)	04-10-2018	Waterrock: 51°55'N 8°11'W (Cork) 514km WNW 0y 3m 9d
E940753	Adult	20-05-2018	Kallo: 51°15'N 4°16'E (Oost-Vlaanderen) Belgium
	Alive (c-r)	04-08-2018	Slatty Bridge, Carrigtwohill: 51°54'N 8°16'W (Cork) 869km W 0y 2m 15d
6J3405	Nestling	16-06-2013	Sneum Sluse, Esbjerg: 55°25'N 8°36'E (Ribe) Denmark
	Alive (c-r)	24-07-2018	Confidential Site: c. 51°54'N 8°50'W (Cork) 1,186km WSW 5y 1m 8d
IA17794 0	Nestling	15-06-2018	Kiesgrube Lobnitz Gravel Pit: 51°34'N 12°28'E (Leipzig) Germany
	Alive (c-r)	11-08-2018	Marsh Lane Nature Reserve, Berkswell: 51°24'N 1°41'W (Wiltshire) 978km W 0y 1m 27d
	Alive (c-r)	11-08-2018	The Lough, Cork City: 51°53'N 8°29'W (Cork) 1,439km W 0y 1m 27d
Common Gull			
EZ04855	Adult	13-11-2018	Togher, Cork City: 51°52'N 8°29'W (Cork)
	Freshly dead (injury)	30-08-2019	Craigmillar Castle Road: 55°55'N 3°9'W (Edinburgh) 569km NE 0y 9m 17d
5190174	Nestling	05-07-2019	Equinor Hovedkontor, Stavanger: 58°52'N 5°43'E (Rogaland) Norway
	Alive (c-r)	06-02-2020	The Lough, Cork City: 51°53'N 8°29'W (Cork) 1,185km SW 0y 7m 1d

6184165	Adult Male	25-07-2020	Sandbotnan, Yttervær: 68°4'N 13°7'E (Nordland) Norway
	Alive (c-r)	05-03-2022	Clones Strand: 52°44'N 6°8'W (Wicklow) 1,993km SW 1y 7m 8d
	Alive (c-r)	17-12-2022	Jacob Island, Cork Harbour: 51°51'N 8°23'W (Cork) 2,148km SW 2y 4m 22d
6184165	Adult Male	25-07-2020	Sandbotnan, Yttervær: 68°4'N 13°7'E (Nordland) Norway
	Alive (c-r)	05-03-2022	Clones Strand: 52°44'N 6°8'W (Wicklow) 1,993km SW 1y 7m 8d
	Alive (c-r)	17-12-2022	Jacob Island, Cork Harbour: 51°51'N 8°23'W (Cork) 2,148km SW 2y 4m 22d
	Alive (c-r)	11-01-2023	Cork City Docks: 51°54'N 8°26'W (Cork) 2,146km SW 2y 5m 17d

Great Black-backed Gull

MA2912 8	Nestling	25-06-2011	Ireland's Eye: c. 53°24'N 6°4'W (Dublin)
	Alive (c-r)	26-08-2018	Cork Harbour: 51°54'N 8°18'W (Cork) 225km SW 7y 2m 1d
	Alive (c-r)	07-04-2019	Howth Harbour: c. 53°23'N 6°3'W (Dublin) 3km 7y 9m 13d
	Alive (c-r)	12-08-2020	Cork Harbour: 51°54'N 8°18'W (Cork) 225km SW 9y 1m 18d
MA3988 3	Nestling	26-06-2020	Mullion Island: c. 50°0'N 5°16'W (Cornwall)
	Alive (c-r)	07-10-2020	Schull: 51°30'N 9°31'W (Cork) 344km WNW 0y 3m 11d
MA2498 1	Nestling	19-06-2019	Ynys Gwylan Islands: 52°47'N 4°41'W (Gwynedd)
	Alive (c-r)	23-10-2020	Ring, Clonarkilty: 51°36'N 8°51'W (Cork) 311km WSW 1y 4m 4d
MA4698 0	Nestling	08-07-2021	Skokholm Island: 51°41'N 5°17'W (Pembrokeshire)
	Alive (c-r)	16-02-2022	Unnamed Site: 48°1'N 4°37'W (Finistere) France 411km S 0y 7m 8d
	Alive (c-r)	30-04-2023	Gann Estuary, Dale: 51°42'N 5°10'W (Pembrokeshire) 9km ENE 1y 9m 22d
	Alive (c-r)	13-07-2023	Somerville, Carrigaline: 51°48'N 8°21'W (Cork) 213km W 2y 0m 5d
MA6105 8	Nestling	10-06-2023	Dalkey Island: 53°16'N 6°5'W (Dublin)
	Alive (c-r)	01-10-2023	Youghal Bay: 51°57'N 7°50'W (Cork) 189km SW 0y 3m 21d
	Alive (c-r)	26-11-2023	Dungarvan Bay: 52°5'N 7°36'W (Waterford) 168km SW 0y 5m 16d

Herring Gull

GV70346	Nestling	01-07-2018	Leinster House: 53°20'N 6°15'W (Dublin)
	Alive (c-r)	13-01-2019	Cork City: 51°54'N 8°28'W (Cork) 219km SW 0y 6m 12d

GY20551	Nestling	26-06-2021	Calf of Man: 54°2'N 4°49'W
	Alive (c-r)	21-03-2022	Cuskinny Marsh, Cobh: 51°51'N 8°15'W (Cork) 337km SW 0y 8m 23d
Yellow-legged Gull			
EA58686 4	Nestling	02-06-2020	Carteau, Port-Saint-Louis-Du-Rhone: 43°22'N 4°51'E (Bouches-du-Rhone) France
	Alive (c-r)	24-09-2020	Cork City: 51°53'N 8°27'W (Cork) 1,374km NW 0y 3m 22d
	Alive (c-r)	03-07-2022	Horgan's Quay, Cork City: 51°55'N 8°30'W (Cork) 1,373km NW 2y 1m 1d
	Alive (c-r)	11-07-2023	Cork City: 51°55'N 8°30'W (Cork) 1,374km NW 3y 1m 9d
Lesser Black-backed Gull			
GA0127 7	Nestling	28-06-2000	Ballycotton Island: 51°49'N 8°0'W (Cork)
	Sick (natural causes)	01-03-2010	Reserva Natural Das Dunas de Sao Jacinto, Aveiro: 40°40'N 8°45'W (Aveiro) Portugal 1,241km S 9y 8m 1d
GH8260 7	Nestling	16-06-1991	Cape Clear Bird Observatory: 51°25'N 9°30'W (Cork)
	Alive (r-r)	02-01-2016	Praia Do Paraíso, Matosinhos: 41°13'N 8°43'W (Porto) Portugal 1,137km S 24y 6m 17d
	Alive (r-r)	29-08-2019	Matosinhos: 41°10'N 8°40'E (Porto) Portugal 1,798km ESE 28y 2m 13d
GV87688	Nestling	28-06-2018	Lough Ree, Co. Longford: 53°38'N 8°1'W (Longford)
	Alive (c-r)	28-09-2018	Espinho Beach, Portugal: 41°0'N 8°38'W (Aveiro) Portugal 1,407km S 0y 3m 0d
	Alive (c-r)	22-09-2019	Blackrock Castle, Cork City, Co. Cork, Republic of Ireland: 51°54'N 8°24'W (Cork) 197km S 1y 2m 25d
GY08227	Nestling	03-07-2019	Cape Clear Bird Observatory: 51°29'N 9°29'W (Cork)
	Alive (c-r)	24-09-2019	Reserve de Chantaloup, L'Ile d'Olonne: 46°33'N 1°47'W (Vendee) France 784km SE 0y 2m 21d
	Alive (c-r)	09-11-2019	Karraspio, Lekeitio: 43°21'N 2°29'W (Vizcaya) Spain 1,043km SSE 0y 4m 6d
GV64924	Nestling	23-06-2018	Cape Clear Bird Observatory: c. 51°28'N 9°31'W (Cork)
	Alive (c-r)	10-11-2018	Praia da Vieira, Portugal: 39°52'N 8°58'W (Leiria) Portugal 1,288km S 0y 4m 18d
	Alive (c-r)	14-01-2020	Vila Do Conde, Portugal: 41°20'N 8°44'W (Porto) Portugal 1,128km S 1y 6m 22d
	Alive (c-r)	11-12-2020	Hayle Estuary: 50°11'N 5°25'W (Cornwall) 321km ESE 2y 5m 18d
GV87558	Nestling	15-06-2018	Lough Ree, Co. Longford: 53°38'N 8°1'W (Longford)
	Alive (c-r)	09-10-2019	Fonte da Telha, Costa da Caparica, Portugal: 38°34'N 9°11'W (Setúbal) Portugal 1,679km S 1y 3m 24d

	Alive (c-r)	24-06-2020	Arthur's Quay, Limerick City, Republic of Ireland: 52°39'N 8°37'W (Limerick) 117km SSW 2y 0m 9d
	Alive (c-r)	27-10-2020	Kennedy Quay, Cork City, Co. Cork, Republic of Ireland: 51°53'N 8°27'W (Cork) 197km S 2y 4m 12d
GY32688	Nestling	01-07-2023	Copeland Bird Observatory: 54°41'N 5°31'W (Down)
	Alive (c-r)	17-09-2023	Horgan's Quay, Cork City: 51°54'N 8°27'W (Cork) 367km SSW 0y 2m 16d
GY07187	Nestling	23-06-2019	Lambay Island: 53°29'N 6°0'W (Dublin)
	Alive (c-r)	04-02-2020	Matosinhos Beach: 41°10'N 8°41'W (Porto) Portugal 1,382km S 0y 7m 12d
	Alive (c-r)	06-06-2020	Limerick / Luimneach: 52°40'N 8°37'W (Limerick) 197km WSW 0y 11m 14d
	Alive (c-r)	05-10-2020	Cork City: 51°54'N 8°28'W (Cork) 242km SW 1y 3m 12d
	Alive (c-r)	26-08-2021	Togher, Cork City: 51°52'N 8°29'W (Cork) 245km SW 2y 2m 3d
	Alive (c-r)	22-05-2022	Grange Castle Bus Park: 53°19'N 6°26'W (Dublin) 34km WSW 2y 10m 29d
	Alive (c-r)	14-08-2022	Togher, Cork City: 51°52'N 8°29'W (Cork) 245km SW 3y 1m 22d
	Alive (c-r)	15-07-2023	Grange Castle Bus Park: 53°19'N 6°26'W (Dublin) 34km WSW 4y 0m 22d
	Alive (c-r)	23-11-2023	Togher, Cork City: 51°52'N 8°29'W (Cork) 245km SW 4y 5m 0d
FJ77362	Nestling	22-06-2022	Lough Ree, Co. Longford: 53°38'N 8°1'W (Longford)
	Freshly dead	18-09-2023	Benduff, Roscarberry, Co. Cork, Republic of Ireland: 51°36'N 9°4'W (Cork) 239km SSW 1y 2m 27d
GV87782	Nestling	28-06-2018	Lough Ree, Co. Longford: 53°38'N 8°1'W (Longford)
	Alive (c-r)	19-10-2018	Matosinhos Beach, Matosinhos, Portugal: 41°10'N 8°41'W (Porto) Portugal 1,386km S 0y 3m 21d
	Alive (c-r)	22-09-2019	Kennedy Quay, Cork City, Co. Cork, Republic of Ireland: 51°53'N 8°27'W (Cork) 197km S 1y 2m 25d
	Alive (c-r)	28-06-2020	O'Callaghans Strand, Limerick, Republic of Ireland: 52°39'N 8°38'W (Limerick) 117km SSW 2y 0m 0d
	Alive (c-r)	20-01-2023	Cork City: 51°53'N 8°27'W (Cork) 197km S 4y 6m 23d
GY21769	Nestling	01-07-2021	Cape Clear Bird Observatory: c. 51°28'N 9°31'W (Cork)
	Alive (c-r)	18-08-2021	Cedeira: 43°39'N 8°3'W (Coruna) Spain 876km S 0y 1m 17d
	Alive (c-r)	01-11-2021	Matosinhos Beach, Matosinhos, Portugal: 41°10'N 8°41'W (Porto) Portugal 1,145km S 0y 4m 0d
	Alive (c-r)	08-04-2023	Esmelle Beach, Ferrol: 43°32'N 8°17'W (Coruna) Spain 887km S 1y 9m 7d
	Alive (c-r)	20-08-2023	Les Grandes Prises, Ars-En-Re: 46°13'N 1°31'W (Charente-Maritime) France 825km SE 2y 1m 19d
GV86161	Nestling	23-06-2018	Cape Clear Bird Observatory: 51°29'N 9°29'W (Cork)

	Alive (c-r)	02-10-2020	Terschelling, The Netherlands: 53°25'N 5°24'E (Terschelling) The Netherlands 1,032km ENE 2y 3m 9d
	Alive (c-r)	10-10-2020	Juist, Weser-Ems, Germany: 53°40'N 6°59'E (Weser-Ems) Germany 1,139km ENE 2y 3m 17d
	Alive (c-r)	14-10-2020	Scheveningen, The Netherlands: 52°6'N 4°16'E (Zuid-Holland) The Netherlands 948km E 2y 3m 21d
	Alive (c-r)	25-07-2021	Ostend Harbour: 51°13'N 2°55'E (West-Vlaanderen) Belgium 862km E 3y 1m 2d
	Alive (c-r)	22-06-2023	Borkum Island: 53°36'N 6°41'E (Weser-Ems) Germany 1,119km ENE 4y 11m 30d
6005287	First-year Female	21-02-2022	Jaen: 37°55'N 3°37'W (Jaen) Spain
	Alive (c-r)	24-07-2023	Togher, Cork City: 51°52'N 8°29'W (Cork) 1,597km NNW 1y 5m 3d
GV64870	Nestling	22-06-2018	Cape Clear Bird Observatory: 51°25'N 9°31'W (Cork)
	Alive (c-r)	23-09-2018	la Chaume, Les Sables d'Olonne, Vendee, France: 46°29'N 1°48'W (Vendee) France 785km SE 0y 3m 1d
333609	Nestling	14-07-2016	Brimnes, Kjalarnes: 64°13'N 21°49'W (Kjósarsýsla) Iceland
	Alive (r-r)	20-10-2018	Kennedy Quay, Cork City: 51°52'N 8°27'W (Cork) 1,576km SE 2y 3m 6d
GY08283	Nestling	03-07-2019	Cape Clear Bird Observatory: 51°29'N 9°29'W (Cork)
	Alive (c-r)	15-10-2019	Quarteira: 37°4'N 8°6'W (Faro) Portugal 1,606km S 0y 3m 12d
	Alive (c-r)	22-10-2019	Cortelha: 37°16'N 7°58'W (Faro) Portugal 1,584km S 0y 3m 19d
	Alive (c-r)	16-07-2021	Lower Compton Landfill: 51°26'N 1°58'W (Wiltshire) 521km E 2y 0m 13d
GY42145	Nestling	01-07-2021	Lough Ree, Co. Longford: 53°38'N 8°1'W (Longford)
	Alive (c-r)	27-08-2021	Horgans Quay, Cork City, Co. Cork, Republic of Ireland: 51°54'N 8°27'W (Cork) 197km S 0y 1m 26d
GV86121	Nestling	23-06-2018	Cape Clear Bird Observatory: 51°29'N 9°29'W (Cork)
	Alive (c-r)	18-04-2021	R/V Miguel Oliver: 44°10'N 8°33'W (Bay of Biscay) Bay of Biscay 816km S 2y 9m 26d
GY21677	Nestling	01-07-2021	Goat Islands: 51°29'N 9°36'W (Cork)
	Alive (c-r)	04-09-2021	off Cabo Vilan, Muxia, A Coruna, Spain: 43°11'N 9°21'W (North Atlantic Ocean) North Atlantic Ocean (other parts) 923km S 0y 2m 3d
	Alive (c-r)	12-11-2021	Praia da Caparica, Caparica: 38°38'N 9°14'W (Setúbal) Portugal 1,427km S 0y 4m 11d
GY08196	Nestling	03-07-2019	Cape Clear Bird Observatory: c. 51°28'N 9°31'W (Cork)
	Alive (c-r)	30-07-2022	Hayle Estuary: 50°11'N 5°25'W (Cornwall) 321km ESE 3y 0m 27d

Sandwich Tern

DD5646 7	Nestling	12-06-2010	Lady's Island: 52°12'N 6°23'W (Wexford)
	Dead (leg only)	15-07-2010	Ballyrisode Stand, Toormore: 51°29'N 9°41'W (Cork) 240km WSW 0y 1m 3d
DT74708	Nestling	20-06-2022	Cemlyn: 53°24'N 4°30'W (Isle of Anglesey)
	Alive (c-r)	17-09-2022	Clonakilty Bay: 51°36'N 8°51'W (Cork) 355km WSW 0y 2m 28d
DD4085 1	Nestling	07-06-2005	Lady's Island: 52°12'N 6°23'W (Wexford)
	Caught by ringer	21-08-2018	L.Beg, Ringaskiddy: 51°49'N 8°18'W (Cork) 138km WSW 13y 2m 14d
DE54563	Nestling	19-06-2012	Cockle Island, Groomsport: 54°40'N 5°37'W (Down)
	Caught by ringer	05-09-2018	L.Beg, Ringaskiddy: 51°49'N 8°18'W (Cork) 364km SSW 6y 2m 17d
Common Tern			
SV64189	Nestling	12-06-2005	Lough Beg, Ringaskiddy: 51°49'N 8°19'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	15-06-2020	Ringaskiddy: 51°49'N 8°19'W (Cork) 2km 15y 0m 3d
ST25230	Nestling	25-06-2015	Rockabill: 53°35'N 6°0'W (Dublin)
	Caught by ringer	14-07-2020	Ringaskiddy : 51°50'N 8°19'W (Cork) 250km SW 5y 0m 19d
SR10709	First-year	29-06-2012	Marino Point, Belvelly, Cork Harbour: 51°53'N 8°19'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	30-03-2021	la Somone: 14°28'N 17°4'W (Senegal) Senegal 4,229km SSW 8y 9m 1d
SR10723	First-year	29-06-2012	Marino Point, Belvelly, Cork Harbour: 51°53'N 8°19'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	03-04-2022	la Langue de Barbarie: 15°55'N 16°30'W (Senegal) Senegal 4,062km SSW 9y 9m 5d
ST60411	Nestling	21-06-2018	Ringaskiddy: 51°49'N 8°19'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	06-04-2022	la Langue de Barbarie: 15°55'N 16°30'W (Senegal) Senegal 4,057km SSW 3y 9m 16d
SR10630	Nestling	25-07-2011	Ringaskiddy: 51°49'N 8°19'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	07-06-2023	Raffeen: c. 51°50'N 8°21'W (Cork) 3km 11y 10m 13d
ST60491	First-year	21-08-2018	L.Beg, Ringaskiddy: 51°49'N 8°18'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	03-04-2023	la Langue de Barbarie: 15°55'N 16°30'W (Senegal) Senegal 4,055km SSW 4y 7m 13d
SR21626	Nestling	29-06-2023	Ringaskiddy Port: 51°50'N 8°19'W (Cork)
	Alive (c-r)	07-12-2023	Kartong - Fishing Village: 13°4'N 16°45'W (Gambia) The Gambia .km 0y 5m 8d
ST60165	First-year	28-08-2016	L.Beg Ringaskiddy: 51°49'N 8°18'W (Cork)

	Freshly dead	28-05-2023	Markermeer: 52°34'N 5°22'E (Ijsselmeerpolders) The Netherlands 936km E 6y 9m 0d
ST45780	Nestling	27-06-2018	Ynys Feirig, Rhosneigr: 53°13'N 4°32'W (Isle of Anglesey)
	Long dead	25-08-2018	Ballymacoda Estuary: 51°54'N 7°54'W (Cork) 272km WSW 0y 1m 29d
ST79037	Nestling	10-07-2018	Rockabill: 53°35'N 6°0'W (Dublin)
	Caught by ringer	05-09-2018	L.Beg, Ringaskiddy: 51°49'N 8°18'W (Cork) 251km SW 0y 1m 26d
Guillemot			
R12318	Nestling	18-06-2000	Great Saltee Island: 52°7'N 6°36'W (Wexford)
	Freshly dead	15-02-2021	Garretstown: 51°37'N 8°35'W (Cork) 147km WSW 20y 7m 28d
Barn Owl			
GC97829	Nestling Male	16-07-2009	Milltown: 52°11'N 9°40'W (Kerry)
	Freshly dead (hit by car)	02-07-2010	Lissavard: 51°33'N 8°56'W (Cork) 80km SE 0y 11m 16d
GY26392	Nestling Female	01-07-2020	Confidential Site in Cork: c. 51°55'N 8°4'W (Cork)
	Dead (hit by car)	05-11-2022	Near Mitchelstown: c. 52°0'N 8°21'W (Cork) 16km NW 2y 4m 4d
Peregrine			
GR38678	Nestling	22-05-2014	Site Confidential, near Barking: c. 51°32'N 0°5'E (Greater London)
	Dead	23-03-2023	Cobh: 51°50'N 8°13'W (Cork) 576km W 8y 10m 1d
Penduline Tit			
NDC584	Adult Male	28-03-2023	Lough Beg, Ringaskiddy: c. 51°54'N 8°50'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	15-10-2023	Donges: 47°18'N 2°1'W (Loire-Atlantique) France 677km SE 0y 6m 17d
Sand Martin			
ALR4814	First-year	23-06-2022	Owenahincha: 51°34'N 8°59'W (Cork)
	Caught in nestbox	11-07-2023	Harper's Island, Cork Harbour: 51°54'N 8°18'W (Cork) 60km NE 1y 0m 18d
Willow Warbler			
HH1664 6	Adult	01-06-2019	Sore Merkeskog, Utsira: 59°18'N 4°52'E (Rogaland) Norway
	Caught by ringer	05-07-2019	Cape Clear: 51°25'N 9°30'W (Cork) 1,258km SW 0y 1m 4d

JLJ130	First-year	01-09-2019	Keelnacronagh West, Enniskeane: 51°45'N 8°55'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	14-04-2020	Bardsey Island: 52°45'N 4°47'W (Gwynedd) 305km ENE 0y 7m 13d

Chiffchaff

LVL 437	First-year	22-10-2019	Nanjizal, Lands End: 50°3'N 5°41'W (Cornwall)
	Caught by ringer	16-11-2019	Owenahincha: 51°34'N 8°59'W (Cork) 287km NW 0y 0m 25d

KNH080	First-year	20-03-2019	Calf of Man: c. 54°3'N 4°48'W
	Freshly dead (hit glass)	23-04-2020	Newberry, Mallow: 52°7'N 8°42'W (Cork) 338km SW 1y 1m 3d

LRR441	First-year	21-10-2020	Owenahincha: 51°34'N 8°59'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	04-04-2021	Walsey Hills, Salthouse: 52°57'N 1°3'E (Norfolk) 702km ENE 0y 5m 14d

NLL051	First-year	23-09-2022	Owenahincha: 51°34'N 8°59'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	11-10-2022	Sherpa Marsh, Velator, Braunton: 51°5'N 4°10'W (Devon) 340km E 0y 0m 18d

Sedge Warbler

T971608	Adult	16-05-2010	Cape Clear Bird Observatory: 51°26'N 9°30'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	21-08-2010	Tour Aux Moutons, Donges: 47°19'N 2°4'W (Loire-Atlantique) France 707km SE 0y 3m 5d

S391735	First-year	01-08-2018	Lytchett Bay, Poole Harbour: 50°43'N 2°2'W (Dorset)
	Caught by ringer	18-06-2019	Cape Clear: 51°25'N 9°30'W (Cork) 529km WNW 0y 10m 17d

AJB1303	First-year	08-08-2018	Ballard Down: 50°37'N 1°56'W (Dorset)
	Caught by ringer	16-06-2019	Lough Beg, Ringaskiddy: 51°48'N 8°19'W (Cork) 463km WNW 0y 10m 8d

ALE7285	First-year	24-07-2019	Lough Beg, Ringaskiddy: 51°48'N 8°19'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	01-08-2019	Llangorse Lake: c. 51°55'N 3°15'W (Powys) 348km E 0y 0m 8d

ALE7333	First-year	24-07-2019	Lough Beg, Ringaskiddy: 51°48'N 8°19'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	03-08-2019	Nanjizal, Lands End: 50°3'N 5°41'W (Cornwall) 269km SE 0y 0m 10d

AVF2446	First-year	22-09-2019	Owenahincha: 51°34'N 8°59'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	03-10-2019	Trunvel, Treogat: 47°52'N 4°21'W (Finistere) France 529km SE 0y 0m 11d

AHL4326	Juvenile	26-06-2020	Owenahincha: 51°34'N 8°59'W (Cork)
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	Caught by ringer	07-08-2020	Shorne Marshes, Gravesend: 51°26'N 0°25'E (Kent)	652km E	0y 1m 12d
AHL4321	Juvenile	26-06-2020	Owenahincha: 51°34'N 8°59'W (Cork)		
	Caught by ringer	29-07-2020	Squire's Down: 50°58'N 2°21'W (Dorset)	466km E	0y 1m 3d
AHL4574	First-year	14-09-2020	Owenahincha: 51°34'N 8°59'W (Cork)		
	Caught by ringer	22-09-2020	Nanjizal, Lands End: 50°3'N 5°41'W (Cornwall)	287km SE	0y 0m 8d
AJJ2239	First-year	01-08-2020	Lough Beg, Ringaskiddy: 51°48'N 8°19'W (Cork)		
	Caught by ringer	10-08-2020	Mars-Ouest, Sant-Philbert-De-Grand-Lieu: 47°7'N 1°40'W (Loire-Atlantique) France	709km SE	0y 0m 9d
ARN9151	First-year	24-07-2021	Lough Beg, Ringaskiddy: 51°48'N 8°19'W (Cork)		
	Caught by ringer	11-08-2021	Nanjizal, Land's End: 50°3'N 5°41'W (Cornwall)	270km SE	0y 0m 18d
ALR4105	First-year	08-08-2021	Owenahincha: 51°34'N 8°59'W (Cork)		
	Caught by ringer	21-08-2021	Cabanot, Audenge: 44°40'N 1°1'W (Gironde) France	966km SE	0y 0m 13d
ARN9181	First-year	31-07-2021	Lough Beg, Ringaskiddy: 51°48'N 8°19'W (Cork)		
	Caught by ringer	11-08-2021	Noyant, Soulaire-Et-Bourg: 47°33'N 0°31'W (Maine-et-Loire) France	733km SE	0y 0m 11d
ARN9140	First-year	24-07-2021	Lough Beg, Ringaskiddy: 51°48'N 8°19'W (Cork)		
	Caught by ringer	10-08-2021	St Ouens Pond, Jersey: 49°12'N 2°13'W (Jersey) Channel Islands	520km ESE	0y 0m 17d
ALR4255	First-year	03-09-2021	Owenahincha: 51°34'N 8°59'W (Cork)		
	Caught by ringer	05-05-2022	Teifi Marshes: 52°4'N 4°38'W (Ceredigion)	305km ENE	0y 8m 2d
AAV7521	First-year	17-07-2022	Lough Beg, Ringaskiddy: 51°48'N 8°19'W (Cork)		
	Caught by ringer	27-07-2022	Donges: 47°18'N 2°1'W (Loire-Atlantique) France	677km SE	0y 0m 10d
BVB6207	First-year	22-08-2023	Clogheen Marsh, Clonakilty: 51°35'N 8°53'W (Cork)		
	Caught by ringer	02-09-2023	Sint Jan-in-Eremo: 51°16'N 3°34'E (Oost-Vlaanderen) Belgium	865km E	0y 0m 11d
S730718	Juvenile	31-07-2018	Lough Beg, Ringaskiddy: 51°48'N 8°19'W (Cork)		
	Caught by ringer	14-08-2018	Squire's Down: 50°58'N 2°21'W (Dorset)	424km E	0y 0m 14d
S730688	First-year	24-07-2018	Lough Beg, Ringaskiddy: 51°48'N 8°19'W (Cork)		
	Caught by ringer	06-08-2018	Nanjizal, Lands End: 50°3'N 5°41'W (Cornwall)	269km SE	0y 0m 13d
Z200999	First-year Male	23-08-2014	Nanjizal, Lands End: 50°3'N 5°41'W (Cornwall)		

	Caught by ringer	04-07-2018	Lough Beg, Ringaskiddy: 51°48'N 8°19'W (Cork) 269km NW 3y 10m 11d
Reed Warbler			
AXL2002	Adult	28-05-2020	Nanjizal, Lands End: 50°3'N 5°41'W (Cornwall)
	Caught by ringer	08-06-2020	Sherpa Marsh, Velator, Braunton: 51°5'N 4°10'W (Devon) 160km NE 0y 0m 11d
	Caught by ringer	26-06-2020	Owenahincha: 51°33'N 8°56'W (Cork) 287km NW 0y 0m 29d
ARJ1632	First-year	25-08-2019	Nanjizal, Lands End: 50°3'N 5°41'W (Cornwall)
	Caught by ringer	25-07-2021	Owenahincha: 51°33'N 8°56'W (Cork) 287km NW 1y 11m 0d
17977793	First-year	13-08-2023	Lier: 51°7'N 4°34'E (Antwerpen) Belgium
	Caught by ringer	12-09-2023	Cape Clear Bird Observatory: 51°26'N 9°30'W (Cork) 980km W 0y 0m 30d
9854222	First-year	02-09-2021	Réserve Ornithologique du Teich - Roselière Est, le Teich: 44°37'N 1°1'W (Gironde) France
	Caught by ringer	21-09-2021	Cape Clear: 51°25'N 9°30'W (Cork) 984km NW 0y 0m 19d
ALR4946	Juvenile	29-07-2022	Owenahincha: 51°33'N 8°56'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	26-08-2022	Chenal, Chenac-Saint-Seurin-D'uzet: 45°30'N 0°49'W (Charente-Maritime) France 903km SE 0y 0m 28d
Blackcap			
X743882	First-year Male	22-09-2009	Pett Level, Sussex: 50°54'N 0°40'E (East Sussex)
	Dead (hit by car)	16-05-2010	Cape Clear: 51°25'N 9°30'W (Cork) 712km W 0y 7m 24d
16170144	First-year Male	31-08-2019	Bolland: 50°40'N 5°46'E (Liege) Belgium
	Caught by ringer	24-10-2019	Cape Clear Bird Observatory: 51°26'N 9°30'W (Cork) 1,070km WNW 0y 1m 23d
KYL223	First-year Female	26-09-2019	Ballinphellic: 51°50'N 8°37'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	21-09-2020	Erme Valley At Harford: c. 50°25'N 3°55'W (Devon) 364km ESE 0y 11m 26d
AVJ8382	First-year Female	18-09-2021	Cape Clear Bird Observatory: 51°26'N 9°30'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	28-10-2023	Laguna Primera de Palos, Palos de la Frontera: 37°10'N 6°52'W (Huelva) Spain 1,597km S 2y 1m 10d
15205949	Full-grown Male	16-09-2017	Neerharen: 50°55'N 5°40'E (Limburg) Belgium
	Caught by ringer	19-03-2018	Cape Clear: 51°25'N 9°30'W (Cork) 1,059km W 0y 6m 3d
Goldcrest			
NBC703	First-year Female	13-09-2020	Yarnolds Plantation, near Kingshill Farm: c. 52°9'N 2°21'W (Worcestershire)

	Caught by ringer	11-09-2021	Cape Clear Bird Observatory: 51°26'N 9°30'W (Cork) 498km W 0y 11m 29d
Blackbird			
7643224	First-year Male	30-10-2018	Revtangen, Klepp: 58°45'N 5°30'E (Rogaland) Norway
	Freshly dead	18-12-2020	Eyrecourt: 52°10'N 8°8'W (Cork) 1,126km SW 2y 1m 18d
LJ64226	First-year Male	13-11-2016	Cape Clear Bird Observatory: 51°26'N 9°30'W (Cork)
	Freshly dead	13-04-2018	Austre Liknesvei, Åkrehamn, Karmøy: 59°13'N 5°12'E (Rogaland) Norway 1,265km NE 1y 5m 0d
Fieldfare			
A811670	Adult Female	27-06-2022	Orimattila, Päijät-Häme: 60°45'N 26°7'E (Uusimaa) Finland
	Freshly dead (bird of prey)	23-03-2023	Enniskeen: 51°44'N 8°55'W (Cork) 2,374km W 0y 8m 24d
Song Thrush			
RW5834	Adult Female	27-07-2007	Slapton Ley: c. 50°17'N 3°38'W (Devon)
6	Long dead	21-08-2010	Fota Wildlife Park, Carrigtwohill: 51°54'N 8°13'W (Cork) 367km WNW 3y 0m 25d
Dipper			
RW7785	Nestling Female	15-04-2003	Rathduff: 52°0'N 8°35'W (Cork)
8	Caught by ringer	22-04-2010	Waterloo, Blarney: 51°57'N 8°34'W (Cork) 6km SSE 7y 0m 7d
RL92349	Nestling	07-04-2019	Riverstick, near Cork City: 51°50'N 8°30'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	25-11-2021	Dripsey: 51°54'N 8°45'W (Cork) 19km WNW 2y 7m 18d
Duncock			
NZ28555	Juvenile	22-08-2017	Frimley Station Lakes: 51°18'N 0°44'W (Surrey)
	Caught by ringer	24-03-2022	Cape Clear Bird Observatory: 51°26'N 9°30'W (Cork) 608km W 4y 7m 2d
Chaffinch			
AKF9204	First-year Female	04-02-2019	Distillery Fields: 51°53'N 8°29'W (Cork)
	Freshly dead (hit glass)	(04-06-2019)	Kanturk: 52°10'N 8°54'W (Cork) 43km NW 0y 4m 0d
AVF2684	First-year Female	22-11-2019	Owenahincha: 51°34'N 8°59'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	26-11-2020	Tremough Campus, Penryn: 50°10'N 5°7'W (Cornwall) 314km ESE 1y 0m 4d

Common Rosefinch

TX22136	Adult Male	29-05-2021	Confidential Site: c. 51°51'N 4°53'W (Pembrokeshire)
	Freshly dead (cat)	05-06-2022	Ballycotton: 51°50'N 7°55'W (Cork) 188km W 1y 0m 7d

Greenfinch

AFB9622	First-year	25-03-2018	Harty's Quay, Rochestown: 51°52'N 8°23'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	20-03-2020	Ballinphellic: 51°50'N 8°37'W (Cork) 17km WSW 1y 11m 24d
TS23440	Adult Female	07-05-2017	Cape Clear Bird Observatory: 51°26'N 9°30'W (Cork)
	Alive (r-r)	26-12-2018	Brittas Pines, Ardfield, Clonakilty: 51°34'N 8°54'W (Cork) 44km ENE 1y 7m 19d

Goldfinch

AVA4847	Adult Male	22-04-2019	Cape Clear Bird Observatory: 51°26'N 9°30'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	14-05-2023	Lundy Island: 51°9'N 4°39'W (Devon) 338km E 4y 0m 22d
AFF9741	Adult Female	30-01-2019	Dunmore Lawn, Cork City: 51°53'N 8°27'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	30-01-2021	le Fougeray, Moulins: 48°0'N 1°22'W (Ille-et-Vilaine) France 666km SE 2y 0m 0d
AAF1784	Adult Female	30-10-2021	St Austell: 50°20'N 4°46'W (Cornwall)
	Freshly dead	29-03-2022	Audley Cove, Ballydehob: 51°30'N 9°27'W (Cork) 352km WNW 0y 4m 27d

Siskin

AAD562 1	First-year Female	16-03-2018	Chilworth: 51°12'N 0°32'W (Surrey)
	Caught by ringer	26-02-2020	Ballinphellic: 51°50'N 8°37'W (Cork) 565km W 1y 11m 10d (Map)
ALE7070	First-year Male	16-02-2019	Healy's Bridge, near Ballincollig: 51°54'N 8°34'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	05-11-2020	Leswalt, Stranraer: 54°56'N 5°5'W (Dumfries and Galloway) 407km NNE 1y 8m 20d
X469869	Adult Male	26-10-2017	Cape Clear Bird Observatory: 51°26'N 9°30'W (Cork)
	Caught by ringer	20-02-2018	University of Ulster, Coleraine: 55°8'N 6°40'W (Londonderry) 453km NNE 0y 3m 25d
S217540	First-year Female	27-03-2016	Ffynnon Gro, Llanfynydd: 51°55'N 4°6'W (Carmarthenshire)
	Caught by ringer	16-02-2018	Ballinphellic: 51°50'N 8°37'W (Cork) 310km W 1y 10m 20d

References

Robinson, R.A., Leech, D.I. & Clark, J.A. (2025) The Online Demography Report: Bird ringing and nest recording in Britain & Ireland in 2024. BTO, Thetford (<http://www.bto.org/ringing-report>)

Addendum

Wilson's Storm-Petrel *Oceanites oceanicus*

County Total	pre-1959	1959-2018	2019-2023
544	0	309	235

About 216 birds were recorded in 2019–23: 2019 (12), 2020 (6), 2021 (84) 2022 (47) and 2023 (67). Most birds (158), were recorded on pelagic trips from Reen Pier and Baltimore, within the 12nm (22.2km) limit. There was a significant increase in records from land based seawatching, including: Ballycotton (3), Cape Clear (8), Galley Head (22), Mizen Head (6), Seven Heads (8) and Toe Head (12). Birds were recorded in June (3), July (78), August (60) and September (75), between 5 June and 18 September. The highest counts included - seventy-three on a pelagic on 5 September 2021, twenty on a pelagic on 21 August 2022 and eighteen from Galley Head on 7 July 2023.